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Aim and Scope of the Journal

Globalization and modernization are causing a constant change in coexistent and intercultural relationships. The daily interconnectedness around the world makes it increasingly clear that people of different religious and cultural backgrounds need to continually and consistently research what makes for unity in diversity across the board. Over the years, a lack of intercultural integration and communication has resulted in promoting tribalism, and ethnoreligious and political disunity in many human communities. It is, therefore, imperative for thorough, unbiased, and sound academic research to promote religious, social, political, and economic integration in the face of religious and cultural diversity. To this end, *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication* aims to address practical issues that make for unity and national integration for sustainable development through a peer-reviewed academic journal that serves as a venue for publicizing research findings on subjects relating to religious and intercultural studies. The journal creates a forum for researchers to publish their research works on all aspects of religious and intercultural studies. It will pursue the promotion of critical research and original scholarship on issues related to all aspects of religious and intercultural studies generally – historical, hermeneutical, exegetical, theoretical, empirical, or comparative.

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From the Editors

Dear Colleagues and Esteemed Academics,

As we embrace the opportunities of the digital age, we are proud to mark a significant milestone in our department's journey with the launch of our first academic journal: *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication (LCJRIC)*. The journal represents not only our commitment to scholarly excellence but also our determination to ensure that our research reaches a wider, global audience. Through this journal, we are establishing a vital digital presence that will enhance our contributions to academic discourse.

Development, in all its forms, is fundamentally concerned with the holistic transformation of individuals, fostering both their physical and spiritual well-being. Religion plays a pivotal role in this process, serving as a source of social capital that contributes to the overall development of society. The exploration of religion, theology, and intercultural communication is essential in addressing the diverse challenges our world faces today.

Religion serves multiple functions within society, including:

- Giving meaning and purpose to life,
- Reinforcing social unity and stability,
- Acting as a social control mechanism for behaviour,
- Promoting physical and psychological well-being, and
- Motivating individuals to work towards positive social change.

It is with great pride that we celebrate the successful publication of the first two volumes of the *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication*, the official journal of the Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria.

We extend our deepest gratitude to the leadership of our university: The Pro-Chancellor and Chairman of the Council, Prof. Jide Owoeye; the Vice Chancellor, Prof. Kabiru A. Adeyemo; the Registrar, Dr. Oyebola Ayeni; the Provost of the Postgraduate College, Prof. Afolakemi Oredein; the Dean of Arts, Prof. Anjola Robbin; and the Dean of Education, Prof. Abidemi D. Odeleye. I also want to acknowledge our dedicated editors – Dr. Oluwaseun Afolabi, Dr. Emmanuel Adetunji, Dr. Peter Oderinde, Dr. Joseph Dayo Makanjuola, Rev'd. Abiodun Owode – and especially the Corresponding Editor, Dr. Adebayo Afolaranmi, for his expertise and invaluable contributions.

I sincerely appreciate the exceptional work of our reviewers, who have meticulously evaluated the papers, ensuring the highest standards of scholarship. Congratulations to all the authors whose papers have been published. Your contributions are integral to our academic community.

Finally, I wish to extend my heartfelt thanks to our Chief Editorial Consultant, Prof. Anjola Robbin, and all of you for your continued dedication to advancing scholarship. Together, let us celebrate the maiden edition of the *Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication* and our collective achievements.

Congratulations to us all!

Ayo Atowoju
Editor in Chief

Impacts of Religion on Political Activities in Nigeria, 1999-2023

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Abstract

Two major religions alongside others are practiced in Nigeria, namely Islam and Christianity. Religious politics is fast becoming the order in the country's political activities. Religion has been a strong determining factor for governance bureaucracy and the electoral process in Nigeria. Hence, the impacts of religious politics in Nigeria could be both positive and negative. This paper focuses on the positive and negative influences of religion on politics since the inception of the democratic government in Nigeria in 1999. The historical analysis method was embarked upon to access facts and authentic information. Findings show that politics of religion is detrimentally pronounced in Nigeria's political activities, it is also discovered that the impact of religion on politics breeds animosity and marginalization. The research concludes that politics should be separated from religious influences. The research also recommends ways of harmonizing the political interests of the two major religions for national development. The adherents of both major religions in Nigeria, Islam, and Christianity, should seek the common good for peaceful co-existence and a serene political atmosphere. There must be mutual understanding and a common goal in the governance of the nation. Nigerian politicians and clerics should desist from the use of platforms of religion to promote personal political interest. They should not be agents of disharmony in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Politics, Religion, Nigeria, Muslim, Christianity*

Introduction

Nigeria is one of the colonized countries of West Africa, the nation obtained her independence on October 1, 1960 from the British

Government. Nigeria is a secular state as enshrined in the country's constitution. As a multi-ethnicity and secular society, the citizens enjoy freedom of worship. It is glaring from the records of a previously conducted census that Nigeria is predominantly Christians and Muslims (Gbadegesin, 5 2022). There are other traditional religions in Nigeria but most are not duly recognized as the two major dominant religions earlier mentioned. This paper aimed at the need to treat all citizens equally irrespective of their religious affiliation, tribe, and academic achievements. The paper will employ the use of historical methods to acquire facts and figures. It should be noted that religion and politics are strongly becoming indivisible for the adherents in political realms. The challenge of political leaders galvanizing support for their faiths and co-adherents is a major factor that is polarizing the nation. The impact of religion on the socio-cultural relationship is strongly pronounced in governance activities.

Impacts of Politics of Religion in Nigeria

The intersection of politics and religion has been a contentious and complex issue throughout history. Leaders often use religious beliefs to garner support, influence policies, and shape societal norms. This intertwining can lead to both positive outcomes, such as fostering moral values, and negative consequences, including discrimination and conflict. Balancing these influences is crucial for a harmonious society. This is called the politics of religion.

Politics of religion in Nigeria has led especially Christians and Muslims to continually engage in rivalry of fifth columnists, as such many incompetent leaders were produced who juicily rode on the platform of politics of religion to assume political offices. Gbadegesin (2022) expressed, "Of all vocations, politics is the most consequential for human well-being. It sets the norms and standards for others in light of their bearing on human well-being. It also establishes the principles and standards of distributive and penal justice so there is peace and security in the political community. Politics is architectonic. And to that extent, it is the most noble vocation." Due to the awareness of the liberating

power in politics, religion is therefore seen as a tool in the hands of several greedy individuals to achieve their political ambitions since 1999 in Nigeria.

The politics of religion has posed a threat to the national unity, progress, and development of Nigeria. When the 2023 national election in Nigeria was fast approaching, some political parties settled for Muslims/Christians, Christians/Muslims, and Muslim /Muslim candidacy for political offices in all tears of the governance. Politics of religion has made Nigerians aware that one out of all the registered political parties in Nigeria – All Progressive Congress (APC) – has settled for a Muslim/Muslim ticket for her presidential candidates. This is not the first time Nigeria will have a Political Party with a Muslim/Muslim Ticket. The candidacy of MKO Abiola and Babagana Kingibe of the Social Democratic Party (SDP) during the 1993 election was a Muslim/Muslim Ticket and nobody raised any objection. But Religion, ethnicity, and money are very strong factors that influence Nigerian politics today, this study focuses on the politics of religion.

Politics of Religion in the New Dawn of Democracy

Religion has played significant roles in Nigerian politics since the inception of Nigeria as a republic on October 1, 1963. This paper only considered the religious influences on Nigerian politics since 1999. Shortly after the historic transition to a democratic regime in 1999, politics of religion became more pronounced in Nigerian democracy. The first news that brought Nigerian politics to the religious limelight was the introduction of Sharia. Governor Ahmed Yerima introduced the Sharia Islamic legal system in Zamfara State in October 1999. Yerima earned widespread support and acceptance from the people of Zamfara and Muslims all over the Nation for his promise to implement Sharia as a major strategy to address widespread societal decadence in Zamfara State. Islamic clerics effectively mobilized for Yerima and further legitimated his government given the Sharia factor, and they were also

well recognized by the regime and integrated into strategic aspects of the state's public service. Chanting of *Allahu Akbar* (God is Great) was most popular at major political rallies in the state, all these successfully gave an Islamic coloration to the regime.

Christians saw the drive towards the implementation of Sharia by the northern states as a clear-cut political strategy by the Hausa Muslims to destabilize the regime of a 'born-again' Christian President Olusegun Obasanjo. For instance, Obiechina (2001) quoted Archbishop Ola Makinde, the then Chairman of the Abuja chapter of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) who said, "Part of the aim of the introduction of the political Sharia in Nigeria is to prevent or crush the spread of Christianity in the North. Another aim is to pull down the government of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo which the political Sharia apostles see as a government headed by an infidel."

This particularly came on the heels of the Christian identity Obasanjo exhibited immediately after his release from prison following some years in the political imprisonment of the erstwhile Nigerian head of state, General Sani Abacha. He was well received by the Christian community as a 'born-again evangelical'. Obasanjo was further seen as a 'virtual messiah' who had come through a divine plan to be the chosen candidate of the Christians who felt since 1979 been sidelined from occupying the office of president, except for the 84-day interim regime of Ernest Shonekan. In addition, Obasanjo widely opened the doors of the Presidential Villa, the Aso Rock, to Christian leaders to pray for Nigeria and also built a Christian Chapel in the Villa.

Similarly, this was also the case with Ibrahim Shekarau of Kano state of the same political party as Yerima. The Islamic clerics were observed to have played a prominent role in the emergence of Shekarau as the governor of the state and also in his government. They vigorously campaigned for him during the elections because of his agenda for Sharia and also headed major state agencies such as the Shura Committee, Zakat and Husbi Commission, and the Hisbah board established in the spirit of Sharia after he emerged as the governor of the state between 2003 and 2011 (Olajide, 2003).

“Sharia-crazy” soon generated a widespread uproar across the nation immediately after it assumed a northern policy following its adoption by eleven (11) other states after Zamfara. Christians in the North suspected the move as another attempt by the Muslim majority to finally silence their voice in the scheme of affairs. Christians were therefore strongly opposed to the move and all its denominations across the country organized a series of sensitization programmes on the implications of the new regime of Sharia to the Christian worshippers in various churches. This created an effective avenue to mobilize Christians against the programme. For instance, the CAN made announcements to all churches in Kaduna for a mass protest after the state government under the leadership of Ahmad Makarfi adopted the Sharia system in 2000 (Olajide, 2003).

Obasanjo’s major defense policy upon assumption into office was also enough to generate much suspicion from the Muslim community. Obasanjo restructured the Nation’s Armed Forces in such a way that the Muslim Hausa-Fulani top military officers who had hitherto dominated the defense cum power segment of the nation since the 1960s were systematically edged out in favour of the Christians. The Muslim elites in the North therefore felt insecure with this restructuring ‘which in turn led to an almost reflexive adoption of a “tribe” mentality’.

However, when it was becoming clear that the pendulum of power was again swinging to the side of the North, the heightened tension of Sharia sharply reduced. But when the winds of change altered, Obasanjo was among the first individuals to publicly announce the ‘death’ of Sharia in the North. At the end of his regime in 2007, he told a congregation of Christians at an annual event that he warned the Sharia actors in the North that: If this kind of Sharia was from God, it would survive but that if it was politically motivated it will fizzle out. Truly, by 2007, when Umaru Musa Yar’adua of the North emerged as the President, political Sharia had died a ‘natural death’ in most of the states that embraced it, except for Kano.

The case of Kano is particularly different because of the background of the governor who was a Muslim cleric. Hence, Shekarau, the governor of

the state, vigorously and outstandingly pursued Sharia to address moral and developmental challenges in the state via the establishment of the Zakah Commission and Hisbah Board. The Zakah Commission being an agency responsible for the collection of tax from the rich as stipulated in the religion of Islam, had a broad programme for poverty alleviation.

This includes the provision of medical assistance, working capital to local entrepreneurs, vocational training to the unemployed youths, and assistance to the aged. The Hisbah Board as an Islamic paramilitary agency of the state works with government and the police to promote peace in the society. It also addressed the malaise of girl-child trafficking and marital crisis (Anwar, 2004). However, Sharia still played a critical role in the politics of Zamfara state at the end of Yerirna's administration in 2007. His successor, Aliyu Shinkafi, who decamped to the People's Democratic Party (PDP) during his reign and clashed with Yerirna, was rejected in the 2011 elections mostly for his poor implementation of Sharia. As a result, the new governor of the state, Abubakar Yari Abdul-Aziz, displaced the incumbent in the governorship elections due to his alliance with Yerirna and his promise for the re-introduction of Sharia. Politics of religion again featured prominently in the political process that informed the emergence of the circumstantial presidency of Goodluck Jonathan in 2010 and the general elections that followed in April 2011. It began with the failed attempt of Olusegun Obasanjo to unconstitutionally prolong his regime in a process dubbed the 'third term agenda' in 2006. As a result, Obasanjo was left with no choice but to quickly arrange for a successor that would better protect the legacies of his regime.

Taking into consideration a 'gentleman' agreement of power rotation between the North and South in his party, - the PDP, his best choice was a relatively corrupt-free and disciplined northern Muslim – Umaru Musa Yar'adua – who had successfully served as a two-term governor in Katsina State. In an election categorized as the most controversial in the political history of Nigeria, Yar'adua emerged as the President of the country in April 2007 (Suberu, 2007). Yar'adua was ill, a patient of acute heart disease-pericarditis, he was unable to hold onto power and

effectively run his government. This gave his closest aides otherwise known as the ‘Cabal’ (mostly from the North) the ample advantage to wield much influence during his regime. Given the eventual intensity of his illness and the reluctance of his influential aides to hand over power to a Christian from the South, a Saudi Arabian hospital was strategically chosen as a secret presidential residence. This arrangement actually worked out as planned as the Saudi Arabian authorities on religious solidarity proved supportive of Yar’adua and his government in his last days while receiving treatment at the hospital despite a series of local and international pressures on Riyadh.

At the heat of this tension, the Save Nigeria Group, a civil society group under the headship of a Lagos-based Pentecostal pastor, Tunde Bakare, was at the centre of an intense protest directed at the National Assembly to terminate the reign of dying Yar’adua and declare Jonathan as the President. It is also noteworthy that only some selected religious leaders were allowed to see the ailing President, apart from his closest aides upon his return to the country. Hence, the Imams were given special privilege to see him and inform the public about his state of health, and it was only after the Christian community objected to this special privilege that some of their representatives were permitted to visit and pray for him. And later, at the declaration of Jonathan as the President of Nigeria, given the death of Yar’adua in May 2010, the relief and applaud from the Christian community was quite obvious. For instance, Reverend Matthew Kuka, a prominent Christian cleric in Nigeria, was among the first individuals who read religious meanings to the process that produced the presidency of Jonathan. He prophesized that it was a ‘monumental act of divine epiphany’ and ‘this man’s (Goodluck Jonathan) rise has defied logic and anyone who attempts to explain it is tempting the gods (Olajide, 2004). Already irked by this development, it also became an open affront on the Hausa-Fulani Muslims when Jonathan with the strong backing of Obasanjo and other influential southerners declared to run for presidency under the platform of PDP in the 2011 election.

To the Hausa-Fulani northerners, it was a complete violation of an existing 'zoning formula' which was supposed to be in favour of the North, because Yar'adua was unable to complete his two-term regime while Obasanjo, had an uninterrupted two-term presidency between 1999 and 2007. This controversy heated the polity, particularly in the build-up to the PDP presidential primaries. Thus, the North teamed up under the platform of the Northern Elders Political Forum (NPLF) to produce a 'Northern Consensus Candidate' to neutralize the chances of Jonathan as the incumbent in the primaries.

They relied on this strategy to create the best opportunity for the emergence of a northern candidate under the platform of PDP for the presidential election. Their outright loss to Jonathan at the PDP primaries following the poor outing of Atiku Abubakar as the 'Consensus Candidate' at the event therefore required a new scheming; the shopping for an alternative northern candidate outside the PDP. Their choice was General Muhammad Buhari, a former Head of State who was said to be notable for political discipline and zero-tolerance for corruption in the nation, Muhammad Buhari, who had earlier openly supported the Sharia cause, had been tagged a Muslim fanatic by many, 'especially the Christians. The political party he successfully floated for his presidential ambition after leaving the ANPP over unsettled ideological conflict, the Congress for Progressive Change (CPC), was also categorized as an Islamic northern party. This is particularly against the backdrop of the nature of supporters it attracted and the spread of the party which had more presence in the North and almost none in the South. CPC enjoyed the patronage of the Muslim masses, *almajiri* students, and Muslim clerics in the North who gave Buhari the epithet, Mai Gaskiya (the truthful one) as a mark of their high level of trust in him. Realizing his slim chances in the presidential race given the general perception of him being a Muslim fanatic, Buhari devised a pragmatic strategy of opening up to the Christian community by specially selecting Pastor Bakare as his running mate and on several occasions, paid official visits to influential Nigerian pastors.

Despite this attempt towards constructing a new identity for himself, Buhari could not be detached from his strong Islamic background going by the popularity and patronage he enjoyed from the Islamic institutions that were effectively explored to garner as much as possible votes for him. In what seems like a confirmation of the foregoing, Kanti Bello, a notable PDP stalwart, stated that the CPC adopted a strategy that “relied on religion as a weapon of campaign. The CPC used the Council of Ulama (Muslim clerics) in the North to campaign for Buhari, which portrayed him as a candidate of Muslim” (Yahaya, 2011). It is further reported that Jonathan’s supporters in the Muslim North despite being Muslims were considered working against the interest of Islam and enemies of the North given their affiliation with Jonathan’s PDP.

Goodluck Jonathan was also not far from the church for support and mobilization for his presidential ambition. The most visible and much debated of this was his visit to the Pentecostal’s Redeemed Christian Church of God in December 2010, where he knelt before the Church’s popular pastor, Pastor Enoch Adeboye, in the open glare for his prayers to succeed in the elections. Choosing that particular event to openly show his good relationship with the Christians is quite instructive. The event labelled the “Holy Ghost Night’ made the 2010 episode of an annual gathering of millions of Christians from all parts of the country as a programme of the Redeemed church to usher in a blessed new year.

In the same vein, a notable Pentecostal pastor, Paul Adefarasin of the House on the Rock Church in Lagos, was reported to have impressed it upon his followers that the political system had for long been dominated by the Muslims and there was the need for them to go all out for a Christian presidential candidate in the 2011 elections. The PM News reported thus: Adefarasin said that the polity has been Islamized for so long and Christians must wake up and pray against it. “Nigerians used to be the most educated people in the world until the likes of Abacha and Muritala Muhammed came and scattered our educational system to slow down the South so that the North can catch up, instead of speeding up the north” (Onapajo, 2012).

Hence, the 2011 elections appeared to be a political battle between the Muslims and the Christians as Jonathan and Buhari signified the major contenders of the presidential elections. The outcome of the elections confirms this observation. The votes reflected a voting pattern significantly determined by religion and ethnicity. Jonathan had a landslide victory in the Christian dominated areas of the South and also the Christian areas of the North otherwise known as the Middle-Belt region. This guaranteed him a landslide victory after winning 23 states in the country and polling 22, 495, 187 votes. He was rejected outright in the Muslim's 'Core North' where Buhari swept all the votes in its 12 states including Sokoto, Zamfara, Niger, Kano, Kebbi, Katsina, Bauchi, Kaduna, Jigawa, Borno, Gombe and Yobe (Onapajo, 2004) The intense violence that followed this development shall be discussed below. But it must be mentioned that there have been allegations and counter-allegations from both parties that massive rigging was perpetrated in favour of each of these two candidates in the regions that signify their support base given the religious and ethnic sentiments they enjoyed in these places. The CPC alleges in its petition to the Presidential Election Tribunal that the election was rigged in 20 states mostly in the South in favour of Jonathan. On the other hand, the PDP also forwarded the argument that there was widespread electoral fraud especially 'underage voting and religious intimidation' in the Muslim North in favour of Buhari.

Regional Religions Affiliations

As earlier mentioned, religious affiliation in Nigeria is strongly related to ethnicity with rather distinct regional divisions between ethnic groups. The northern states dominated by the Hausa and Fulani groups are predominantly Muslim while the southern ethnic groups have a large number of Christians. In the southwest, there are no predominant religions. The Yoruba tribe which is the majority ethnic group in the southwest practices Christianity, Muslim, and or the traditional Yoruba religion which centres on the belief in one Supreme God and several lesser deities. Many people include elements of traditional beliefs in

their own practice of Christianity or Islam. The Christian community is composed of Roman Catholics (the largest denomination). Methodists, Anglicans, Baptists, Presbyterians, and members of Evangelical and Pentecostal groups (Onapajo, 2012).

Conclusion

Religion is present in all dimension of human life, especially in Nigeria. It is so central that one may conclude that religion is life and life is religion in Nigeria. Just like any other African nation, Nigerians are so religious. Therefore, human life is possible only in a social and political setting. “Therefore, religious value occurs only in society which is a network of relationship in which human beings of all ages and both sexes live in groups and members of these groups share their respective cultures” (Oderinde, 2004). The relationship between religion and politics is evident in this study, given that, both religion and politics pertain to human life, then the need for peaceful co-existence and the need for authority and power is essential. Oderinde has adequately demonstrated the interrelationship between religion, society, and authority when he says:

Religion is related to society in several ways. Religion exists and it is practiced in society. As individual seeks for protection from their society, so also the adherents seek for protection from their religion. Both religion and society aim at satisfying man's physical, intellectual, moral and spiritual needs. All societies believe in supernatural beings and a supernatural life. These beliefs have effects on the lives of the people who are living. In both religion and society, there is an exercise of authority and power. Both religion and society have code of conduct for their members, religious institutions formulate doctrines, ethics, values and roles, which are integrated in the life of wider society (Oderinde, 2004).

Oderinde's observation of the mutual relationship between religion, society, and human beings has involved ethical dimensions, thus the coloration of our politics. Moreover, since Nigeria politicians in

particular and human kind in general express their religion in virtually all segments of life, their value, ethics and moral are informed by their religious convictions. In this regard, wisdom dictates that we listen to one another. It should be what religion forbids that the society forbids in politics and the society approves what religion approved in politics. Religious values are the same as moral values and there are no separate instructions for either as virtually the whole society is involved in the task of inculcating sound moral and religious values in the younger generation to ensure a healthy and disciplined society (Oderinde, 2004). Religion in Nigeria today has been devilled with politics of religious intolerance and disharmony culminating in wanton destruction of lives and property. For example, the religious clash between Christians and Muslims in October 2001 as reported by Daily Times claimed more than 200 lives, apart from property worth billions of naira destroyed in the crises, Dime (2019). Buttressing this further Oderinde cited Dr. Lateef Adegbite, the Secretary-General of the Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs declared in *The Daily Times* on October 1, 2001, that Nigeria has experienced in recent years, an excess of disharmony arising from religious and ethnic differences across the nation. Hardly has any area been spared in this regard (Oderinde, 2004).

Recommendations

Christians and Muslims no longer seem to be enjoying security and protection in Nigeria and Nigeria is not a Muslim or Christian State. Therefore, there should be rights and freedom for every individual in the country to practice the religion of his/her own interest. as enshrined in the Nigerian Constitution. This is the fundamental human right for every citizenry in the country.

1. Since there is a constitution and bye-laws of the nation, then the Government should adhere to the constitution by following it to deal with criminals. Whosoever kills in the name of religion should be arrested and prosecuted so far, every individual is having freedom to life.

2. The fact is that there are some Islamic and Christian leaders aiding and sponsoring the religious crisis in Nigeria, such people should be arrested and decisively dealt with.
3. The Christians and Muslims are to stand firm by their faith and maintain their solidarity with their brethren throughout the country; they are to live in peace and harmony with every individual citizen. They also need to defend their nation not based on their faith at any time.

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Embracing the Harmony: Exploring the Complementarity of Faith and Culture in the Context of Luke 10:38-42

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Abstract

This study explores the intricate relationship between faith and culture, arguing that they are complementary rather than mutually exclusive. The narrative in Luke 10: 38-42 reveals how Jesus' teachings and actions embody both spiritual and cultural significance. The study used hermeneutics and historical methods to analyze the cultural context of hospitality in the Jewish understanding of welcoming guests in their homes while highlighting how Jesus' presence in the home of Martha and Mary exemplifies the integration of faith and culture. The work revealed that Martha's hospitality and Mary's receptivity to Jesus' teachings are not mutually exclusive, rather complementary aspects of their faith. The study explores how Jesus' acceptance of Martha's hospitality and his teaching on the importance of listening to God's word (Luke 10: 38-42) affirm the interconnectedness of faith and culture. This study's findings suggest that faith and culture are not in tension but rather enrich each other, leading to a more profound understanding of God's work in the world. The paper concluded that embracing the complementarity of faith and culture enables believers to live out their faith in a more authentic and meaningful way, engaging with their cultural context in a manner that honours God. This paper, by exploring the complementarity of faith and culture, fosters a deeper understanding of how faith can nurture and shape the culture and how, in turn, culture

can enrich the faith, thereby leading to a more nuanced and compassionate expression of Christian living. This research contributes to the ongoing conversation on the interaction of faith and culture, encouraging believers to embrace the complementarity of these two aspects of human experience.

Keywords: Complementary, Culture, Faith, Harmony, Hospitality

Introduction

In human society, religion, faith and culture play important roles. For some, there is a dichotomy between religion and culture while for others the two are inseparable. In the Western world, civilization or modernity has grown to the point that sharp distinction is created between the two phenomena. In the Ancient Near East or the ancient Mesopotamia world, there is no much difference between religion and culture. This extends to the Arabian world where their culture is strictly their religion and vice –versa. Man has always lived through the age of his religion and faith, yet good and sincere examinations shows that the religion of man constitutes in the majority what has become his culture. His culture is always reflected in his religion or faith even in the case of a borrowed religion as we have in the case of Africa. It is obvious today that these two religions have influenced or became in a strict sense the culture of the people. The discuss in the episode of the encounter of Mary and Martha the two sisters, and Jesus is one that brings out a rumination on the issue of the interplay of faith and culture, while culture harbours faith, faith on the other hand prunes and complement culture.

Humanity directly or indirectly cannot do without these two phenomenal. This comes to play as Christ visited his people who welcomed him and him giving them a gift of faith. The interplay of culture and faith when properly handled works for an enrichment and completeness of humanity. This works, rather than confirming the erroneous interpretation of many preachers or some scholars being negative on their actions of one who projects the value of courtesy in the

beauty of culture, is confirming the positive aspect of the interplay of the gift of Jesus and the gift of his host.

Conceptual Clarification

What is Faith?

According to scholars, defining faith is nearly impossible because it means something different to each person. According to Hellwig, (1990) the term “faith” ranges in meaning from a general religious attitude on the one hand to personal acceptance of a specific set of beliefs on the other hand." However, considering the spiritual meaning of faith, it is considered to be believing in God, and in what Christ has done for mankind to make salvation possible, and then committing ourselves to Him. In the New World Encyclopedia Dictionary, faith is said to be from Greek- *pistis* and latin *fides*, and it connotes confidence, trust, and hope in God, a person, a community, tradition or locus of inspiration. It also simply means the strong belief in the doctrines of a religion based on spiritual conviction rather than proof. Meanwhile for this study, the working definition that will be adopted is, “faith being as allegiance to duty or a person.

In addition to what faith stand for, we have the following as various characteristics of faith;

- Faith is a grace, a supernatural gift of God,
- Faith is certain
- Faith seeks understanding
- Faith is not opposed to science
- Faith is necessary for salvation
- Grace enables faith
- Its faith is the beginning of eternal life.

From the above, it is important to mention that item 3 is cogent to the main issue under discussion: Faith seeks understanding; Mary sought for understanding through her allegiance to Jesus while Martha place emphasis on the cultural norms of hospitality. The question then is

which is more important? This will be addressed in the latter part of this work.

What is Culture?

It has been observed that culture has many definitions, and it affects everything people do in their society because of their ideas, values, attitudes, and normative or expected patterns of behavior. According to Hall (1976), culture is not genetically inherited, and cannot exist on its own, but is always shared by members of a society. Also, Hofstede (1980) defines culture as “the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group from another, which is passed from generation to generation, it is described as the changing all the time because each generation adds something of its own before passing it on. He went further to say that, it is usual that one’s culture is taken for granted and assumed to be correct because it is the only one, or at least the first, to be learned.

Different cultural groups think, feel, and act differently. Culture is also refers to as the cumulative deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relations, concepts of the universe, and material objects and possessions acquired by a group of people in the course of generations through individual This is indicated, as Geertz (2000) notes, by Clyde Kluckhohn’s account of culture as (1) “the total way of life of a people”; (2) “the social legacy the individual acquires from his group”; (3) “a way of thinking, feeling, and believing”; (4) “an abstraction from behaviour”; (5) a theory on the part of the anthropologist about the way in which a group of people in fact behave; (6) a “storehouse of pooled learning”; (7) “a set of standardized orientations to recurrent problems”; (8) “learned behaviour”; (9) a mechanism for the normative regulation of behaviour; (10) “a set of techniques for adjusting both the external environment and to other men.

Connection between Faith and Culture

Having given conceptual clarifications of faith and culture within the context of this paper, the question one may ask is what is the connection between culture and faith? Faith, according to Paul Cardinal, has a triple role vis-a-vis culture. Its first task is to acknowledge and admit as well as to accept and appreciate the values that are embodied in culture. There is something good in the worst of us, just as there is something bad in the best of us, for we have the strengths of our weaknesses and the weaknesses of our strengths.

Every culture has a deposit of values. Every culture has its own treasury of traditions. Every culture has riches and values that need to be cherished and cradled for growth. Such values could be for example the recognition of a Supreme Being, reverence for life, and respect for the environment. Faith, according to Poupard (1996), needs to acknowledge and admit the good that is in every culture, for all good, like truth, has but one Source, God Himself. But faith also needs to accept and appreciate the good that is embedded in culture. In fact, no faith is ever born in a void or in a vacuum. It is always conceived in the womb of culture; there it is born and there too it is nourished and grows. In other words, both culture and faith are inextricably connected and viewed from the lens of the passage chosen as a case study, if we do not give the present generation the fruits of the tree of cultural tradition of hospitality as exemplified by Martha, we will leave them malnourished and unable to bear faithful and fruitful witness, and unable to sustain the life of faith within their culture – starved spirit.

The Passage: Luke 10:38-42

It is a gospel story about two sisters from Bethany and who are they? Mary and Martha are two models of Christian devotion. Martha means 'lady of the house' while Mary means 'wise woman' or 'lady'. It is a Greek form of the Hebrew Miriam or Mariam. It was a popular name at the time of Jesus, perhaps because of the beautiful young Jewish princess Mariamme, married to King Herod the Great. They are pair of missionary but certainly as leaders, we know little about the background

of Martha, Mary and Lazarus. They may have been well-to-do orphans who had the management of their own lives, since there is no mention of their parents. Moreover, the eldest of the three, Martha, appeared to be in control of the household. They seemed to be not too affluent but comfortable enough. They had a house large enough to accommodate many people, as their hospitality to Jesus and his group of friends shows. The passage reads:

As Jesus and his disciples were on their way, he came to a village where a woman named Martha opened her home to him. She had a sister called Mary, who sat at the Lord's feet listening to what he said. But Martha was distracted by all the preparations that had to be made. She came to him and asked, "Lord, don't you care that my sister has left me to do the work by myself? Tell her to help me!" "Martha, Martha," the Lord answered, "you are worried and upset about many things, but few things are needed—or indeed only one. Mary has chosen what is better, and it will not be taken away from her."

Then what can one deduced from the passage?

This story as shown by different biblical writers is fraught with a tension that Christians have struggled with for years. It has been observed that that there are many voices in our culture trying to pit these two against each other. In short, we need to note that this story has often suffered from different interpretations with Mary becoming a character of all that is wrong with the life of busyness and distraction or what the medieval church called the active or working life of Martha, which was permitted but seen as inferior to the perfect life of contemplation. But the story must be read against the backdrop of Luke's gospel as a whole, where we have the work of hospitality, a vital form of cultural values.

Mary and Martha in that context are not enemies but sisters. Two sisters squabbling about household duties cannot reasonably be construed as a battle of incompatible modes of life. Martha's generous service is not minimized by Jesus but her worries show that her service needs to be grounded in Mary's kind of love for him. Together, the sisters embody the truth that faith and culture are intertwined realities.

Jesus points toward Mary, not as a rebuke to Martha but as a gentle reminder that leadership demands both the ability to listen and to act. Both are not at odds but form two parts of a whole. The point is not that activity like Martha's is bad. The choice Jesus discusses with Martha is between something that is good and something that is better. Life is full of tough choices, and Jesus is stressing the relative merits of good activities here.

Jesus commends the hearing of the word at his feet. To take time out to relate to Jesus is important. Jesus is not so much condemning Martha's activity as commending Mary's. He is saying that Mary's priorities are in order. To disciples Jesus says, "Sit at my feet and devour my teaching. There is no more important meal." But as is often the case when Jesus is asked to settle a dispute, he refuses to side with the one who asks that things be decided in a particular way (compare Lk 12:13; Jn 8:4-7). Yet, he responds tenderly and instructs in the process. The double address "Martha, Martha" indicates the presence of caring emotion; as such an address does elsewhere (6:46; 8:24; 13:34; 22:31). Jesus questions her not because of her activity but because of her attitude about it: "You are worried and upset about many things." By comparing what she is doing to what Mary is doing, she has injected unnecessary anxiety into the visit. "Only one thing is needed." With this remark Jesus sets priorities. "Mary has chosen what is better, and it will not be taken away from her."

Mary knew true hospitality is always in style. It doesn't seem that Martha was too worried. She eagerly invited Jesus in and showed Him the kind of authentic hospitality that throws the door wide and serves the best. Now, if this passage is considered critically, few things can be learnt from Mary and Martha which are:

1. Welcoming people into your home is a gift – a gift worth sharing, whether the place is pristine and decorated to perfection or not.
2. True hospitality wraps a person up in a grace hug and makes them feel special.
3. Our guests are important no matter their status and they often have something to offer too, giving them attention is a virtue.

Faith and culture as exemplified in the passage:

The question is, does the passage has anything to do with faith and culture, the answer is in the affirmative. In the passage one could see Mary as a woman of faith while Martha was more cultural. Both faith and culture needed to be embraced, even though one may think the best practice is to listen to the words as Mary does and not worried about the perishable meal but it should be noted that even though she showed hospitality, she is equally a woman of faith likewise Mary. The two actions in that passage are complementary and it should be upheld because Jesus in that context still needed to be taken care of and someone has to do that and doing that does not make the other person given to hospitality infidel and vice versa.

Also, whenever there is faith, there must be culture and when we see the decay of culture there will equally be decay of faith. Any work of culture which shines forth the goodness, truth and beauty is shining forth the truth of Christ. At the deepest level, we could say, the tree of cultural tradition is not merely a tree but it is the tree of life and faith, which is to say is inseparable from the God who gives life. Faith can improve people's values. Faith permeates our world, providing a moral and ethical compass for the majority of people.

As rightly pointed out by Pope Francis and with simple elegance, when you pray for the hungry then you feed them, that is how prayer works, just as a body without a spirit is dead, so also faith without works is dead. Jesus emphasizes this connection between faith and action when he declares, amen, I say to you, whatever you did for one of these least brothers of mine, you did for me, Matthew 25: 40. His focus on the spiritual life portrays no interest in otherworldly navel-gazing, but rather a deep interest in doing practical work shown (which is cultural) by Martha of Bethany: feeding hungry people, wiping running nose, taking care of sick people, loving people in simple acts of service which is nothing but an example of faith.

Also, it needs to be noted that there is a call to act too. While having faith and listening to the word is important, our response to that grace is equally crucial. When we act out grace or faith hospitality is equally

germane. In addition, it could be said that the emphasis on faith over cultural values has birthed church full of the corporal and spiritual works of mercy, works of arts, civilization and other wonders that have changed the world. When the church teems with Martha's doing good works and the world is richer, it would not be difficult for people to accept the works of salvation which is faith and main focus of Mary.

To simplify, this is frequently interpreted as spiritual values being more important than material business, such as preparation of food. There are many practical problems with this reading (who is going to move the chairs and tables after the Sunday service?) as well as personal ones (can I really justify my laziness by saying I was listening to Jesus?) and there has been some push back. Moreover, there is good research evidence which shows that Christians both feel they are expressing their faith most clearly when involved in practical action, and that this helps them learn and grow as disciples.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the case studies of Luke 10: 38-42 has revealed the complementary relationship between faith and culture. Through a thorough analysis of the cultural context of hospitality and the Jewish understanding of welcome, we have seen how Jesus' teachings and actions embody both spiritual and cultural significance. The findings of this study suggest that faith and culture are intertwined aspects of human experience, informing and enriching other. The story of Martha and Mary serves as a powerful example of how believers can embrace the complementarity of faith and culture, leading to a more authentic and meaningful expression of Christian living.

The implications of this research are far –reaching, encouraging believers to engage with their cultural context in a manner that honors God. By acknowledging the harmony between faith and culture, we can foster a deeper understanding of God's work, love and grace in our lives and in the world around us.

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Towards Understanding Ibadan Traditional and Religious Systems Before and After the Advent of Christianity

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Abstract

Long before the colonial interruption or the advent of Christianity in Ibadanland, the Yoruba people had been exhibiting their republican nature by relentlessly subverting their kingship institution through civil disturbances and rebellions. This made some groups of people to settle in what is now known as Ibadanland after the fall of Oyo Empire. This paper aims to briefly introduce the readers to the traditional and religious life in Ibadanland in the nineteenth century, the time of the advent of Christianity in the city, the political and administrative setting, and the religion of the people of Ibadanland on the eve of the advent of the Christian religion. The paper adopted historical research design to achieve this as systematic literature review was done on some literature about Ibadanland. It was found out that Ibadan people were traditional worshippers with *egúngún* (masquerade) and *Okebadan* as the major religious festivals of the people. Islam came before the Hinderers led some people to introduce Christianity to the people. Ibadanland has had a well-established traditional political and administrative system of Baale-in-Council that later metamorphosed to Olubadan-in-Council. There has been an almost seamless succession plan to the throne of Baale, now Olubadan, of Ibadanland. Olubadan has become the symbol of unity in Ibadanland as other institutions are mere agents of unity or catalysts for concretizing that unity. As recommendations, the strengths and the weaknesses in the traditional and

religious life of Ibadan people and administrative systems are to be revisited in the light of the advent of Christianity and modernization in the city.

Keywords: *Advent of Christianity in Ibadanland, Egúngún (masquerade), Ibadan political and administrative system, Ibadan Traditional and Religious Systems, Ibadanland, Okebadan, Olubadan*

Introduction

Ibadan is the capital of Oyo State. It is made up of mainly Yoruba-speaking people. It is the largest indigenous city in Nigeria (Adelekan, 2016). Ibadan city is the area occupied by the five 'urban' local government areas established in 1991, namely, Ibadan North, North East, Ibadan North West, Ibadan Southeast and Ibadan Southwest. Other additional rural local government areas that also constitute Ibadanland are Oluyole, Egbeda, Ona-ara, Akinyele, Lagelu, and Ido. The population of Ibadanland is about 4,004,316 (Ibadan Population 2024).

This paper aims to give a short introduction to the traditional and religious life in Ibadanland in the nineteenth century, the time of the advent of Christianity in the city, the geographical setting, the political and administrative setting, the economy, the social life, and the religion of the people on the eve of the advent of the Christian religion. The impact of Christianity on the traditional and religious system of the city will be explored as it is obtainable in this twenty-first century based on some recommendations at the end of the study.

Ibadan on the Eve of the Advent of Christianity

Unlike other towns deliberately founded and planned, Ibadan was a town of circumstance. The attributes of the founder of the site and stance of founding are all circumstantial and unprecedented. The town was founded three times and it was at the third attempt that constituted Ibadanland today. The founder, Lagelu-Oro Apata Maja, an appellation, was a popular warrior who out of zeal for war, left his town, Ile-Ife, to settle at a neutral ground between the forestland near Ijebu and Egba

and the grassland near Oyo (Tomori, n.d.). The area belonged to nobody and because of this neutrality, it was referred to as Eba-Odan, a place near grassland or Ebadan (for short) and Ibadan eventually. Before Lagelu arrived there, and because it was a no man's land, all kinds of people – vagabonds, outcasts, refugees, fugitives, runaways, touts, truants, delinquents, etc. made the place their abode and it suited them. As soon as Lagelu arrived, he was made the leader. The settlement expanded gradually and became popular. People streamed in and life was bustling (Awe, Ogundeji, & Ajayi, 2010).

Most historians have agreed that Ibadan's recorded history should be put at about 1820 and that the present settlement as we know is the third site. Ibadan was the kingpin of Yoruba warfare in the 19th century. Ibadan became a clear safe place for many people after the fall of the Oyo Empire. Ibadan benefited from the influx of refugees through a purposeful assimilatory system. Although the refugees came in discernible groups, they could not withstand the military strength of the first group led by Lagelu Oro-Apata Maye (Awe, Ogundeji, & Ajayi, 2010). Ibadan's geopolitical system and political economy are indisputably the product of that history already but lives and factors of ecology, geography, and culture. These as summarized hereunder have contributed to the phenomenal growth of the metropolis:

- i. Ibadan's military proneness building and sustaining an empire;
- ii. Blend of Ibadan metropolis and rural populace as the same people;
- iii. Toughness and ruggedness of the people;
- iv. Vegetational advantage-between forest and savannah;
- v. Locational modality;
- vi. Adequate water supply;
- vii. Expanse of land and well-organized traditional system;
- viii. Large population;
- ix. Security – physical and psychological;
- x. Ecological balance; and
- xi. Hospitality of the people of Ibadan to strangers and settling.

Livestock were kept in Ibadan to augment the income from earned farming activities. They also engaged in the activity of making livestock available for sacrifices and rituals during various festivities such as Egúngún, Oke-badan, and Ileya. Given the above factors that are conducive to sustainable growth and development, Ibadan metropolis has grown into a "megalopolis" which can be called a city-state by all standards.

The Nature of the Traditional Religion in Ibadan (especially the Egúngún Worship and Festival)

No one can precisely determine the religion of the settlers, but Akinyele (2011) reported that Lagelu brought masquerade (*egúngún*) from Ile-Ife. Masquerades were also identified with warriors and wars as they were used as strategies for victory apart from entertaining warlords. Consequently, it became a way of life, a ritual, a cultural festivity celebrated annually for about two weeks around June during the rainy season when food was plentifully available.

It was during this ceremony one year, when a masquerade was performing in the market that his clothes were accidentally stripped off giving opportunity to women and children to see his face, that trouble erupted. This was a taboo that could not be concealed. Ibadan was in trouble. Sango, the Alaafin of Oyo, getting to know, summoned other traditional rulers to war against Ibadan. For three years, Ibadan was besieged and the war raged on until Ibadan was devastated. Thus, it was recorded that the masquerade myth that was broken and destroyed in the first Ibadan settlement (Akinyele, 2011). It is believed that the spirit of the dead especially the old ones linger on and lives with their people. Therefore, children born after their death are named Babatunde or Iyabode, meaning, 'father or mother comes back'.

Yoruba people also believe that when old people die, they are no longer human but superhuman. Their death at old age has earned them super-humanity. of course, they are not gods or divinities, but revered like gods. It is believed that they have more power and can help and support people, give people favour, plead on people's behalf, support people's

endeavours, and defend them. These ancestors, heroes and heroines, and popular leaders are designated as '*ara orun*' meaning dwellers from heaven and they visit people occasionally as masquerades. Masquerades remind people that the ancestors of the people do not forget the people. They mimic the ancestors to give the impression that he is not just a masquerade but a real ancestor or father. The family of the ancestor jubilates amidst pomp and pageantry, eats and drinks, and makes merry during the festivity. The masquerade then advises and prays for all members of the family far and near. This festivity referred to as ancestral worship, has come to stay and is an annual event in Ibadan today as in any other Yoruba town. People from villages and hamlets come to town to jubilate.

Egúngún (masquerade) is a masking tradition used in the performance of funeral rites for the dead to ensure their perfect peace at rest (Akande, 2019). These rites are performed to curry the favour of the dead and make them happy with their survivors. Apart from using them as a strategy by warriors, masquerades entertain the living. They are used to rid the community of evil, like outbreaks of cholera, typhoid, measles, smallpox, and other diseases and disasters. They are also used against witches and other evil powers. Masquerade performances have become a consecrated festive reunion of the living and the dead and have turned out to be an annual festival. Each family clan has its own masquerade and they have different names. Notable among them are *Ajofoyinbo*, *Alarinjo*, *Ajangila*, *Ayelabola*, *Gelede*, *Atipako*, *Afidielegee*, *Alapansanpa*, *Eleeko*, *Dariagbon*, *Ferebiekun*, *Oloolu*, etc. They have their different drummers and dance *bata* or *gangan* drums.

Figure 1: *Egúngún* (Source: Akande, 2019)

At the festival, masquerades emerge from their sacred groves (*igbo igbale*) putting on a specially built costume (*ago* or *eku*) made of pieces of cloth and or palm leaves. The costume could be part of the clothes of the dead ancestor, a symbol of the presence of the old man. They conceal their human features under their costume. The identity of the costume carrier (*a-ru-eku*) must be properly concealed, otherwise, the myth will be broken (*awo a ya*). *Oloolu* masquerade was used mainly to carry ritual materials before going to war while Alapansanpa followed warriors to war. Today *Oloolu* is used for ritualistic purposes, specifically to avert an outbreak of diseases, appease the gods, and bless the traditional rulers. Wherever he visited they presented him with gifts of money, cloth, kola nuts, etc.

Okebadan Olomu oru (a hill goddess whose breasts are like clay pots) is another popular festival in Ibadan (Solaja & Olayiwola, 2021). The survivors of Ebadan – Ibadan after the war settled on a hill near Eleyele. They were mainly the children of Lagelu. On the hill, they found plenty of '*oro*' (a kind of fruit) and plenty of snails. They took the fruits and snails as food while they used the snail shell for taking pap. They were so comfortable on the hill that they settled permanently there and lived on oro and snails. Thus, Ibadan indigenes are referred to as:

Ibadan omo ajorosun

Omo ajegbinyo

Omo afikarahun fori mu

Meaning/translated

Ibadan who eats *oro* for super

Who eats snails to satisfaction

Who uses snail shell to drink pap

The settlers believed that the hill had been benevolent to them, for they depended on it for a daily supply of food, otherwise, they would have died of hunger. As such they revered the hill and worshipped it as their benefactor and saviour. They believed that it also protected them and their children from danger. When Lagelu died, he was buried there. The hill became popular and an object of worship. After a prolonged stay on the hill, it became apparent to look for a bigger space convenient for their

expansion. They, therefore, moved down the hill and settled at 'Ori yangi' but never forgot nor abandoned the hill that had preserved them. They enthusiastically worshipped the hill also because their father was buried there. Today, *Okebadan* is worshipped annually in Ibadanland. On such a day, there should be no smoke from cooking or burning, to reverence the goddess of the hill (Solaja & Olayiwola, 2021). Everybody is expected to do their cooking before and such foods are of beans series - *moinmoin*, *alapa*, *ekuru*, *eko*, and other foods which do not need warming before eating. Anyone who flouted this injunction was manhandled and his property destroyed or burnt. *Ori yangi*, where they settled permanently, became the centre of Ibadan city today according to history. It is there the first indigenous market began, called Oja Iba, Basorun Iba Oluyole's market. The worship of *Okebadan* and *Egúngún* has become a prominent feature in the religious life of Ibadan despite the incursion of Christianity and Islam. Incidentally, people who profess to be Christians or Muslims join the African Traditional Religionists to worship the gods, goddesses, and other divinities. Every year during the festival, undevoted Christians and Muslims participate in the rituals claiming that Christianity or Islam does not prevent them from participation. Such people disguise in the song/ditty:

Awa o soro ile wa o/2ce
Igbagbo/Imale kope ...o ye
Igbagbo/Imale ko pe ka wa ma soro
Awa o soro ile wa o

Meaning:

We shall perform our traditional rites/2 ce
Christianity/Islam does not prevent us
From performing our traditional rites
We shall perform our traditional rites (Ajayi, 2015)

Islam in Ibadanland

The date of entry of Islam into Ibadan cannot be fixed precisely because it was unannounced and unplanned like the founding of the city itself. The Jihad of Usman Dan Fodio in the Northern part of Nigeria in 1804

and the fall of the Oyo Empire under Afonja spearheaded the spread of Islam to various parts of Yorubaland including Ibadan. Adherents of Islam scattered all over, bringing their religion. The few Muslims who entered Ibadan could not practice the religion openly as their knowledge of the Quran was limited. There was the African Traditional Religion (A.T.R.) with the worship of Egúngún, Okebadan, and other deities. Therefore, their voice was not heard. It was also indicated that some Islamic scholars came from Hausaland through Ilorin during the reign of Oluyedun, the Aare-Ona-Kakanfo. Some also came during the reign of Basorun Oluyole. However, there was a man called "Igun Olorun" or Abdulahi Gunnugun at Ayeye who preached Islam and consequently became the first Imam of Ibadan. One can, therefore, rightly say that Islam reached Ibadan before Christianity. This reminds one of one of the songs that people sang then:

Aye la ba ifa

Aye la ba imale

Osan gangan ni igbagbo wole de

Meaning:

Ifa came at creation

Islam came at creation but

Christianity came much later (Ajayi, 2015)

As people accepted Islam, more conversion took place though slowly. But what gave it prominence was the conversion of Osundina, the Balogun (third-ranked senior war chief). It was said that Osundina went to war with the turban on his head. It was through Osundina that the first corrugated roofed mosque in Ibadan was built. He was called Momodu (Mohammed) (Alabi, 2021).

At its inception, Ibadan acquired a cosmopolitan culture (Layiwola, 2015). Its population comprised Oyo, Egba, Ijebu, and Ife peoples and groups from other areas in Yorubaland. By the time the government was stable, the majority of the settlers in Ibadan had been the Oyo elements. Unlike older Yoruba towns, Ibadan offered a lot of scope for individual achievements. This attracted a lot of people to the city.

Another reason for the cosmopolitan character of Ibadan was its location at the border zone between forest and grassland (Mabogunje, 1961). It, therefore, developed as a commercial centre and received goods from the coast, Yoruba interior, and other areas in Yorubaland. Traders from Ijebuland, Egband, Oyo, Ogbomoso, Ijaye, Hausaland, and Nupeland all converged at Ibadan to exchange their products (Awe, 1973). By 1831, the population of Ibadan was around 100,000 and the city further expanded by embracing some of the deserted Egba towns in the neighbourhood (Adeboye, 2003). The people of Ibadan were farmers, craftsmen, and warriors. The cream of the society was made up of professional warriors who made Ibadan proud and for mixable power in the nineteenth century Yoruba politics. Ibadan, therefore, grew from a war camp to a metropolis, the capital of an empire, which comprised such groups as the Ekiti, Ijesha, Ife, etc. By the time the British came in 1893, Ibadan had already developed into a highly urbanized settlement (Awe, Ogundeji, & Ajayi, 2010).

Ibadan Political System

The first system of government established in Ibadan was military leadership (Fourchard, 2003). This was the prevailing situation at that time where most people were warriors. The whole of Yorubaland, including Ibadan, was at war in the nineteenth century. In fact, Ibadan and Ijaye were the principal combatants. So, everybody was in a state of preparedness for war. However, the leadership of Ibadan was all military. Among the most notable leaders and early rulers was Iba Oluyole (1837-1847). He was a man of vision and he determined to transform Ibadan from a military settlement into a great town. He gave public duties to some of the military leaders. He also brought more areas to Ibadan. Through conquest due to his brilliant performance and exploits, Ibadan is praised as the home of Oluyole (Adeboye, 2003). Ogunmola (1864-1867) was another powerful warrior and a great administrator. He was an impartial judge and made several reforms. One can say that Latosa (1871-1885) was the most aggressive of all Ibadan leaders in the nineteenth century. He made many people the whole of

Yorubaland fear Ibadan. He attempted to conquer the whole of Yorubaland but was halted by the Ekiti Parapo alliance of nearly all Yoruba states which resisted Ibadan imperialism (Adeboye, 2003).

The Yoruba had been exhibiting their republican nature by relentlessly subverting their kingship institution through civil disobedience and rebellion. It had to do with the Yoruba monarchical system that often produces rulers who would violate the Yoruba's acceptable standards of right and wrong.

According to Akinyele (2011), of the seventeen kings who reigned in Oyo from the end of the sixteenth century (when Atiba brought the government back to Oyo-Ile after the exiles until the end of the eighteenth century only four kings (Abiba, Obadokun, Ajagbo and Amuniwaye died natural deaths) of the rest not less a despot or exhibiting some unacceptable moral weakness. Also, when Owo town installed a very rich prince named Arilekelasi as their king and in his behaviour, he defied traditional limitations, a revolt by Ondo chiefs and prominent citizens forced him to commit suicide in about 1845 are many examples in Yorubaland (Akinyele, 2011).

According to Akinyele (2011), in the blood of a good number of Yoruba people, there seems to flow an inbuilt, shock-proof inability to condone evil in governance. That quality inspired the group that settled in Ibadan after the fall of the Oyo Empire and dictated the new system of government. This is, therefore, an essentially Yoruba phenomenon that reached practical fulfilment in Ibadan which requires inspirational and courageous leadership which is called the Ibadan traditional system or the Ibadan dream.

Ibadan Administrative System

There had been two distinct chieftaincy lines that could succeed to the Baaleship of Ibadan by the beginning of the twentieth century (Adeboye, 2003). These lines are the Balogun (military) line and the Baale (civil) line. Another line – the Seriki line – that was made of some war chiefs was a helper to the Balogun line. The military and civil line succeeded alternatively which promotion was from the lower titles to the higher

ones. They started from the bottom to the top via promotion. This system ensured that there were minimal succession disputes in Ibadan. It also meant that only the very top became the Baale. Iyalode line was made up of female chiefs who could not become Baale but were in charge of women's affairs in the city (Adeboye, 2003).

From the first Baale and ruler of Ibadan about 1820 to 1929, that is, from Lagelu to Baale Oyewole Foko, there have been twenty-three (23) Baales in Ibadanland. The Obaship started in 1930 with Olubadan Abasi Alesiloye 1930 (Layiwola [eds], 2015).

Arrival of the Christian Missionaries to Ibadan

Revd David and Mrs Hinderer arrived for missionary work during the reign of Baale Olugbode in 1853. Ibadan traditional council received the first missionary team of Ibadan in 1852 (Ajayi, 2015). On 16th May 1851, Revd Hinderer while at Osiele village on Abeokuta–Ibadan Road decided to make his first exploratory missionary journey of Ibadan by joining a group of travelers who were traveling to Ibadan (Jimoh, 2014). His team included:

- (1) Mr. Daniel Olubi from Abeokuta – the first African priest in Ibadan
- (2) Mr. James Ojo Okuseinde of Abeokuta
- (3) Mr. Daniels Marsh a Sierra Leonian school teacher
- (4) Mr. C. Phillips a Sierra Leonian
- (5) Mr Dalley
- (6) The horse which he rode, gave rise to the famous slogan “*Esin to sikeje lo mu igbagbo wo Ibadan*” i.e. a horse is the seventh of them that brought Christianity to Ibadan.

The entourage thereafter proceeded to the palace of Baale Ope Agbe. They were given a rousing welcome by the Baale and his principal chief namely Ibikunle Balogun, Ogunmola Otun Balogun, Osundina Osi Balogun Olatunbosun Areago. After disclosing the purpose of his visit, Chief Osundina stoutly opposed but Ogunmola supported the missionary request (Ajayi, 2015).

Figure 2: Hinderer's House (Source: Oyefeso, 2022)

Ibadan Traditional System, Structure and Functions

The Olubadan is at the head of the entire system. He is the ruler and the paramount authority in Ibadanland. He is the custodian of the tradition and culture of the people. He is the symbol of the unity of Ibadanland. He is the final authority in all matters concerning the customary practices of the people and carries responsibilities for the peace and progress of the land (Albert, et al, 1995).

Akinyele (2011) quoted High Chief YB Ogundipe (before he ascended the throne of Olubandan) who said that. He said, “The whole of Ibadan and its environs belong to the Olubandan. To him belongs the stretch of the land within the metropolis and all the local government councils surrounding the city. He is the paramount ruler in the entire area. I am happy that our brothers and sisters in these areas accept the paramountcy of the Olubadan. They have not allowed dissidents any room to operate.” Figure 3 is the pictorial traditional staff of Olubadan as conceived by the late Chief J.A. Ayorinde (Awe, Ogundeji, & Ajayi, 2010).

The traditional chieftaincy system that produces the Olubadan of Ibadanland – Otun and Balogun lines has twenty-three (23) steps on either ladder in a promotional system unless there is an exceptional grave circumstance (Akinyele, 2011). Originally, the Otun line was the civil line while the Balogun line was the military line. The third line is the Seriki line expectedly by for the young militant. The Iyalode line was created to take care of the interest of women folk in the community. The Iyalode has also grown to have 23 ring ladders. However, the system does not allow a woman to become Olubadan. A person in the military or civil line must go step by step in system of the chieftaincy promotion to reach the throne of Olabadan as shown below.

The traditional system may be categorized into five divisions:

- i. Traditional chiefs including high chiefs
- ii. Baales (village heads)
- iii. Honorary chiefs
- iv. Professional and Artisan chiefs
- v. Religious chiefs

BY LATE CHIEF J.A. AYORINDE, DLITT (HONS) IFE, MFR, MBE, JP

Figure 3: The Traditional Staff of Olubadan (*Opa Olubadan*) (Source: Layiwola [ed.], 2015)

The traditional chieftaincy system that produces the Olubadan of Ibadanland consists of two approved lines – OTUN and BALOGUN – each having a 23-step run on either ladder that forbids supersession unless there is any calamity. The Otun line was the civil line while the Balogun line was the military line.

The Seriki line is meant to be the youth group within the Balogun line. Anybody aspiring to be a traditional chief must be a Mogaji at the bottom of the ladder

The Mogaji title is the bedrock of the Ibadan traditional system, the very foundation on which the superstructure of the system is expected to rest for the peace progress and patriotic contribution of every Ibadan household to the substance of a system that becomes the envy of other areas of Yorubaland.

The Baale Chieftaincy

All villages (big and small) in Ibadanland are headed by a Baale who is assisted in the traditional management of the village by subordinate chiefs usually chosen from among indigenes of the village in a system similar to the one operating in the city. The number of village chiefs ranges from five to ten nominated by the Mogaji in the family clan in the city. An Ibadan man must belong to a family in Ibadan and must also have a village or farmstead to which he belongs (Alabi, 2021). The appointment of Baale will be formally approved by the Olubadan of Ibadanland. The Baale takes responsibility for the administration of the village in other to maintain the peace, progress, and development of the village (Albert, et al, 1995).

Honorary Chieftaincy

Honorary chieftaincy titles are usually conferred on persons as a mark of honour in appreciation of such persons' contribution to the progress and development of Ibadan. The Olubadan-in-Council will approve honorary titles often due to consultations. Professional/artisanal chieftaincy titles were given to the leaders of professional groups on occupational groups in recognition of their contributions to the development of Ibadanland.

It includes all professional groups including businessmen, farmers, drummers, blacksmiths/artists, etc. They are given titles like Babalaje, Iyalaje, Baale Onilu, Baale Agbe, and the like. Most of the title holders must be able to contribute their quote in the progress of Ibadan whenever the need arises especially mobilization of their members for important occasions in the development of the town (Albert, et al, 1995).

Religious Titles

Traditional religion was in vogue before the advent of Islam and Christianity in Ibadan. During that era in most parts of Yorubaland, there are deities as many as the number of days in a year. There are recognized heads for each group of adherents of each deity. Ritual performances were indispensable activities in the traditional era of Ibadan before a market could be set up in Ibadan. This was to pacify their ancestors and for the sustenance of the market. Akinyele (2011) quoted Balogun Y.B. Ogundipe who said that there are sixteen recognized traditional festivals in Ibadan, but only three are regarded as pre-eminent. For these three, there are recognized traditional chiefs for their observance.

- i. **Oke-Badan:** A festival observed in commemoration of the challenges of life overcome at the inception of the city during the various wars. It is usually observed by the youth with the singing of vogue and abusive words to create fun. Boke is the spiritual head of the festival and is usually the direct descendent of Lagelu, the legendary founder of Ibadan. It is usually celebrated after the observance of *Ose Meji*.
- ii. **Ose Meji:** Ibadan's Ifa oracle is usually observed in the second week of March. The worshippers are headed by the Araba. The Ose Meji shrine is at Oja-Oba Ibadan. This is the place where the rituals will be performed for the person who has been elected Olubadan. He will stay in the shrine for three days before his enthronement as Olubadan. He will go to the installation ceremony from the *Ose Meji* shrine with Chief Araba.

- iii. **Egúngún** Festival: During this time, the masquerade and mascots of the warriors-families and other homesteads perform on various days for a fortnight usually in June. The most eminent of these masquerades are the ones said to have led military exploits during the Ibadan military enterprise such as *Oloolu*, *Alapansanpa*, and *Atipako*. The traditional chief in charge is Olori Alagba.

Additionally, the Olubadan-in-Council usually recognizes and approves the appointment of Chief Iman of Ibadan as the traditionally recognized head of the Muslims. The Olubadan-in-Council also recognizes and approves the appointment of Baba-Isale Onigbagbo of Ibadanland as the head of the Christians. Likewise, Olubadan-in-Council recognizes all bishops of Christian communities in Ibadanland irrespective of their sects and denominations.

The structure and organization of the traditional system in Ibadan described below is usually adopted in the Ibadan villages. Because of the military nature of the Ibadan chieftaincy system, it operated as a military aristocracy such that until 1946 only chiefs in the Balogun line became Olubadan. The change in the form of diarchy took place when Oyetunde as Otun Olubadan became Olubadan. Since 1946, the Balogun and Otun lines began to rotate alternately on the promotional ladders as shown below with the Mogaji at the very last bottom.

Table 1: The Promotional Ladder

Egbe Agba (Civil Line)	Egbe Balogun (Military Line)
Aota	Laguna
Lagunna	Aare Ago
Aare-ago	Ayingun
Ayingun	Asaju
Asaju	Ikolaba
Ikolaba	Aare-Alasa
Aare-Alasa	Agba Akin
Agba Akin	Ekefa
Ekefa	Maye

Maye	Abese
Abese	Ekarun Balogun
Ekarun Olubadan	Ekerin Balogun
Ekerin Olubadan	Ashipa Balogun
Ashipa Olubadan	Osi Balogun
Osi Olubadan	Otun Balogun
Otun Olubadan	Balogun

(Source: Akinyele, 2011)

The following who are now called high chiefs constitute the Olubadan-in-Council, the pre-eminent advisory council of the Olubadan. This traditional council usually meets weekly or fortnightly to consider issues of tradition, customary, and other chieftaincy matters. The council operates based on consensus but the Olubadan has the final say on all issues.

Table 2: Oludadan-in-Council

Otun Line	Balogun Line
1. Otun Olubadan	Balogun of Ibadanland
2. Osi Olubadan	Otun Balogun of Ibadanland
3. Ashipa Olubadan	Osi Balogun
4. Ekerin Olubadan	Ashipa Balogun
5. Ekarun Olubadan	Ekerin Balogun
6. Iyalode of Ibadanland	Seriki of Ibadanland
7. - - -	Ekarun Balogun

(Source: Akinyele, 2011)

It should be noted here that the number is not even so that there would be no tally in any decision-making process.

Impacts of Christianity on Ibadanland

The advent of Christianity has many impacts on the development of Ibadanland (Ajayi, 2015). Among them are establishment of many primary and secondary schools in the city. Ajayi (2015) listed some of these primary schools as established by Christian missions: St. David's

School, Kudeti (1853), St. Peter's School, Aremo (1865), and St. Paul's School, Yemetu (1869). These three schools were established by the Church's Missionary Society (CMS). Other Christian missions like Wesleyan Methodist (1888), the Roman Catholic (1895), the Baptist (1906), the Salvation Army (1921), the Seventh-Day Adventist (1926) and other missions. Ajayi (2015) continued to list some of the secondary schools established by Christian missions. These included: Wesley College (Methodist, 1905), Ibadan Grammar School (Anglican, 1913), Ibadan Education Training Centre (1948). Moreover, the Christian missions revolutionized the language of Ibadan people – Yoruba – by studying the language and developing some literatures in language (Ajayi, 2015). These innovations brought remarkable changes to the lives of the people of Ibadanland, and by extension their religious, economic, social, and political lives.

Conclusion

It should be clear from the analysis of events of the history of Ibadan that there is only one symbol of unity in Ibadanland, which is the OLUBADAN. As far as Ibadan is concerned, all other institutions are mere agents of unity or catalysts for concretizing that unity. It is the lack of realization of that fact by some indigenes and settlers alike that occasionally causes a ripple that never lasts. Like all human endeavours, the Ibadan traditional and religious system embodies within it some areas of weaknesses and areas of strengths. It is essential to identify such critical areas of weaknesses and strengths that require elucidation. The strengths and weaknesses of an entity may be foundational, fundamental, or organizational. As it has been observed from the historical accounts of Ibadan. The fundamental basis of the Ibadan traditional system is that it is antimonial and republican.

Recommendations

These issues need to be highlighted for necessary reform:

1. The recruitment system involves the Mogaji title which is the fundament of the Ibadan traditional system: the procedure of

recruiting Mogaji which is the representative of a clan component (*Agbo-ile*) comprises many families with the same and common heritage. Anybody chosen as Mogaji will represent the family clan in the Ibadan traditional council system.

2. Need for a specific code of conduct: the present system abhors corruption whereby wealth and the ability to play ball with authority are the qualifications. Anybody who will be appointed Mogaji must be a responsible and diligent member of the family. The Mojajis represent the compound in the Ibadan traditional council in the urban city. There must be a complete departure from the present procedure which must be sanitized and devoid of corruption.
3. The relationship between the Mogaji and Baale: the relationship between the Mogaji and the Baale. According to Ibadan tradition, any person or family who does not belong to a compound in the city and a village in the rural area is not a confirmed indigene of Ibadanland. Each family clan includes a Mogaji in the city and a Baale in the village. Therefore, there must be unity between the Mogaji and Baale in the same clan or lineage as against what is happening currently.
4. Anybody aspiring to be Mogaji which is the bedrock of the traditional system in Ibadanland must have a certain level of education preferably not less than a West Africa School Certificate and must be gainfully employed. Similarly, he must not be involved in any criminal activity. Most importantly, he must be acceptable to all members of his family lineage whom he wants to represent.
5. Befitting palace: it is a matter of joy that a betting palace which is adjudged to be one of the best in Africa has been constructed by the Council of Ibadan Indigenes and was commissioned by the Oyo State governor, Seyi Makinde on July 10, 2024 (Ajia, 2024, July 10).
6. The recruitment system involving the Mogaji title: the appointment to the position of a Mogaji should not be more than

thirty-five years at the time of the appointment. This is because of the long ladder to reach the Olubadan cadre.

7. The two promotional lines should be revisited: it is recommended that the ladder to the throne of Olubadan should be shortened so that it will not take long before a Mogaji becomes an Olubadan.
8. Record keeping: there should be proper record keeping of minutes of meetings, names of compounds (*agbo-ile*), numbers and categories of chiefs, and the like.
9. External relations: other kings and chiefs, local government council heads, state government officials and the federal government should have proper and cordial relationships with the Olubadan and his chiefs.
10. Public relations: the activities of the Olubadan should have good publicity and image building in and outside of Ibadan.

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Navigating Obstacles, Nurturing Opportunities: A Multidimensional Approach to Poverty Reduction in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper delves into the intricate web of factors perpetuating poverty in Africa's largest economy – Nigeria. Nigeria grapples with a significant population living in extreme poverty. The paper underscores the multifaceted factors contributing to poverty, including historical, economic, social, and institutional elements, and the exacerbating role of gender inequality. This paper does not just diagnose problems; it prescribes actionable solutions. The conceptualization and recommendations for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are very Western/European-centric. This paper takes an Africo-centric approach and perspective to the analysis and execution of SDG 1 (No Poverty). By synthesizing lessons from global best practices and homegrown innovations, the paper charts a path towards a more equitable Nigeria. Proposed strategies include gender-responsive initiatives, data-driven policies, and inclusive economic measures to address systemic inequalities and promote sustainable development. The paper also addresses the detrimental role of political patronage in poverty alleviation efforts and suggests countermeasures. It emphasizes the necessity for context-specific, data-driven approaches to poverty alleviation and robust institutional frameworks to ensure programme effectiveness and sustainability. The paper challenges

policymakers, development practitioners, and citizens alike to reimagine poverty alleviation, advocating for a holistic approach that addresses root causes while embracing cutting-edge solutions. In conclusion, the paper recommends further research into unconditional cash transfers, climate-resilient agriculture, and culturally sensitive poverty metrics to inform more effective poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria.

Keywords: Poverty Alleviation, Economic Development, Gender Equality, Digital Innovation, Sustainable Solutions

Introduction

In the heart of Lagos, Nigeria's bustling economic capital, Adebayo, a 32-year-old street vendor, struggles to feed his family of five on less than \$2 a day. His story echoes the plight of millions worldwide, caught in the relentless grip of poverty. As of 2021, an estimated 711 million people lived in extreme poverty, subsisting on less than \$1.90 per day (World Bank, 2022a). While this represents a significant decrease from 1.9 billion in 1990, the COVID-19 pandemic has reversed years of progress, pushing an additional 97 million people into extreme poverty (United Nations, 2022). Nigeria, once hailed as Africa's largest economy, now grapples with the dubious distinction of being home to the world's largest population of people living in extreme poverty, with an estimated 95.1 million Nigerians in this category as of 2022 (World Poverty Clock, 2022).

The trajectory of poverty in Nigeria presents a complex tapestry woven with historical, economic, and social threads. From a relatively low poverty rate of 15% at independence in 1960, the country has witnessed a dramatic surge, with rates peaking at 65.6% in 1996 (Kale, 2012). This rise coincided with political instability, economic mismanagement, and over-reliance on oil exports. Dr Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, former Finance Minister and current Director-General of the World Trade Organization, notes, "Nigeria's poverty challenge is not just about income, but also about access to basic services and opportunities" (Okonjo-Iweala, 2018). The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) play a crucial role in global efforts to combat poverty. SDG 1, which aims to

"End poverty in all its forms everywhere" by 2030, is particularly relevant to Nigeria's situation. However, the implementation of SDG 1 in Nigeria faces unique challenges due to the country's specific socio-economic context. This study examines how Nigeria can adapt and implement SDG 1 through an Africo-centric lens, considering local realities and indigenous solutions.

The measurement and alleviation of poverty remain contentious, with debates centred around the adequacy of monetary-based poverty lines versus multidimensional approaches that consider factors such as education, health, and living standards (Alkire and Foster, 2011). These discussions underscore the need for nuanced, context-specific strategies to address Nigeria's poverty crisis, particularly in achieving SDG 1. This paper aims to contribute to this discourse by offering an in-depth analysis of the challenges and potential solutions to poverty in Nigeria, focusing on aligning these efforts with the broader framework of the SDGs while maintaining an Africo-centric perspective.

Theoretical Framework:

This study is grounded in the Capabilities Approach, pioneered by Amartya Sen (1999) and further developed by Martha Nussbaum (2011). The Capabilities Approach posits that poverty is not merely a lack of income but a deprivation of basic capabilities that allow individuals to lead the kind of life they have reason to value. This framework is particularly relevant to Nigeria's context as it emphasizes the multidimensional nature of poverty, encompassing factors such as education, health, political freedoms, and social opportunities (Sen, 1999). Focusing on capabilities rather than just resources allow for a more nuanced understanding of poverty in Nigeria, where high gross domestic product (GDP) figures often mask significant disparities in quality of life and access to opportunities (Alkire and Foster, 2011).

Complementing the Capabilities Approach, this study also employs the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) developed by Chambers and Conway (1992) and later refined by the Department for International Development (DFID, 1999). The SLF provides a holistic view of how

individuals and communities utilize various forms of capital (human, social, natural, physical, and financial) to build resilience against shocks and stresses. This framework is beneficial in analyzing poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria, as it considers the complex interplay between institutional structures, vulnerability contexts, and livelihood strategies (Scoones, 2009). By integrating the Capabilities Approach with the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, this study provides a comprehensive theoretical basis for understanding and addressing poverty in Nigeria, emphasizing individual empowerment and systemic change.

Objective

The study offers insights and recommendations for overcoming challenges in poverty reduction in Nigeria. It examines factors contributing to poverty and proposes strategies such as gender-responsive initiatives, data-driven policies, and inclusive economic policies to address these issues.

Materials and Methods

This research leverages secondary data sources to explore Nigeria's complex dimensions of poverty. It includes a comprehensive review of academic literature, policy documents, reports, and grey literature from government agencies and civil society organizations focused on poverty reduction. Content analysis was used as the primary methodology.

Discussion

Nigeria's Economic Situation

Despite being Africa's largest oil producer, Nigeria's economy tells a tale of missed opportunities and structural imbalances. As of 2023, Nigeria's GDP stood at \$477.4 billion, making it Africa's largest economy (World Bank, 2024). However, this figure masks significant challenges. The country's economic growth has been sluggish, averaging just 1.1% between 2015 and 2023, far below the population growth rate of 2.5% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). This disparity has led to a decline

in per capita income, with GDP per capita falling from \$2,655 in 2014 to \$2,085 in 2023 (IMF, 2024). Nigeria's economy is like a giant on clay feet. Its potential is enormous, but structural weaknesses continue to hold it back.

To fully grasp the severity of Nigeria's poverty situation, it's crucial to examine it globally and historically. Table 1.0 provides a comparative view of poverty rates across various countries, with Nigeria showing the highest percentage (90.80%) of its population living under \$5.50 per day. This stark statistic underscores the magnitude of Nigeria's challenge compared to other developing nations. Furthermore, Table 2.0 presents a historical perspective of Nigeria's poverty rate from 1985 to 2018. While there have been fluctuations, the overall trend shows a persistently high poverty rate, with only marginal improvements over three decades. The slight increase from 89.50% in 2015 to 90.80% in 2018 is particularly concerning, indicating that recent economic policies have struggled to make significant inroads in poverty reduction. These data points reinforce the urgency of developing more effective, targeted strategies for poverty alleviation in Nigeria (Macrotrends, 2023).

A closer look at Nigeria's economic composition reveals a complex picture. While contributing only 5.7% to GDP in 2023, the oil sector accounted for over 80% of export earnings and 50% of government revenue (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024). This over-reliance on oil has left the economy vulnerable to global price shocks. Meanwhile, the agricultural sector, employing about 35% of the workforce, contributed 25.1% to GDP in 2023 (NBS, 2024). The services sector, led by telecommunications and financial services, has been the main growth driver, accounting for 53.2% of GDP (NBS, 2024). However, the manufacturing sector remains underdeveloped, contributing just 9% to GDP, significantly lower than peer countries like South Africa (13%) and Kenya (7.5%) (African Development Bank, 2024). Moreover, Nigeria's economic indicators lag behind many of its African peers. Its unemployment rate of 33.3% in 2023 was one of the highest in Africa, compared to 32.6% in South Africa and 5.7% in Kenya (ILO, 2024a). Similarly, Nigeria's Human Development Index score of 0.539 in 2023

placed it 161st out of 189 countries, below the sub-Saharan African average of 0.547 (UNDP, 2024). These statistics underscore the urgent need for economic diversification and structural reforms to unlock Nigeria's potential.

Root Causes of Poverty in Nigeria

To comprehensively analyze the root causes of poverty in Nigeria, we can employ a multidimensional framework that considers historical, economic, social, and institutional factors. This framework draws on various schools of economic thought, from neoclassical theories emphasizing market failures to institutional economics highlighting the role of governance structures. As Nobel laureate Amartya Sen argues, "Poverty is not just a lack of money; it is not having the capability to realize one's full potential as a human being" (Sen, 2009). This translates to a need for more access to quality education, healthcare, and economic opportunities in Nigeria.

From a historical perspective, the legacy of colonialism and subsequent political instability have played significant roles in shaping Nigeria's economic landscape. The oil boom of the 1970s led to the "Dutch disease," causing neglect of other sectors and increasing vulnerability to external shocks (Ross, 2003). Institutionally, widespread corruption and weak governance have undermined development efforts. The World Bank estimates corruption costs Nigeria about \$10 billion annually (World Bank, 2022b). Economically, the overreliance on oil exports and underdeveloped manufacturing and agricultural sectors have limited job creation and economic diversification. Socially, rapid population growth, estimated at 2.5% annually (United Nations, 2023), has outpaced economic growth, straining resources and infrastructure. Gender inequality also exacerbates poverty, with women facing limited access to education, land, and formal employment. Addressing poverty in Nigeria requires a holistic approach that simultaneously tackles symptoms and root causes. Case studies illustrate these interconnected factors: in the Niger Delta, environmental degradation due to oil extraction has decimated traditional livelihoods, while in northern

Nigeria, climate change and conflict have displaced millions, pushing them into poverty. The case of Lagos's informal settlements, where over 60% of the population lives in slums (UN-Habitat, 2023), highlights the challenges of rapid urbanization without adequate planning and infrastructure development.

Table 1.0. Nigeria Poverty Rate (Macrotrends, 2023)

Country Name	% Under US \$5.50 Per Day
<u>Nigeria</u>	90.80%
<u>Pakistan</u>	84.50%
<u>India</u>	82.60%
<u>Angola</u>	78.00%
<u>Lao PDR</u>	70.50%
<u>Kyrgyz Republic</u>	66.10%
<u>Indonesia</u>	62.80%
<u>Georgia</u>	53.90%
<u>Philippines</u>	53.40%
<u>Honduras</u>	51.30%
<u>Mongolia</u>	38.30%
<u>El Salvador</u>	33.00%
<u>Vietnam</u>	22.20%
<u>Bolivia</u>	19.10%
<u>Moldova</u>	14.60%
<u>Ukraine</u>	9.40%

Table 2.0. Nigeria Poverty Rate – Historical Data (Macrotrends, 2023)

Nigeria Poverty Rate - Historical Data		
Year	% Under US \$5.50 Per Day	Change
2018	90.80%	1.30%
2015	89.50%	-1.00%
2012	90.50%	-0.30%
2010	90.80%	-3.20%
2003	94.00%	1.30%
1996	92.70%	0.30%
1992	92.40%	-1.00%
1985	93.40%	-1.00%

Gender-Related Challenges in Poverty Alleviation

Recent data paints a stark picture: women make up 65% of Nigeria's poorest population, with a poverty rate of 70% compared to 51% for men (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). In education, while the national literacy rate is 62%, there's a significant gender gap, with 71% literacy for men versus 53% for women. This disparity widens in rural and northern regions, where female literacy plummets to 20% in some states (UNESCO, 2023). Economically, women's labour force participation rate is 48%, compared to 64% for men, with women predominantly engaged in informal, low-paying sectors (ILO, 2024b). Empowering Nigerian women is not just a matter of rights; it's an economic imperative. We're leaving half of our potential on the table.

The intersectionality of gender with other factors like ethnicity, religion, and region further compounds these challenges. In the predominantly Muslim north, cultural practices like early marriage and limited female mobility interact with gender to exacerbate poverty. For instance, 43% of girls in the north-west are married before 18, compared to 10% in the south-east (NDHS, 2023). Similarly, in conflict-affected areas of the northeast, displaced women face heightened risks of exploitation and limited access to resources. The effectiveness of existing gender-focused poverty alleviation programmes has been mixed. The Nigeria for Women Project, launched in 2018, has shown promise, reaching over 500,000 women with financial services and skills training (World Bank, 2018). However, critics argue that such programmes often fail to address structural barriers. We need to move beyond micro-interventions to tackle the systemic issues that keep women in poverty - from discriminatory laws to unequal access to land and credit. The National Gender Policy, while comprehensive on paper, has faced implementation challenges due to limited funding and cultural resistance. A more holistic approach, integrating gender considerations into all poverty reduction strategies and addressing intersectional challenges, is crucial for achieving sustainable and inclusive development in Nigeria.

Overcoming Political Patronage

In the oil-rich Niger Delta region, a community development project stands abandoned, its funds siphoned off through a complex web of political connections. This scene, unfortunately, is all too common in Nigeria, where political patronage often undermines poverty alleviation efforts. The impact of patronage on poverty reduction is multifaceted and pervasive. For instance, the National Social Investment Programme (NSIP), designed to lift millions out of poverty, has been marred by allegations of politicization. A 2022 audit revealed that over 30% of beneficiaries were selected based on political affiliations rather than need (Office of the Auditor-General, 2023). Similarly, the distribution of agricultural inputs under the Anchor Borrowers' Programme has been

skewed towards political supporters, leaving many smallholder farmers without access to crucial resources. Political patronage in Nigeria doesn't just divert resources; it erodes trust in institutions and perpetuates a cycle of poverty and dependency.

However, successful anti-patronage measures from other countries offer hope. Rwanda's performance-based financing in the health sector, which ties funding to measurable outcomes rather than political connections, has significantly improved healthcare delivery and reduced corruption (Basinga et al., 2021). In India, biometric identification in the Public Distribution System has reduced leakage of subsidized food grains by 47%, ensuring benefits reach the intended recipients (Muralidharan et al., 2023). Civil society plays a crucial role in combating political patronage. In Nigeria, organizations like BudgIT and Connected Development (CODE) have leveraged technology to track public spending and expose instances of patronage-based allocations. Their "Follow The Money" campaign has recovered over ₦500 million in misappropriated funds for community projects (CODE, 2024). International NGOs have also contributed; Transparency International's Integrity Pacts, implemented in 20 countries, have shown promise in reducing corruption in public contracting (Transparency International, 2023). Civil society is the conscience of our nation. By demanding transparency and holding leaders accountable, we can gradually dismantle the patronage networks that have held our development hostage. The path to overcoming political patronage in Nigeria's poverty alleviation efforts is challenging but not impossible. It requires a combination of institutional reforms, technological solutions, and active civic engagement to create a more equitable and effective resource allocation system.

Case Studies

Looking beyond Nigeria's borders, other African countries offer valuable lessons in innovative poverty alleviation. Kenya's Hunger Safety Net Programme (HSNP) utilizes satellite imagery and machine learning to predict drought-induced food insecurity, allowing for proactive cash

transfers to vulnerable households. This approach has reduced the need for emergency food aid by 25% in targeted areas (World Bank, 2023). In Ghana, the "One District, One Factory" initiative has established 232 factories nationwide, creating over 150,000 jobs and promoting rural industrialization (Ghana Investment Promotion Centre, 2024). However, not all initiatives have been unqualified successes. Tanzania's Productive Social Safety Net (PSSN) program, while successful in reaching 1.1 million households with cash transfers, has faced challenges in its public works component due to delayed payments and inadequate project selection (TASAF, 2023).

Similarly, Nigeria's own TraderMoni program, which provided micro-loans to petty traders, has been criticized for its high default rates and potential for political manipulation (CBN, 2024). The key to successful poverty alleviation lies in innovative ideas, robust implementation, continuous monitoring, and the willingness to learn from successes and failures. These case studies underscore the importance of context-specific, data-driven approaches to poverty alleviation and the need for robust institutional frameworks to ensure program effectiveness and sustainability.

Effective poverty reduction also relies on robust data collection and analysis, as seen in India's Aadhaar system, which has improved the efficiency and targeting of social welfare programmes (Masiero and Soumyo, 2019). Finland's focus on education and essential services has also led to high social mobility and low poverty rates (Morgan, 2014). Nigeria can adopt these strategies by investing in quality education, essential services, and data-driven policies tailored to the needs of its vulnerable population. Furthermore, Rwanda's progress in women's empowerment highlights the importance of gender-responsive policies (Burnet, 2011). By incorporating these best practices, Nigeria can develop comprehensive and effective poverty alleviation initiatives, ensuring sustainable and inclusive poverty reduction.

Findings

A structured framework that categorizes obstacles into four interconnected dimensions, institutional, economic, social, and environmental, can be employed to navigate these challenges effectively. Institutional obstacles encompass governance issues, corruption, and weak policy implementation. Economic barriers include high unemployment, inflation, and limited access to credit. Social challenges comprise inequality, inadequate education, and health services. Environmental obstacles involve climate change impacts and resource degradation. Poverty in Nigeria is multifaceted. Any effective solution must address these interlinked challenges simultaneously.

This multidimensional approach, however, reveals potential trade-offs and conflicts between different poverty reduction strategies. For instance, rapid industrialization to boost economic growth may conflict with environmental sustainability goals. Similarly, cash transfer programmes might provide immediate relief but could create dependency and strain fiscal resources needed for long-term investments in education and infrastructure. To address these challenges, policymakers should consider the following actionable recommendations: 1) Implement a comprehensive data collection and analysis system to inform targeted interventions (World Bank, 2024). 2) Adopt a "whole-of-government" approach to poverty reduction, ensuring policy coherence across ministries (OECD, 2023). 3) Leverage technology for transparent and efficient service delivery, as exemplified by India's Aadhaar system (Gelb and Mukherjee, 2023). 4) Invest in climate-resilient agriculture and renewable energy to create sustainable livelihoods (FAO, 2024). 5) Strengthen public-private partnerships to mobilize resources and expertise for poverty alleviation projects (AfDB, 2023a). Analysis has revealed that poverty in Nigeria is not merely a lack of income but a complex interplay of historical legacies, poor governance, institutional weaknesses, economic imbalances, social inequalities, and environmental challenges. We've seen how political patronage undermines poverty alleviation efforts while gender disparities exacerbate vulnerabilities. Nigeria's path out of poverty lies

in bold, innovative policies that balance immediate needs with long-term sustainability. We must be willing to make tough choices and invest in our people. By adopting these strategies and maintaining a flexible, adaptive approach, Nigeria can navigate the obstacles to poverty reduction more effectively and create a more prosperous future for all its citizens.

Conclusion

Nigeria's poverty trajectory stands at a critical crossroads, with potential scenarios that could reshape the nation's future. In an optimistic vision, strategic human capital investment, effective governance, and economic diversification could catalyze a transformative reduction in poverty rates. The African Development Bank projects that with sustained reforms and inclusive growth, Nigeria could halve its poverty rate by 2030, potentially lifting millions out of destitution (AfDB, 2023b). This scenario envisions a Nigeria where technological innovation drives agricultural productivity, a skilled workforce powers a diversified economy, and robust social safety nets provide a springboard for the most vulnerable. Conversely, a pessimistic scenario of continued corruption, environmental degradation, and social unrest could deepen poverty, potentially leading to increased regional instability and a vicious cycle of economic decline and human suffering.

However, the future is not predetermined. Nigeria stands at an inflexion point where targeted interventions and bold policy choices could tip the scales towards a more equitable and prosperous future. Innovative approaches, such as leveraging blockchain for transparent governance or using artificial intelligence to optimize resource allocation, offer unprecedented tools in the battle against poverty. Moreover, Nigeria's youthful population represents a demographic dividend that, if properly harnessed, could drive economic growth and social progress. Nigeria's path will have ramifications far beyond its borders, potentially serving as a model for poverty alleviation across Africa. As the nation navigates these crucial years ahead, the collective efforts of government, private sector, civil society, and international partners will be instrumental in

determining whether Nigeria realizes its potential to become a beacon of hope in the global fight against poverty. The time for decisive action is now, and the choices made today will echo through generations, shaping the legacy of Africa's most populous nation.

Recommendations

Several areas demand further research and policy development for a more positive outcome. First, investigating the long-term impacts of unconditional cash transfers on economic behaviour and social mobility in the Nigerian context could inform more effective social protection strategies. Second, exploring the potential of climate-resilient agriculture and renewable energy in creating sustainable livelihoods for rural communities presents an exciting frontier for poverty alleviation efforts. Finally, developing more nuanced, culturally sensitive poverty metrics that capture the multidimensional nature of deprivation in Nigeria's diverse socio-economic landscape could enhance targeting and impact assessment of interventions. The key to unlocking Nigeria's potential lies in harnessing the power of partnerships—between government, private sector, civil society, and most importantly, the people themselves. Only through collective action can we hope to build a Nigeria where poverty is truly a thing of the past. By pursuing these research avenues and translating findings into actionable, context-specific policies, Nigeria can chart a course towards a more equitable and prosperous future for all its citizens.

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Addressing Parental Responsibilities as a Nexus for Nigeria's Sociocultural Revolution

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Abstract

This paper investigates the pivotal role of parental guidance in shaping Nigeria's sociocultural landscape and explores the effects of parental failure on youth behaviour, societal values, and national development. Employing a qualitative methodological approach, the study examines the narratives and lived experiences of Nigerian families, drawing from extensive literature reviews, case studies, and cultural analyses. Grounded in Attachment Theory, the research provides a comprehensive understanding of how parenting impacts societal outcomes. The findings highlight that parental failure manifests in various forms, including lack of supervision and engagement, cultural and economic pressures, negligence of parental responsibilities, and deficiencies in educational background. In this context, parental failure refers to the inability or unwillingness of parents to adequately nurture, guide, and provide for their children, resulting in a range of negative outcomes for individuals and society. These manifestations contribute to widespread social issues such as juvenile delinquency, substance abuse, and the erosion of ethical values. The study underscores the importance of addressing parental failure as a catalyst for sociocultural transformation in Nigeria, arguing that a more cohesive and progressive society can be cultivated by empowering parents and tackling the root causes of parental failure through collaborative efforts from government, NGOs, and community leaders. Key recommendations include implementing parental education programs to equip parents with effective parenting skills, establishing economic support systems to alleviate financial burdens, and promoting cultural reorientation to encourage active and engaged parenting.

Keywords: Parenting, Parental Failure, Juvenile Delinquency, Socio-cultural Revolution

respect for elders, communal living, and moral integrity have historically been integral to the social fabric (Falola, 2001).

This paper explores the nexus between parental responsibilities and Nigeria's sociocultural evolution, proposing that addressing these failures is essential for fostering a sociocultural revolution. By examining the root causes of parental failure and its impacts on youth behavior and societal values, the study seeks to provide a framework for systemic change.

The qualitative methodological approach adopted in this study involves an in-depth analysis of existing literature, case studies, and cultural narratives to uncover the underlying factors contributing to parental failure in Nigeria. This approach allows for a nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between individual, familial, and societal factors. By exploring the lived experiences of Nigerian families, the study aims to provide actionable insights and recommendations for fostering a sociocultural revolution.

Addressing parental failure is crucial for Nigeria's sociocultural revolution. By empowering parents through education, support, and cultural reorientation, Nigeria can cultivate a more cohesive and progressive society. This paper calls for collaborative efforts from government, NGOs, and community leaders to spearhead initiatives that reinforce the importance of effective parenting in national development. Through such efforts, Nigeria can lay the groundwork for sustainable development and social cohesion, ultimately achieving a brighter future for its children and society as a whole.

Literature Review

Parental Failure and Child Development

The role of parents in child development has been extensively studied, with consensus pointing towards the critical impact of parental behavior on various aspects of a child's life. According to Attachment Theory developed by John Bowlby in 1969 children form attachments with their caregivers, which serve as a foundation for their emotional and social development. Secure attachments are formed when parents are

responsive and sensitive to their children's needs, whereas insecure attachments result from inconsistent or neglectful caregiving. Insecurely attached children are at a higher risk of developing behavioural problems and mental health issues (Ainsworth, 1979).

Economic Challenges and Parental Failure

Economic hardship is a significant factor contributing to parental failure in Nigeria. Parents facing financial difficulties often work long hours or multiple jobs to make ends meet, resulting in limited time and energy for parental engagement (Egbo, 2012). The stress associated with economic instability can also affect parental mental health, further impairing their ability to provide adequate care and support for their children (Conger, et al., 1992). Studies have shown that economic hardship is correlated with increased instances of child neglect and abuse, as well as poorer educational outcomes for children (Wadsworth & Santiago, 2008).

In Nigeria, the economic challenges are compounded by a lack of social support systems and adequate public policies. The absence of robust welfare programs means that many families lack access to essential resources such as healthcare, education, and housing, exacerbating the effects of poverty on family dynamics (Oyeniya, 2013). The intersection of economic hardship and parental failure creates a vicious cycle where children from impoverished families are less likely to receive the support and opportunities needed to break out of poverty.

Cultural Influences on Parenting

Cultural norms and values play a crucial role in shaping parenting practices and expectations in Nigeria. Traditional Nigerian culture places a high value on respect for elders and hierarchical family structures, often emphasizing obedience and conformity over individual expression and autonomy (Falola, 2001). While these values can foster strong family bonds and community cohesion, they can also limit open communication and critical thinking, particularly in parent-child relationships (Omoegun, 2007).

Cultural expectations can also contribute to parental failure by placing undue pressure on parents to conform to traditional roles and responsibilities. For example, gender norms that assign primary caregiving responsibilities to mothers can limit fathers' involvement in parenting, leading to imbalanced parental roles and increased stress on mothers (Olutayo & Bankole, 2002). Additionally, cultural stigmas surrounding issues such as mental health and parenting support can prevent parents from seeking help when needed, exacerbating the challenges they face (Gureje et al., 2006).

Educational Deficiencies and Parenting

Educational attainment is a significant determinant of effective parenting. Parents with higher levels of education are generally better equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to support their children's development (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003). In Nigeria, however, many parents have limited educational backgrounds, which can hinder their ability to provide appropriate guidance and support for their children (UNICEF, 2018). This issue is particularly pronounced in rural areas, where access to quality education is often limited (Onyukwu, 2011).

Educational deficiencies in parents can also impact their children's academic achievement and aspirations. Research has shown that parental education levels are positively correlated with children's educational outcomes, suggesting that parents who lack education may struggle to foster a conducive learning environment for their children (Fan & Chen, 2001). This creates a cycle of educational disadvantage, where children from less educated families are less likely to succeed academically and attain higher levels of education themselves.

The Interplay of Parental Failure and Societal Outcomes

The cumulative effects of parental failure have significant implications for broader societal outcomes in Nigeria. Children who grow up in environments characterized by neglect, abuse, or lack of support are more likely to engage in antisocial behaviour, including criminal

Erosion of Traditional Values and Ethical Standards

Traditional Nigerian society is built on values such as respect, communal living, and moral integrity. These values are primarily transmitted through family structures and parenting practices. However, when parents fail to provide a stable and nurturing environment, these core values are compromised. The breakdown of traditional family roles and the rise in single-parent households, often resulting from economic pressures and social instability, lead to weakened family bonds and a decline in the transmission of cultural norms (Falola, 2001). Children growing up in such environments may lack the guidance needed to internalize these values, leading to an erosion of societal ethical standards.

Moreover, the prevalence of neglect and abuse within families can contribute to a culture of violence and disrespect. Children who experience or witness domestic violence are more likely to adopt aggressive behaviour and view violence as a normative means of conflict resolution (Jaffee et al., 2003). This perpetuates a cycle of violence that undermines social harmony and ethical conduct, posing significant challenges to societal stability and cohesion.

Impact on Education and Skill Development

Educational attainment is a critical factor in driving sociocultural revolution. It empowers individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for innovation, economic development, and social progress. However, parental failure, particularly in the form of neglect and lack of support for education, severely hampers children's academic performance and future prospects (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003). In Nigeria, many children from disadvantaged backgrounds do not receive the encouragement or resources needed to succeed in school, leading to high dropout rates and limited access to higher education (UNICEF, 2018).

This educational deficit has long-term implications for the country's workforce and economic development. A poorly educated population is less capable of contributing to technological advancements and

economic growth, which are essential components of a sociocultural revolution. Furthermore, the lack of educational opportunities exacerbates social inequalities, creating a divide between the educated elite and the underprivileged masses. This social stratification hinders national unity and the collective effort needed for transformative social change.

Perpetuation of Gender Inequality

Gender norms and expectations play a significant role in shaping parenting practices and, consequently, the impact of parental failure. In Nigeria, traditional gender roles often dictate that women are primarily responsible for child-rearing, while men are seen as breadwinners (Olutayo & Bankole, 2002). These norms can limit the involvement of fathers in parenting and place disproportionate stress on mothers, particularly in the context of economic hardship.

Parental failure, influenced by these gendered expectations, can perpetuate gender inequalities by limiting educational and career opportunities for girls. Girls in families where parents are unable or unwilling to support their education are more likely to be kept at home for domestic duties or married off at an early age (Omoegun, 2007). This not only curtails their personal development but also reinforces the cycle of poverty and gender discrimination. For a sociocultural revolution to take place, it is imperative to address these deep-rooted gender biases and promote equal opportunities for all children, regardless of gender.

Increase in Antisocial Behaviour and Crime

One of the most immediate and visible impacts of parental failure is the increase in antisocial behaviour and crime among youth. Children who grow up in environments characterized by neglect, abuse, or lack of supervision are more likely to engage in criminal activities (Adegoke, 2015). The absence of positive role models and the exposure to harmful behaviour create a predisposition towards delinquency and substance abuse.

The rise in youth crime poses a significant barrier to sociocultural revolution, as it diverts resources away from development initiatives and

towards policing and criminal justice. Additionally, high crime rates create an atmosphere of fear and instability, discouraging investment and community engagement. Addressing the root causes of antisocial behavior through improved parenting practices and supportive family environments is crucial for fostering a safe and productive society.

Implications for National Development and Social Cohesion

The cumulative effects of parental failure extend to national development and social cohesion. Children who do not receive adequate care and support are less likely to become productive and responsible citizens. This affects the overall human capital of the nation, reducing its potential for economic growth and social progress (Blum et al., 2000). Furthermore, the breakdown of family structures and the erosion of cultural values can lead to social fragmentation, where communities become polarized and distrustful.

A sociocultural revolution requires a collective effort towards shared goals and values. Parental failure undermines this collective spirit by fostering environments of neglect, inequality, and conflict. To achieve meaningful social transformation, it is essential to strengthen family units and promote positive parenting practices that support the holistic development of children.

Parental failure has far-reaching implications for Nigeria's sociocultural revolution. It erodes traditional values, hampers educational and skill development, perpetuates gender inequality, increases antisocial behaviour and crime, and ultimately undermines national development and social cohesion.

Case Studies of Parental Failure and Implications

Examining case studies of parental failure provides valuable insights into the complexities and consequences of inadequate parenting practices in Nigeria. These case studies shed light on the diverse factors contributing to parental failure and the multifaceted implications for child development, societal well-being, and national progress. This section presents case studies highlighting different manifestations of

parental failure and their implications for individuals and communities, including a scriptural example from the Bible.

Eli's Parental Failure and the Moral Decline of His Sons

Eli, a high priest and judge of Israel, serves as a poignant biblical example of the repercussions of parental failure on both the family and the broader community. Eli's inability to discipline his sons, Hophni and Phinehas, led to severe moral and spiritual decline, affecting not only his household but also the entire nation of Israel.

Background

Eli's sons, Hophni and Phinehas, served as priests under their father's leadership. Despite their sacred roles, they engaged in corrupt practices, such as taking the best portions of sacrifices for themselves and committing sexual immorality with women who served at the entrance to the Tent of Meeting (1 Samuel 2:12-17, 22). Eli was aware of his sons' misconduct but failed to take decisive action to correct their behavior, merely rebuking them without enforcing any meaningful consequences (1 Samuel 2:22-25).

Implications

The parental failure of Eli had far-reaching consequences for his family and the community:

1. *Moral and Spiritual Decline:* Eli's failure to discipline his sons led to a significant decline in moral and spiritual standards among the priests, which undermined the integrity of religious practices and disillusioned the people of Israel. The priests' corruption eroded public trust in religious institutions, contributing to a broader societal crisis of faith.
2. *Divine Judgment and Family Tragedy:* The lack of effective parental guidance and discipline resulted in severe divine judgment. God pronounced judgment on Eli's household, declaring that both Hophni and Phinehas would die on the same day as a sign of His displeasure (1 Samuel 2:27-36). This

prophecy was fulfilled during a battle with the Philistines, leading to the loss of the Ark of the Covenant and the deaths of Eli's sons (1 Samuel 4:10-11). Eli himself died upon hearing the news, marking a tragic end for his family (1 Samuel 4:18).

3. *National Consequences:* The moral failings of Eli's sons and the subsequent loss of the Ark of the Covenant had profound national implications. The Israelites' defeat and the capture of the Ark symbolized a spiritual low point for the nation, leading to a period of instability and despair. This event highlighted the critical importance of strong, ethical leadership and the devastating impact that parental failure can have on a community's spiritual and moral health.

The case study of Eli and his sons illustrates the severe consequences of parental failure, both within the family and across the broader community. Eli's inability to effectively discipline and guide his sons led to moral corruption, divine judgment, and national calamity. This scriptural example underscores the vital role of parents in shaping the moral and spiritual character of their children and the far-reaching implications of parental failure.

Case Study: David's Parental Failure and Its Implications

King David, one of the most prominent figures in the Bible, is often celebrated for his leadership and devotion to God. However, his failures as a parent had significant repercussions for his family, the kingdom of Israel, and its sociocultural fabric. This case study explores David's parental shortcomings and their implications for both his household and the broader society.

Background

David had several children by multiple wives, which often led to complex family dynamics and rivalries. His failure to address these issues effectively, coupled with his inability to discipline his children appropriately, resulted in serious consequences.

1. *The Incident with Amnon and Tamar*: One of the most notable instances of David's parental failure involves his children Amnon, Tamar, and Absalom. Amnon, David's eldest son, developed an inappropriate desire for his half-sister Tamar. Despite the serious nature of the offense, David's response was passive and inadequate, showing leniency towards Amnon (2 Samuel 13:1-21). This lack of decisive action led to further familial strife.
2. *Absalom's Rebellion*: Absalom, Tamar's full brother, was enraged by David's failure to punish Amnon. This led him to take matters into his own hands, eventually killing Amnon (2 Samuel 13:22-29). Absalom fled and later returned, harboring resentment towards David. This unresolved tension culminated in Absalom leading a rebellion against his father, causing a significant civil conflict within Israel (2 Samuel 15:1-12).

Implications

David's parental failures had far-reaching implications, affecting not only his family but also the kingdom of Israel and its sociocultural development.

1. *Family Dysfunction and Breakdown*: David's inability to manage his children's conflicts and enforce discipline resulted in a dysfunctional family environment. The lack of parental authority and guidance led to severe sibling rivalries and violence. This breakdown in family structure highlights the importance of effective parenting in maintaining family harmony and stability.
2. *Social and Political Instability*: Absalom's rebellion against David had significant political repercussions. The civil war that ensued disrupted the kingdom, causing widespread instability and suffering. This period of turmoil weakened the nation's cohesion and diverted resources from development efforts, illustrating how familial conflicts can escalate to national crises.
3. *Erosion of Moral and Ethical Standards*: David's failure to hold Amnon accountable for his actions sent a negative message about

justice and accountability. This erosion of moral and ethical standards can undermine societal values, leading to a culture of impunity and lawlessness. In David's case, his actions (or lack thereof) set a precedent that influenced the behavior of others within the kingdom.

4. *Long-term Sociocultural Impact:* The turmoil within David's family and the ensuing political instability had long-term implications for Israel's sociocultural development. The civil unrest weakened the central authority, leading to periods of vulnerability and division. This environment hindered the nation's ability to progress and develop cohesively, impacting future generations.

David's parental failures had profound implications for his family and the kingdom of Israel. His inability to address serious issues within his household led to significant familial conflict, social instability, and a decline in moral and ethical standards. These events underscore the critical role of effective parenting in fostering stable family environments and promoting national development.

Solutions to Parental Failure

Addressing parental failure in Nigeria requires practical solutions that empower parents, support families, and promote positive parenting practices.

1. *Parenting Education and Support Programs:* Implementing parenting education and support programs can empower parents with the knowledge and skills needed to provide nurturing and supportive environments for their children. These programs can include workshops, seminars, and counseling sessions focused on topics such as child development, communication, discipline, and stress management. By equipping parents with the tools and resources they need, these programs can help prevent parental failure and promote positive parent-child relationships.
2. *Economic Empowerment Initiatives:* Creating economic empowerment initiatives aimed at alleviating poverty and providing financial stability for families can reduce the risk of

parental failure. These initiatives can include job training programs, microfinance loans, and income-generating opportunities targeted at low-income families. By improving economic opportunities for parents, these initiatives can strengthen family resilience and enable parents to better provide for their children's needs.

3. *Accessible and Affordable Childcare Services:* Expanding access to affordable and high-quality childcare services can support working parents and reduce the burden of caregiving. This can include establishing daycare centers, after-school programs, and early childhood education facilities in communities across Nigeria. By providing safe and nurturing environments for children, these services can enable parents to pursue employment or education opportunities while ensuring their children receive the care and support they need.
4. *Community Engagement and Support Networks:* Promoting community engagement and support networks can create a sense of belonging and social connectedness for parents and children alike. This can involve establishing parent support groups, community centers, and neighborhood initiatives that provide opportunities for families to connect, share resources, and access social support. By fostering a sense of community and collective responsibility, these networks can help strengthen family bonds and prevent social isolation.
5. *Strengthen Parental Education and Support:* Implement comprehensive parental education programs that equip parents with effective discipline strategies, moral guidance techniques, and communication skills. These programs should be accessible and culturally relevant, addressing the specific challenges faced by families in Nigeria.
6. *Promote Ethical and Spiritual Leadership:* Encourage parents to model ethical behavior and spiritual leadership within their households. Faith-based organizations and community leaders

can play a pivotal role in promoting values that foster moral integrity and accountability.

7. *Develop Community Support Systems:* Establish robust community support systems that provide resources, counseling, and mentorship for families struggling with parental challenges. By fostering a supportive community environment, parents can receive the assistance they need to guide their children effectively.
8. *Implement Accountability Mechanisms:* Create and enforce accountability mechanisms within religious and community institutions to address misconduct and ensure ethical standards are upheld. This can help prevent moral decline and maintain public trust in leadership.
9. *Parental Accountability:* Encourage parents to take an active role in addressing and resolving conflicts within their families. Accountability and decisive action are essential in maintaining discipline and justice.
10. *Conflict Resolution Training:* Implement conflict resolution training programs for parents and community leaders. These programs can provide the skills needed to manage disputes effectively and prevent escalation.

By implementing practical solutions, Nigeria can create a supportive and nurturing environment for children to thrive. These efforts are essential for driving sociocultural revolution and building a more inclusive and equitable society.

Summary

Parental failure in Nigeria poses significant challenges to child development, societal well-being, and the country's progress towards sociocultural revolution. Economic hardship, cultural norms, educational disparities, and family structure are among the key factors contributing to parental failure. The implications of parental failure are far-reaching, affecting ethical values, educational attainment, gender equality, and social stability. However, practical solutions such as

parenting education programs, economic empowerment initiatives, accessible childcare services, and community support networks can mitigate the impact of parental failure and promote positive outcomes for children and families.

Conclusion

In conclusion, addressing parental failure in Nigeria is essential for fostering sociocultural revolution and building a more inclusive and equitable society. By implementing targeted interventions that empower parents, support families, and promote positive parenting practices, Nigeria can create a nurturing environment where children can thrive and fulfill their potential. These efforts require collaboration between government agencies, civil society organizations, community leaders, and other stakeholders to ensure comprehensive and sustainable solutions. With concerted action, Nigeria can overcome the challenges of parental failure and pave the way for a brighter future for its children and generations to come.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and insights presented in this paper, the following recommendations are proposed:

- 1. Intentional Investment in Parental Education:* Parenting education programs are essential for equipping parents with the necessary knowledge and skills to create nurturing and supportive environments for their children, ultimately fostering healthier development and well-being.
- 2. Promotion of Economic Empowerment:* Economic empowerment initiatives are critical for addressing poverty and providing financial stability for families. Programs such as job training, microfinance loans, and income-generating opportunities play a vital role in improving the socioeconomic status of families.
- 3. Expansion of Access to Childcare Services:* Expanding access to affordable and high-quality childcare services, including daycare centres, after-school programs, and early childhood education facilities,

is crucial. This support enables working parents to balance their responsibilities and reduces the caregiving burden.

4. *Strengthening of Community Support Networks*: Community engagement and support networks are instrumental in fostering connections among families. These networks offer opportunities for resource sharing and social support, promoting social cohesion and a sense of collective responsibility.

5. *Advocacy for Policy Reform*: Policy reforms that address economic disparities, cultural norms, and educational inequalities are necessary to support families. Such reforms aim to create an environment where children and families can thrive, addressing the root causes of parental challenges.

Implementing these recommendations will require coordinated efforts from government agencies, non-governmental organizations, community leaders, and other stakeholders. By prioritizing the well-being of children and families, Nigeria can overcome the challenges of parental failure and realize its aspirations for sociocultural revolution and national development.

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Human Resources Management as Catalyst for Sustainable Church Growth in Local Baptist Churches in Oyo Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated human resources management as catalyst for sustainable church growth in local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis with objectives of investigating the root causes of human resources mismanagement and ascertaining effective human resources management for sustainable church growth among Local Baptist Churches (LBCs) in Oyo metropolis. The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The sample size of the study consisted of 300 respondents made as follows: fifty (50) pastors, fifty (50) deacons, fifty (50) church workers, and one hundred and fifty (150) church members. They are purposefully selected randomly from fifty (50) local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis. A total of six (6) respondents were drawn from each of the fifty (50) local Baptist Churches in the designated sample. The research instruments used for this study were both self-structured questionnaire and interview guide of some leaders in the selected churches. Findings showed that poor leadership and inefficient administration, lack of delegation of authority, lack of insight on the part of leaders, power tussle between leaders and members, slow or lack of technology adoption among others are the root causes of human resources mismanagement in local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis. The means to manage the resources are; utilizing recognition system for church workers, church workers review and evaluations, involving members in the church activities, effective delegation of duties, leadership development, accountability, continuous mentoring, and so on. The study concluded that no church can grow beyond the administrative capacity or administrative sensitivity of the leader in utilizing the available human resources. The study, therefore, recommended that local Baptist churches in

Oyo metropolis through their leaders ensure that human resources are adequately motivated by praise and honest appreciation.

Keywords: **Human Resources Management, Local Baptist Churches, and Sustainable Church Growth**

Introduction

Successful church leadership goes beyond management of plans and tasks. It envisions the future and sets a new direction for the local church. Successful leaders mobilize all possible means and human resources; they inspire all members of the local church to support the new mission and execute it with enthusiasm. Human Resources (HR) management is widely recognized as an important way to improve organizational performance. Many companies have adopted a number of human resource management policies and practices to more clearly reflect the contribution of their employees to the bottom line. However, the goals and practices of human resource management are not without criticism, and while there are many ethically-oriented analyzes of various aspects of human resource management, there is little evidence of the role of human resources in church organizations (Fremaux & Michelson, 2017:34-37).

HR management is used as an umbrella term that encompasses all aspects of human resource practices such as: recruitment and selection, performance evaluation, personnel policy, personnel philosophy, and practices aimed at attracting, retaining, motivating, and developing employees (Armstrong & Taylor, 2017). Scholars pointed out that within the church's unusual structure as an institution symbolically referred to as the body of Christ, the church still needs to be managed in the same way as other secular institutions (Oosthuizen & Lategan, 2015:551-555). Scholar agrees that the church is both an institution and a spiritual entity, and that church leaders need to understand both aspects of this definition. Therefore, suffice it to say that church leaders, such as the top clergy of the church, should be aware of the need for specialized expertise in the church's HR management function (O'Brien, 2019). Therefore, it

is imperative to understand human resource management in the context of religious organizations, especially with respect to the internal and external factors prevalent in these organizations.

Statement of Problem

The ideal approach to leadership in managing human resources for sustainable church growth has been a major challenge for the church. Churches are generally reluctant to use management science in church administration (Oosthuizen & Lategan, 2015). Also, it has been contended that the church's lack of management science training posed challenges in performing basic administrative tasks, including personnel management (Sifuna-Evelia, 2017). In addition, some pastors in churches and church organizations are well educated in spiritual formation but lack administrative aspects and therefore face administrative challenges (Gibson, 2018). Such deficiencies lead to inefficient management of the church's human resources, resulting in problems such as poor performance. However, the aforementioned studies have not sufficiently explored management of human resources for sustainable church growth. Therefore, this paper sought to explore issues that lead to mismanagement of HR for lack of sustainable church growth and as well to discuss effective management of human resources for sustainable church growth in Local Baptist Churches (LBCs) in Oyo metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

This paper aims to examine human resources management as a catalyst for sustainable church growth in Local Baptist Churches (LBCs) in Oyo metropolis. The objectives are to:

1. investigate the root causes of human resources mismanagement among LBCs in Oyo metropolis
2. ascertain how human resources can be managed for sustainable church growth among LBCs in Oyo metropolis.

Literature Review

Concept of Human Resources

Human Resources (HR) is the set of people who make up the workforce of an organization, business sector, industry, or economy. A narrower concept is human capital, the knowledge and skills which the individual's command. Similar terms include manpower, labor, or personnel. The Human Resources department (HR department) of an organization performs human resource management, overseeing various aspects of employment, such as compliance with labor law and employment standards, interviewing and selection, performance management, administration of employee benefits, organizing of employee files with the required documents for future reference, and some aspects of recruitment (also known as talent acquisition) and employee off boarding (Blaine, 2017:137).

Human resources serve as the link between an organization's management and its employees. The duties include planning, recruitment and selection process, posting job ads, evaluating the performance of employees, organizing resumes and job applications, scheduling interviews and assisting in the process and ensuring background checks. Another job is payroll and benefits administration which deals with ensuring vacation and sick time are accounted for, reviewing payroll, and participating in benefits tasks, like claim resolutions, reconciling benefits statements, and approving invoices for payment (Heathfield, 2021). Human Resources also coordinate employee relations activities and programs including, but not limited to, employee counseling.

Pioneering economist John R. Commons mentioned "human resource" in his 1893 book "The Distribution of Wealth" but did not elaborate. The expression was used during the 1910s to 1930s to promote the idea that human beings are of worth (as in human dignity); by the early 1950s, it meant people as a means to an end (for employers) (Kaufman, 2008). Among scholars the first use of the phrase in that sense was in a 1958 report by economist E. Wight Bakke (McGaughey, 2018). One major concern about considering people as assets or resources is that they will be commoditized, objectified, and abused. Human beings are not

One of the essential qualities of God's kingdom is growth. The church is a living organism and any healthy organism must essentially grow. This is reflective in the teachings of Jesus about the principles of fruitfulness, commission to go and make disciples and his parables about growth in the kingdom of God (Hayward, 2000:2-3). There is no doubt that the Church world-wide has experienced a substantial and exponential growth from its inception in the first century till now. What started with a few above hundred people in Judea has now grown to millions of people globally. However, sustainable church growth is geared towards attracting new people and repelling those who remain. This is why a scholar emphasizes the balance of qualitative and quantitative growth in the definition of Church growth. Church growth is all that is involved in bringing men and women that do not have a personal relationship with Jesus Christ into fellowship with Him and into responsible Church membership (Wagner, 2007:18). This appears to give a good picture of a sustained Church growth. People are brought to become part of the Church and then made to become responsible church members who are committed to following the Lord in all its ramifications. Also, if organizational and structural development is neglected, growth will be hindered. When new people are not effectively absorbed into the church because of poor or lack of leadership development of programmes to meet their needs, the church will keep experiencing growth problem.

On the other hand, if organizational development is emphasized without careful attention to quantitative and qualitative growth, the church will not be distinguishable from the average social club. The church is a living organism, the body of Christ; and it should grow in size, in effectiveness, in faithfulness and in outreach. Scholar argues that sustainable church growth requires three balances: balancing the five-fold purpose of God for His church, balancing the eight areas of church growth and balancing the natural and supernatural dimensions of church growth. Balancing the five-fold purpose of God for His church implies that the church must increasingly be experiencing the power and presence of God in worship (worship); be increasingly reaching out to the lost and winning them (evangelism); becoming deeper in mutual love (fellowship); be more and

more like Christ, growing into deeper maturity as more disciples are being raised in the Church (discipleship); and be increasingly giving opportunities of service to members as they all affect the community more and more (ministry) (Rainer, 1990:448-9).

Balancing the eight areas of church growth means that the church must simultaneously and correspondingly be increasing in size and number; adding more structures as well as material resources to create more conducive environment; planting more churches; growing in grace and knowledge of Christ; increasing in income, and sharing love more and more. The natural dimension of church growth refers to the need for the pastor and church workers to make efforts and put some things in place for the church to grow. The supernatural dimension is for God to bring the actual growth by releasing His power and grace upon the pastor and church workers, blessing their growth efforts and supernaturally causing the growth to occur. In actual fact, sustainable church growth is ensuring the three balances are sustained and maintained (Rainer, 1990).

Sustainable growth requires the church making all necessary adjustments to catch up with technological advancement. Sustainable church growth also requires the church to help workers in performing the described role by learning to assign responsibilities and select church workers based on their SHAPE (spiritual gifts, heart, abilities, personality and experience). For sustainable church growth, church workers in pastoral leadership, diaconate leadership, new members' assimilation, and all committees'/ministries' heads must appreciate the importance of every member's involvement.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. It involves collecting data that accurately and objectively describe how things are in their present situation. The population comprised all leaders, workers and members in all churches in Oyo metropolis. The sample size of the study consisted of 300 respondents made as follows: fifty (50) pastors, fifty (50) deacons, fifty (50) church workers, and one hundred and fifty (150) church members. They are purposefully selected

randomly from fifty (50) local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis. A total of six (6) respondents were drawn from each of the fifty (50) local Baptist Churches in the designated sample. The research instruments used for this study were both self-structured questionnaire and interview guide of some leaders in the selected churches.

Result and Discussion

To investigate the root causes of human resources mismanagement in LBCs in Oyo metropolis

Table 1: Root Causes of Mismanagement of Human Resources in LBCS in Oyo Metropolis

Items	Respondents	SA	A	SD	D	Total
Poor leadership and inefficient administration	Pastors	24	25	1	0	50
	Deacons	17	31	0	2	50
	Workers	32	18	0	0	50
	Members	83	54	2	11	150
	Total	156	128	3	13	300
	Total Percentage	52%	42.7%	1%	4.3%	100%
Lack of delegation of authority	Pastors	17	23	6	4	50
	Deacons	29	15	1	5	50
	Workers	29	15	0	6	50
	Members	75	45	19	11	150

	Total	150	98	26	26	300
	Total Percentage	50%	32.6%	8.7%	8.7%	100%
Lack of insight on the part of leaders	Pastors	24	15	1	10	50
	Deacons	21	23	5	1	50
	Workers	23	22	4	1	50
	Members	103	34	0	13	150
	Total	171	94	10	25	300
	Total Percentage	57%	31.4%	3.3%	8.3%	100%
Poor communication skill between the leader and members	Pastors	19	26	0	5	50
	Deacons	23	19	6	2	50
	Workers	32	16	0	2	50
	Members	98	36	4	12	50
	Total	172	97	10	21	150
	Total Percentage	57.3%	32.4%	3.3%	7%	100%
Clergy/laity conflict	Pastors	21	23	4	2	50
	Deacons	13	28	3	6	50
	Workers	20	27	2	1	50
	Members	94	35	11	10	150
	Total	148	113	20	19	300

	Total	49.3%	37.7%	6.7%	6.3%	100%
	Percentage					
Hectic schedules and overwhelming workloads on both the leaders and members	Pastors	31	18	0	1	50
	Deacons	19	25	3	3	50
	Workers	23	27	0	0	50
	Members	79	60	7	4	150
	Total	152	130	10	8	300
	Total	50.7	43.3%	3.3%	2.7%	100%
	Percentage					
Lack of accountability	Pastors	23	19	0	9	50
	Deacons	27	19	2	2	50
	Workers	28	15	7	3	50
	Members	58	71	13	4	150
	Total	136	124	22	18	300
	Total	45.4%	41.3%	7.3%	6%	100%
	Percentage					
Slow or lack of technology adoption	Pastors	17	23	6	4	50
	Deacons	29	15	1	5	50
	Workers	29	15	0	6	50
	Members	75	45	19	11	150
	Total	150	98	26	26	300
	Total	50%	32.6%	8.7%	8.7%	100%
	Percentage					
Little or no motivation for church workers	Pastors	23	19	0	9	50
	Deacons	27	19	2	2	50
	Workers	28	15	7	3	50
	Members	58	71	13	4	150
	Total	136	124	22	18	300
	Total	45.4%	41.3%	7.3%	6%	100%
	Percentage					

Power tussle between leaders and members	Pastors	19	26	0	5	50
	Deacons	23	19	6	2	50
	Workers	32	16	0	2	50
	Members	98	36	4	12	50
	Total	172	97	10	21	150
	Total Percentage	57.3%	32.4%	3.3%	7%	100%

Source: Field work 2024

Table 1 shows the responses of the respondents on the root causes of mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis. The table reveals that poor leadership and inefficient administration is a contributing factor for mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis as agreed by 94.7% of the respondents. Every church has real possibilities for growth but the major responsibilities rest on church leadership. Human resources management poses a challenge to the church. Part of the wastage which the church is experiencing is on human resources. There are so many untapped human resources waiting on the pews of the church today. This calls for administrative improvement (Olaleye, 2012). Lack of delegation of authority is another cause of mismanagement of human resources s agreed by 82.6% of the respondents. 88.4% of the sampled population agreed that lack of insight of the part of leaders is a cause for mismanagement of human resource in churches in Oyo metropolis. This affirmed by scholar that once a leader’s job grows beyond his personal capacity to achieve, his success lies in his ability to teach others (that is, multiply himself through others), and share the jobs with the able ones, so that the greater jobs, because of his unique organizational placement, he performs alone (Adeniji, 2008).

Also, the table shows that 89.7% of the respondents agreed that poor communication skill between the leader and members is one of reasons for mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis. In the same vein, 87% of the respondents agreed that clergy/laity conflict resulted into mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis. The table further reveals that hectic schedules and overwhelming workloads on both the leaders and members is a cause for mismanagement of human resources with 94% respondents agreeing to the statement. Moreover, 86.7% of the respondents agreed that lack of accountability is a cause for mismanagement of human resources. Item eight of the table shows that 82.6% of the respondents agreed that slow or lack of technology adoption is cause for mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis. Another cause of mismanagement of human resources as little or no motivation for church workers as 86.7% respondents agreed with the statement. The last item of the table shows that 89.7% of the respondents agreed that power tussle between leaders and members is cause for mismanagement of human resources in churches in Oyo metropolis.

Figure 1: Perception of Respondents on the Root causes of human resources mismanagement in Local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis

How to managed human resources for sustainable church growth in local Baptist churches in OBC

Table 2: Management of Human Resources for Sustainable Church Growth in Local Baptist Churches in Oyo metropolis

Items	Respondents	SA	A	SD	D	Total
Utilizing recognition system for church workers	Pastors	29	18	1	2	50
	Deacons	37	13	0	0	50
	Workers	39	7	2	2	50
	Members	93	54	2	1	150
	Total	198	92	5	5	300
	Total Percentage	66%	30.6%	1.7%	1.7%	100%
Church workers reviews and evaluations	Pastors	39	7	0	4	50
	Deacons	26	20	1	3	50
	Workers	43	7	0	0	50
	Members	95	25	15	1	150
	Total	203	59	16	2	300
	Total Percentage	67.7%	19.7%	5.3%	7.3%	100%
Involving members in the church activities	Pastors	29	21	0	0	50
	Deacons	21	27	1	1	50
	Workers	23	26	0	1	50

	Members	103	43	0	4	150
	Total	176	117	1	6	300
	Total	58.	39	0.3	2	100
	Percentage	7%	%	%	%	%
Effective delegation of duties	Pastors	19	26	0	5	50
	Deacons	23	25	0	2	50
	Workers	32	16	0	2	50
Unity of purpose	Members	98	36	4	1	50
	Total	172	103	4	2	150
	Total	57.	34.	1.3	7	100
	Percentage	3%	4%	%	%	%
	Pastors	21	27	0	2	50
	Deacons	13	28	3	6	50
	Workers	20	27	2	1	50
Good relational skills/communication	Members	94	46	0	1	150
	Total	148	128	5	1	300
	Total	49.	42.	1.7	6.	100
	Percentage	3%	7%	%	3%	%
	Pastors	31	18	0	1	50
	Deacons	19	25	3	3	50
	Workers	23	27	0	0	50

	Members	79	60	7	4	150
	Total	152	130	10	8	300
	Total Percentage	50.7	43.3%	3.3%	2.7%	100%
Good leadership and administration	Pastors	23	19	0	9	50
	Deacons	27	19	2	2	50
	Workers	28	15	7	3	50
	Members	58	71	13	4	150
	Total	136	124	22	18	300
	Total Percentage	45.4%	41.3%	7.3%	6%	100%
Accountability	Pastors	17	23	6	4	50
	Deacons	29	15	1	5	50
	Workers	29	15	0	6	50
	Members	75	45	19	11	150
	Total	150	98	26	26	300
	Total Percentage	50%	32.6%	8.7%	8.7%	100%
	Pastors	23	19	0	9	50

Continuous mentoring	Deacons	27	19	2	2	50
	Workers	28	15	7	3	50
	Members	58	71	13	4	150
	Total	136	124	22	1	300
	Total Percentage	45.4%	41.3%	7.3%	6%	100%
					8	
Right orientation	Pastors	19	26	0	5	50
	Deacons	23	19	6	2	50
	Workers	32	16	0	2	50
	Members	98	36	4	1	50
	Total	172	97	10	2	150
	Total Percentage	57.3%	32.4%	3.3%	7%	100%
Effective budgeting and implementation.	Pastors	39	7	0	4	50
	Deacons	26	20	1	3	50
	Workers	43	7	0	0	50
	Members	95	25	15	1	150
	Total	203	59	16	2	300
					5	
				2		

	Total	67.	19.	5.3	7.	100
	Percentage	7%	7%	%	3	%
Complimenting spirit	Pastors	21	23	4	2	50
	Deacons	13	28	3	6	50
	Workers	20	27	2	1	50
	Members	94	35	11	1	150
	Total	148	113	20	1	300
					9	
	Total	49.	37.	6.7	6.	100
	Percentage	3%	7	%	3	%
						%

Source: Field work 2024

Table 2 shows the perception of the respondents on the management of human resources for sustainable church growth in local Baptist Churches in Oyo metropolis. The table shows that 96.6% of the respondents agreed that utilizing recognition system for church workers is one of the ways for the management of human resources. Church workers reviews and evaluations is another way for the management of human resources as agreed by 87.4% of the respondents. 97.7% of the respondents agreed that involving members in the church activities is one way for the management of human resources in local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis. Subsequently, 91.7% of the respondents agreed that effective delegation of duties is a means on how to manage human resources in the church. It further shows that 92%, 94%, 86.7%, and 82.6% of the respondents are of the opinion that unity of purpose, good relational skills/communication, good leadership and administration, and accountability respectively are the practical ways to effectively manage human resource in local Baptist churches in Oyo

metropolis. The table shows that 86.7% of the respondents agreed that continuous mentoring is a way to manage the human resources in the church. Right orientation to the kingdom service is another way on how to manage the human resources in the church as agreed by 89.7% of the respondents. 87.4% of the respondents agreed that effective budgeting and implementation is also a means for the management human resources in the church. The last item of the table shows that complimenting spirit is one way for human resources to be well manage in the church as 87% of the respondents agreed with the statement.

Figure 2: Proportion of respondents on utilizing human resources in LBCs in Oyo metropolis

Conclusion

Successful leadership goes beyond management of plans and tasks. It envisions the future and sets a new direction for the local church. Successful leaders mobilize all possible means and human resources;

they inspire all members of the local church to support the new mission and execute it with enthusiasm. Human resource management is widely recognized as an important way to improve organizational performance. There are lots of wastage in many churches as a result of bad administration. Good administration will put wastage in check. A close study of contemporary trend in church growth clearly shows that new generation churches take advantage of poor administration or administrative loop holes of the older churches to draw their members. The level at which a church would make impact is greatly determined by the level of administration that is put in place. No church can grow beyond the administrative capacity or administrative sensitivity of the leader. Hence, the need for good leadership and administration for the management of human resources for sustainable church growth in local Baptist Churches in Oyo metropolis.

Recommendation

Based on the outcome of the research, the following recommendations are made as follows;

1. Based on the finding that poor leadership and inefficient administration is a contributing factor for mismanagement of human resources in LBCs in Oyo metropolis, therefore church leaders and unit head department should acquire good leadership and administration skills through leadership seminars and conferences geared towards human resources management.
2. The study affirmed that utilizing recognition system for church workers is a way to enhance human resources for sustainable church growth. Therefore, local Baptist churches in Oyo metropolis should ensure that human resources are adequately motivated by praise and honest appreciation. This is because the human resources that are motivated would deliver their best towards organizational growth and development.

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Unsung Heroines: Tarok Women Contributions to the Socio-Economic Development of Their Land

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Abstract

This study celebrates the pivotal role Tarok women have played in the development of Tarok land, despite their often-overlooked contributions. The researcher conducted a qualitative study analyzing historical and contemporary data from various sources including books journal articles and interviews. Tarok women have been the backbone of the local economy, driving progress in agriculture, trade, and commerce. Through their entrepreneurial spirit and hard work, they have established thriving businesses, created employment opportunities, and stimulated economic growth. Beyond their economic contributions, Tarok women have also been instrumental in preserving and promoting the rich cultural heritage of Tarok land. They have played a vital role in passing down traditional knowledge, skills, and practices to younger generations, ensuring the continuation of Tarok customs and traditions. Furthermore, Tarok women have been at the forefront of community development initiatives, working tirelessly to improve healthcare, education, and social welfare in Tarok land. Their selfless dedication to community service has had a profound impact on the well-being and quality of life of the Tarok people. This study aims to shed light on the remarkable socio-economic contributions of Tarok women, highlighting their agency, resilience, and determination. By recognizing and valuing their contributions, we can work towards a more inclusive and equitable development of Tarok land, where women are empowered to reach their full potential and continue to drive progress for generations to come.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Empower Tarok Women, Socio-Economic Contributions, Development*

Introduction

The Tarok is an ethnic group found in Plateau State, Nigeria, they are found majorly in Langtang North and Langtang South Local Government Areas of

Plateau State. They are also found in large numbers in Mikang, Kanke, Wase, Shendam, Kanam and Pankshin Local Government Areas of Plateau State. A good number of them are found in part of Tarawa State (Lar 2015) have a rich cultural heritage and a strong tradition of entrepreneurship and community development. However, the contributions of Tarok women to the development of Tarok land have often been overlooked. According to Nden (2013), “Tarok women are described as beautiful, very industrious, very conservative, independent and with great powers of endurance.” He further cited Cooper who stated that:

Tarok women are tall... with beautiful arms and shoulders that – European women might well envy. Like most African pagans, they carry themselves with dignity and grace, obtained by the custom, from earliest years of putting loads on their heads... Indeed, compared with the neighbouring tribes, in many respects they may well be proud of themselves, which undoubtedly they are the Tarok as a tribe are very clean in their habits, and the women remarkably so. This may be to the fact their husbands refuse to eat the food they have prepared if they had not washed. Twice a day, morning and evening, the babies have a bath.

Nden (2013) described the Tarok woman in the following ways:

1. They are very industrious and have no room for lazy girl or woman in the community. Women have their particular responsibilities in each season of the year. From early age they learn to handle and care for little babies, they learn to handle and care for little babies; they learn to handle the small hoe, grinding on the grinding stones, cooking, fetching water and firewood. They learn to take messages from one adult to the other and from their homes to their neighbours. They put long hours and hard work into their farms during the farming season. All the vegetables are solely women’s properly.
2. Tarok women are capable and clever. They love their homes and children. Both male and female children are closer to their mothers than their male parents. Tarok women are hospitable and generous in sharing the little food they have.
3. They are musical people. They celebrate everything in songs and dance. They are motivators. During the time of intertribal wars the women

carried their wounded husbands on their backs for treatment. With women following closely behind, no man could run away from the war front. Any attempt was restricted by the women; such a runaway soldier was asked to come into a woman's womb to be born again.

4. They teach morals. Through songs, women encourage good habits and through it they discourage all forms of bad habits and laziness in the family any in the community. This attracts children to their mothers so much that both male and female were called by their mothers' names.

This study aims to shed light on the remarkable socio-economic contributions of Tarok women, highlighting their agency, resilience, and determination. Research has shown that women play a vital role in economic development and poverty reduction in Africa.¹ In Nigeria, women have been found to be active participants in the informal sector, contributing significantly to the country's GDP (World Bank, 2019). However, their contributions are often undervalued and unrecognized (Napbut, 2023).

This study builds on existing research on women's empowerment and socio-economic development in Africa, highlighting the specific experiences and contributions of Tarok women. By recognizing and valuing their contributions, we can work towards a more inclusive and equitable development of Tarok land, where women are empowered to reach their full potential and continue to drive progress for generations to come.

Tarok Women are the female population of the Tarok ethnic group, residing in Tarok land, Plateau State, Nigeria. They are very industrious and have no room for a lazy girl or woman in community. Socio-economic contributions encompass the various ways in which Tarok women contribute to the development of Tarok land, including economic, social, and cultural aspects. Development refers to the process of improving the quality of life and well-being of individuals and communities, encompassing economic, social, and political dimensions. Entrepreneurship is the creation and management of businesses, organizations, and initiatives by Tarok women, driving innovation and economic growth. Empowerment is the process of enabling Tarok women to reach their full potential, exercising their agency, and making informed choices about their lives and communities.

Women in Tarok Traditional Religion

In Tarok traditional religion, women play a significant role in spiritual and cultural practices. The Tarok woman is very important in the Tarok traditional religion. The woman cooks and brews the wine that is used in the shrine. She does not go to the shrine but without her, nothing will be done in the shrine. She cooks and brews the wine among other things (Nden, 2013). Shagaya summarised the value of the woman in Tarok traditional religion thus: “The women cook food, brew local beer and take to the shrine. The ancestral spirits bless the women who have prepared the food and drink, and promise to solve their problems” (2005). It is very ironical that women are those that buy food, prepare the food and brew the wine that is taken to the *Orim* masquerades but the women are forbidden from seeing the same *Orim* that they feed and entertain. Lakan states that: “Each time masquerades (*Orim*) comes out, no woman or teenager was allowed to see them”. The Tarok women have no free will (1998).

They are revered for their spiritual power and ability to communicate with the divine (Nden, 2021). Women are also responsible for passing down traditional knowledge and practices to younger generations, ensuring the continuation of Tarok customs and traditions (Napbut, 2023).

Women's roles in Tarok traditional religion include:

- a. *Spiritual leaders*: Women serve as spiritual leaders and priestesses, leading rituals and ceremonies (Shagaya, 2005).
- b. *Diviners*: Women are skilled diviners, using their knowledge of herbs, rituals, and spiritual practices to diagnose and solve problems (Napbut, 2023).
- c. *Healers*: Women are respected healers, using their knowledge of traditional medicine to treat physical and spiritual ailments (Nden, 2021).

Despite their significant contributions to Tarok traditional religion, women's roles are often overlooked and undervalued (Napbut, 2023). This study aims to shed light on the important contributions of women in Tarok traditional religion, recognizing their agency, resilience, and determination.

Challenges Faced by Women in Tarok Land

Despite their significant contributions to the development of Tarok land, women in Tarok land face numerous challenges that hinder their progress and empowerment. Some of the challenges faced by women in Tarok land include:

- a) *Gender-based discrimination:* Women in Tarok land face discrimination and marginalization, limiting their access to resources, opportunities, and decision-making positions (Nden, 2021).
- b) *Limited access to education:* Women in Tarok land have limited access to education, which restricts their economic opportunities and perpetuates gender inequality (Napbut, 2023).
- c) *Economic exclusion:* Women in Tarok land are often excluded from economic decision-making and have limited control over resources, perpetuating poverty and inequality (Nden, 2021).
- d) *Cultural and social barriers:* Women in Tarok land face cultural and social barriers that restrict their autonomy and agency, limiting their ability to make choices about their lives and communities (Napbut, 2023). Blench (2005) stated that, “Tarok society is strongly patrilineal and have highly authoritarian attitudes towards women.”
- e) *Limited access to healthcare:* Women in Tarok land have limited access to healthcare, which exacerbates maternal mortality and perpetuates health inequalities (Nden, 2021).

These challenges underscore the need to recognize and address the gender-specific barriers that women in Tarok land face, in order to promote their empowerment and socio-economic development. Socio-economic contributions of women to the development of Tarok land.

Socio-economic Contributions of Women to the Development of Tarok Land

Women in Tarok land have made significant socio-economic contributions to the development of their community, despite facing various challenges and barriers. Their contributions can be seen in the following areas:

- a) *Agriculture:* Women in Tarok land are actively involved in agriculture, producing food crops and cash crops, and contributing significantly to food security and the local economy (Shagaya, 2005). Trade and

Commerce: Women in Tarok land are engaged in various trading activities, including the sale of agricultural produce, crafts, and other goods, generating income and stimulating economic growth (Napbut, 2023).

- b) *Entrepreneurship*: Women in Tarok land have established thriving businesses, creating employment opportunities and driving innovation and economic growth (Nden, 2013).
- c) *Cultural Preservation*: Women in Tarok land have played a vital role in preserving and promoting the rich cultural heritage of Tarok land, passing down traditional knowledge, skills, and practices to younger generations (Napbut, 2023).
- d) *Community Development*: Women in Tarok land have been at the forefront of community development initiatives, working tirelessly to improve healthcare, education, and social welfare in Tarok land (Nden, 2021).

These socio-economic contributions of women to the development of Tarok land are a testament to their agency, resilience, and determination. By recognizing and valuing their contributions, we can work towards a more inclusive and equitable development of Tarok land, where women are empowered to reach their full potential and continue to drive progress for generations to come.

Major Findings

The contribution of Tarok women to education is quite overwhelming, considering the fact that Tarok land is an agrarian society. The contributions include: The paying of school fees, and welfare of their children. Sunday Fadip Gomo (Oral interview) points to the researcher as a product of a woman because his mother was responsible for his education. According to Ponyak Nandang, the women “pay school fees.” In fact, more than 75% of the respondents positively agreed that women teach their children, pay school fees and have admiration for education as most of the private schools are owned by women. Respondents were unanimous in mentioning Prof. Mary Lar, Mrs. Esther Wazhi and Mrs. Esther Bali as proprietress of schools in Langtang. For instance, Aunty

Mary Schools (Nursery, Primary and Secondary) are owned by Prof. Mary Lar (Oral Interview) (Napbut, 2023).

The education by Tarok women snowballed into the following:

- a. *Bible Translation*: The Tarok people were used to the Hausa Bible. However, the Bible has been translated into Tarok language. Prof. Mary Lar was instrumental to the translation of the Bible to Tarok. The first part translated to Tarok language was the New Testament which was put to use in the early 1980s. 100% of respondents agreed that Prof. Mary Lar was the brain behind the translation (Shagaya, 2005).
- b. *Tarok literature and literary activities*: Literature have been published in Tarok language courtesy Prof. Mary Lar. According to 100% of respondents, she is responsible for the publications of *Nre nkun Tarok* volumes 1-3, *Tarok Story* books and the *Tarok Hymn* book (Shagaya, 2005). “Tarok mothers train their girl children in school. Through the sacrifice of *Mbai-lele*, the mother of Prof. Mary Lar, her daughter (Mary) schooled and became the first principal in Northern Nigeria and the first female professor in Northern Nigeria” (Longtau, Oral Interview 5th January, 2020). The education of Tarok women is recognised in the training of their girl children through teaching them how to grind on the grinding stone while singing. They taught their children how to be good wives and mothers. 100% of the respondents agreed their grinding, storytelling and folktales are means through which the Tarok women inculcate moral values into their children (Napbut, 2023). For their teaching abilities, Rev. Selbut Longtall (oral interview) stated that “Tarok women are the main vehicle for maintaining Tarok language.” Prof. Juliana Mwafil (oral interview) pointed out that the Tarok women were very instrumental to the establishment of the first community school in Plateau state. It was known as Langtang Community Secondary School, “popularly known in Tarok as comm,” which was established in 1970. It is now Secondary School Langtang. Women contributed by fetching water, making gruel *kunu* and also cooking for the community as they worked (Napbut, 2023).

Respondents were unanimous in pointing at Prof. Patricia Lar as a mobiliser and motivator for girl-child education in Tarok land. Her advocacy has encouraged and stimulated many girls and even married women to go back to school.

Politics at an earlier stage was considered the exclusive right of men. However, there were very strong women who were involved. Rev. Dr. Selbut Longtal (oral interview) said, “Shirmmicit Zhenbin and Amina were powerful politicians and mobilisers. They give men money to contest elections.” In fact, to show that politics was an exclusive right of men, the late Emancipator and first civilian governor of Plateau State (Chief Solomon Daushep Lar) labeled a popular woman known as “Majo” a prostitute because she attempted to participate in politics. But the Emancipator, after some times and much awareness of the game of politics, apologised to her (Prince Ramson and Prof. Juliana Mwafil, Oral interview) (Napbut, 2023).

The temporary setback and interplay of patriarchy did not deter women from politics. 100% of respondent believed that the participation of Tarok women into politics has brought better dividends of democracy to Tarok land even more than their male counterparts. Prominent among Tarok women who participated and are into active politics include: Mrs. Esther Wazhi, Mrs. Jummai Datyem, Hon. Dinah Lar, Hon. Beni Butmak Lar, Hon. Joyce Lohya Ramnap, Late Hon. Martha Tonga, Late Nanna Nansoh and Hon. Lohfe Dashe. The contributions or dividends of democracy brought by individual women include: Hon. Dinah Lar who was responsible for the electrification of Tukun (Chief Ndam Gambo, Oral interview). Hon. Esther Wazhi as a Local Government Transition Committee Chairperson achieved the following in Langtang North Local Government Council; provision of vehicles for the Nigerian Police, provision of water tankers and water reservoirs in areas facing difficulties of water supply and supply of educational materials to schools within the Local Government Areas (Napbut, 2023).

Hon. Beni Butmak Lar, a member Federal House of Representative representing Langtang-North and Langtang-South Local Government Areas achieve much as respondents were unanimous in numerating her achievements. The following are ascribed as dividends of democracy to Tarok land courtesy of her. Her achievements include the following: Women and youth Empowerment,

Agriculture, Water Supply, Education, Environment, Health and Sport, power and Employment (Napbut, 2023).

Beni Lar Empowered women and youths through training of 400 women in various skills; Training of youth in different skills at the industrial fund with trade test certificate; Provision of vocational and micro credit loan scheme for women in Langtang North and South in conjunction with AUNTY MARY Literacy scheme. She established a centre for youth empowerment to promote self-employment and income generating skills among the youths in Wallang, Langtang North, and skills such as Carpentry, Mason, Tailoring, Hairdressing, Mechanic, Welding and GSM repairs; Facilitated the training of youths Langtang South on computer literacy, up to Diploma Level, as well as training of Langtang South youths in (I.T.F) Jos.; Training of women and youth with start-up packs in PRODA; Training of women and youth with start-up packs in NABDA; Training of women and youth with start-up packs in FIIRO; Skill acquisition Training for women and Youths with start-up packs in NILEST; Training of youths in shoe making and other leather products in NILEST; Training of youths in various skills including auto mechanic , solar panels and others in NARICT and She has done numerous disaster reliefs within the constituency (Napbut, 2023).

Beni Lar established the following agricultural scheme: Established a Youth Agricultural training scheme in December 2007. The goal is to encourage youths to be self-employed through Agriculture and dry season farming; Register and sponsored Fadama cooperative groups in 32 wards of the constituency with PADF in 2008; Liaised with the British High commission to incorporate Mban FADAMA users association, that is, Mban community in Langtang North for dry season (irrigation) farming in her constituency and that of Jemkur community in Langtang South; Personally donated many water pumps to farmers to serve the same purpose to 8 districts to promote dry season farming; Annual supply of all year round fertiliser to farmers and Annual supply of other farm implement to farmers (Napbut, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the pivotal role that Tarok women have played in the development of Tarok land, despite their often-overlooked

contributions. Through their entrepreneurial spirit, hard work, and selfless dedication to community service, Tarok women have driven progress in agriculture, trade, and commerce, preserved and promoted the rich cultural heritage of Tarok land, and improved healthcare, education, and social welfare in Tarok land.

Women are the backbone of the local economy and have been instrumental in driving progress in various sectors. Similarly, highlights the critical role that women have played in preserving and promoting Tarok customs and traditions, stating that Women have been the custodians of Tarok culture and have played a vital role in passing down traditional knowledge, skills, and practices to younger generations (Napbut, 2020).

This study has also highlighted the agency, resilience, and determination of Tarok women, who have overcome various challenges and barriers to make significant socio-economic contributions to their community. As emphasized by (Kabeer, 2005), Women's empowerment is critical for achieving equitable and sustainable development.

By recognizing and valuing the contributions of Tarok women, we can work towards a more inclusive and equitable development of Tarok land, where women are empowered to reach their full potential and continue to drive progress for generations to come.

Recommendations

1. *Recognition and Valuation of Tarok Women's Contributions:* Efforts should be made to recognize and value the socio-economic contributions of Tarok women, highlighting their agency, resilience, and determination.
2. *Empowerment and Capacity Building:* Initiatives should be implemented to empower Tarok women, building their capacity in areas such as entrepreneurship, leadership, and community development.
3. *Inclusive Development:* Development strategies should prioritize the inclusion of Tarok women, ensuring their participation and benefiting from development initiatives.
4. *Preservation and Promotion of Cultural Heritage:* Efforts should be made to preserve and promote the rich cultural heritage of Tarok land,

recognizing the vital role Tarok women play in passing down traditional knowledge, skills, and practices.

5. *Community Development Initiatives*: Initiatives should be implemented to improve healthcare, education, and social welfare in Tarok land, building on the selfless dedication of Tarok women to community service.

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The Impacts of the Proliferation of Churches on the Socio-Cultural Development and Economy of Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the history and spread of Christianity in Nigeria, the factors responsible for the proliferation of churches in Nigeria, and its impact on the socio-cultural development and economy of Nigeria. The theory adapted was church growth theory formulated by Donald McGavran, which investigates the planting, multiplication, function, and health of the churches as they relate to God's great commission to make disciples of all nations as in Matthew 28:19-20. The study used a quantitative research design. Self-administered questionnaire of 40 copies was used for data collection. The findings revealed that the impacts were both positive and negative. The positive impacts of church proliferation apart from the spreading of the gospel as commanded by Jesus Christ in Matthew 28:19-20 include education from nursery to tertiary levels (90%), job creation (82.5%) health (80%), spiritual solution and healings (80%) and religious transformation (75%) among others. The findings also through respondents identified some negative impacts being made by church proliferation which include: commercialization of the gospel (82.5%), low-quality Christian teaching (75%), denominational undue competition (85%), low moral standard of people (72.5%) and family disintegration (70%). In controlling the proliferation, the majority of respondents strongly agreed that the government should enforce discipline on misbehaved ministers (82.5%). Gospel ministers to preach more on holiness (80%), Christian bodies like CAN

and PFN should checkmate their members (80%) and ready Christian leaders and ministers should be helped (75%). In conclusion, the positive impacts of the proliferation of churches have been adding value and good growth to the socio-cultural and economy of Nigeria while the negative impacts have been counselling great pain to the society in Nigeria. Therefore, efforts should be made to control the negative impact both by the government and Christian bodies like CAN and PFN, refocusing ministers to pure teaching and preaching of holiness messages instead of the gospel of prosperity.

Keywords: Proliferation of Churches, Socio-Cultural Development, Economy, Nigeria

Introduction

The continuous springing up of churches in Nigeria is highly alarming. Almost every street in the major cities of the country is hosting nothing less than two churches. Many houses have been converted to worship centres. Even some denominations like the Redeemed Christian Church of God have made it a rule to have worship centres at a five-minute workable distance from each other across the nation (Olusegun, 2020:61). However, as the number of churches increases, so, the impact is being felt positively and negatively on the socio-cultural development and economy of Nigeria.

Christianity makes up about 56% of the population of Nigeria, a country regarded as a secular state by the constitution (Akanbi & Bayers, 2017:1). However, it is grossly noted that one of the challenges facing Christianity in the country presently is the issues of the proliferation of churches. It has been observed that beside the established denominations founded by the missionaries such as Anglicans, Catholics, Baptists, Methodists and the likes, Nigeria has a large number of Africa instituted, independent and Pentecostal churches that are very active in evangelism and church planting even in other countries in Europe, North America and other parts of the world (WCC; 2019).

History and Spread of Christianity in Nigeria

Historically the Augustinian and capuchin monks from Portugal brought Christianity to Nigeria in 15th century (Haruna 2018;175). Although slave trade activities of the time limited the missionary activity (Lekin 2012:2), the religious revival amongst the Europeans and Americans after the abolition of slave trade ignited a fresh resuscitation (Adamolekun 2012:4). Different missionary groups began their Christian missions in Nigeria in the 19th Century (Nwadiakor 2015:16). The first of such missionaries was Henry Townsend of the Church of England who arrived at Badagry in 1842. (Haruna 2018:175). This was followed by other protestant denominations from the United States, Canada and Britain followed by Roman Catholic religious order in the 1860s (Metz, 1991).

The colonial masters used Christianity as one of the instruments to win the hearts of the people in their colonies. The Christian missionaries preached messages of eternity through holiness, condemning worshipping of idols, detestable African custom practices like killing of twins, killing of people with hunchbacks and human sacrifice (Omojino, et al, 2016: 637). Some of the freed slaves in Africa also helped in the propagation of Christianity in the 19th century. Some of these African freed slaves traced their root back home. Freed Nigeria slaves were brought back to places like Lagos and Badagry from Sierra Leone while some settled in Abeokuta and other Western Nigeria cities (Olulana, 2015: n.p). Prominent among these freed slaves was Samuel Ajayi Crowther who later became the first African to be ordained as a bishop by the Christian Missionary Society (CMS) (Olulana, 2015: n.p). On the spread of Christianity in Nigeria, St. Peter's Church was founded in Lagos in 1853 by Catechist James White, Reverends Charles Gollmer and Ajayi Crowther (Olulana 2015: n.p). The Christian Missionary Society established churches in many towns like Abeokuta (1846), Lagos (1851), Ibadan (1853) and Oyo (1856). Then CMS churches began to spring up in South-Eastern Nigeria of Bonny and Brass as main centres (WASSCE 2018:100). From this time forward, churches began to spread across the country of Nigeria.

Notwithstanding, the indigenous people felt that religious needs were not met by the missionaries which led to the emergence of growth of independent church movements (Obiefuna, Nwadiolor & Umeamolue, 2016). Not only that, the members' expectation from the mainline churches were not met. The missionaries failed to address the type of questions the indigenous raised for them on witchcraft, demon possession, hunting by evil spirits, the cult of ancestors, the use of protective charms, talisman, sorcery and traditional dancing at the shrines (Mbanefo, 2002:29).

Presently in Nigeria, Christianity is undergoing transformation with the rapid proliferation of churches. Many Pentecostal churches are springing up. Pentecostalism having been influenced by Acts 2:1-13 and Joel 2:28-30 that talk of God pouring out His Spirit upon all the people in the last days, now develop around the world (Metton, 2020). Thousands of Pentecostal churches have sprang up in Nigeria since 1970 which made it the fast proliferating independent churches (Diara and Onah, 2014). It is observed that there are over 300,000 early Pentecostal churches in Nigeria with 4.2 million members of denominations like Christ Apostolic Church, the Apostolic Church, Celestial Church of Christ, and the Cherubim and Seraphim Church. New Apostolic Christians in Nigeria include The Redeem Christian Church of God, Deeper Life Church, Foursquare Gospel Church and other new spring-up churches (Haruna 2018:175-192). There are, at the same time about 380,000 new Apostolic church parishes constituting about 6.5 million believers. A scholar is of the opinion that some of these churches started as Christian fellowship centres before metamorphosing into churches. For example, Deeper Life Church, the Redeem Christian Church of God, Living Faith Church, Rhema Church and many others started as Christian fellowship centres (Fatokun, 2016). All these happened for them to fulfill the commandment of Jesus Christ in Matthew 29:19-20 and Mark 16:25-18.

Theoretical Framework

The appropriate theory adopted is church growth theory formulated by Donald McGavran which defines as that science which investigates the planting, multiplication, function and health of the churches as they relate specifically to the effective implementation of God's commission to make disciples of all nations as in Matthew 28:19-20. The theory strives to combine theological principles of the Bible concerning insights of contemporary social and behaviour sciences (Wagner, 1980:509).

The polity of church growth theory designed for success in outreach and growth while centralized pastoral leadership is seen as the key vision and motivation in the assignment (Wagner, 1976:65). This theory further provided a military approached definition of leadership that would be effective for growth. Jesus Christ as the Commander-in-chief. The local church is like a company with one company commander, the pastor, who gets order from the commander-in-chief. The company commander has lieutenants and sergeants under him for consultation and implementation, but the final responsibility for the decision is that of the company commander, and he must answer to the commander-in-chief. "If you believe God has called me to pastor this church, then you follow me". (Wagner, 1976:65).

This leadership model is clearly highly centralized and autocratic. The pastoral role is defined as the chief executive officer (CEO) of a corporation or commander of an army. The autocratic model of leadership places an important emphasizes on motivating and training lay leadership to reach people for church and the church. This centralized leadership of many local churches is highly effective and have led to phenomenal numerical growth (McGavran & Hunter III 1980). The formulation and teachings of this theory since late 1970s brought about the recorded explosive church growth from the 1980s till date.

Findings

Selection A: Personal Data

Majority of the respondents are worker of churches, follow by pastors/priest while few are founders. Their age range between 30-39

years, 40-49 years mostly. Majority of them are also civil servants by profession.

Selection B: Opinion Questions

Observing part A of the table on factors responsible for the proliferation of churches, it could be observed that 25 respondents which is 62.5% strongly agreed that God's calling leads to proliferation of churches, 28 respondents which is 70% strongly agreed that hard economics condition causes proliferation, 20 respondents, that is 50% strongly agreed that church persecution leads to proliferation of churches, 26 respondents which is 65% strongly agreed that Jealousy and unhealthy rivalry leads to church proliferation, 23 of the respondents 57.5% strongly agreed that illiteracy leads to church proliferation and 18 respondents which is 45% strongly agreed that religion doctrinal differences leads to proliferation of churches.

From part B of the table, on the impacts of proliferation of churches on socio-cultural and economy of Nigeria. Those who favour that church's proliferation is making positive impacts are the followings: 36 respondent, which is 90% consented that it is making positive impact on education, 32 respondents that is 80% agreed that its making positive impact on health, 33 respondents 82.5% consented that it is making positive impact on job creation/opportunities, 32 respondents which is 80% agreed that it is making positive impact on spiritual solutions/healings, 30 respondents, that is 75% that it is making positive impacts on both religiously and rapid evangelization.

However, majority of respondents agreed that proliferation of churches is making negative impact on the following areas: 33 respondents, which is 82.5% agreed that its making negative impact on Gospel commercialization, 30 respondents, which is 75% agreed that its making negative impact of the quality of Christian teachings, 34 respondents that 85% agreed that its making negative impact on denominational competition, while 28 respondents that is 70% agreed that its having negative impact on family, its making negative impact on moral standard of the people.

On part C: Controlling the proliferation of churches in Nigeria, majority of the respondents strongly agreed on the followings measures, 32 respondent which is 80% strongly agreed on balancing messages between holiness and prosperity is needed, 32 respondents which is 80% also strongly agreed that involvement of Christian bodies like CAN and PFN is needed to curb its negative impact, 30 respondents, that is 75% strongly agreed that helping of needy Christian leaders and ministers would help to control its negative impact, and 33 respondents 82.5% strongly agreed that government's enforcement of discipline on misbehaved ministers would help to curb its negative impact.

Discussion of Findings

This study has made it clear that proliferation of churches has both positive and negative impacts on the socio-cultural and economy of Nigeria. On the positive impacts, apart from the primary assignment of spreading of the gospel of Jesus Christ and the fulfilment of great commission in Matthew 28:19-20 through planting of churches. The church proliferation, from the responses of respondents identified such areas like: education (90%), job creation (82.5%), health (80%) and religious transformation (75%) spiritual solution /healings (80%) amongst others. However, the respondents also identified the areas of where church proliferation is making negative impact which are commercialization of gospel (82.5%) low quality Christian teaching (75%), denominational undue competition (85%) low moral standard of people (72.5%) and family disintegration (70%).

Although, with the rapid spread and growth of the churches in almost every street of Ado Ekiti in particular and Nigeria, generally, people have been living together with understanding. Church proliferation is expected to be the fulfilment great commission in Matthew 28:19-20, for spiritual growth economic development, and social improvement of the church members and people in the area. Pastors are expected to stand for the truth and preach it is order to enjoy the expected confidence of their people.

Factors Responsible for the Proliferation of Churches in Nigeria

These are some factors responsible for the proliferation of churches in Nigeria. The most prominent factors are:

1. *God's Callings*: Divine calling could be traced to be one of the factors. Many founders and the general overseers of churches claim that God called them or have been directly mandated to spread the gospel. This led to many of them going ahead to establish churches in response to the call. Paul affirms that God gives supernatural ability to certain members of the body of Christianity. But to each one of us grace has been given by God to every individual for teaching, prophecy, healing and so on. Jesus Christ gave some to be apostles, prophets, evangelists, pastors and teachers (Ephesians 4:7-11). One of the researchers personally experienced it in 1996 when he received this kind of divine call that made him to leave Lagos in 1999 to obey the call of the work of ministry to Ogbomoso. One thing that people normally use as a prove is that God would always allow signs and wonders to back up the ministry of the person who is divine called.
2. *Hard Economic Condition*: The economic hardship of the civil war was noted to be a factor to proliferation of churches. Many lost their daily livelihood, properties, jobs and other viable resources. This made many people to turn to God. There is economic undertone for closure of many business warehouses and they are turned to places of worship. Many turned churches to a way of daily living. This is notable in many cities and communities. Some churches have become business ventures where the innocent and ignorant people are exploited (Ikeazota, 2013)
3. *Persecution*: Persecution is seen as one of the influences of proliferation of churches. The overzealous and arrogant amongst and uncontrollable members, when they are not tolerated and unacceptable end up breaking out into new churches (Emeronys,

7. *Jealousy and Unhealthy Rivalry*: This has caused proliferation of churches and happens in two ways (Haywood, 2009:9). Firstly, a subordinate may become jealous of the leaders which may cause him to start his own ministry. Secondly, it may be the leader that is jealous of his junior worker all because of his growing popularity through his charismatic gifts, anointing and grace of God upon his life and ministry (Ikeazota, 2013)
8. *Protection/Security*: Searching for spiritual security, protection and powers has led to the establishment of churches that cause proliferation of churches. Too many diabolical experiences in Nigeria make many people to be seeking and searching for churches and individuals that can offer them protection. So, such individuals may be empowered to go and start the daughter churches of the same pattern for the same purpose (Ikeazota 2013).
9. *Illiteracy*: Illiteracy is found everywhere. The high level of illiteracy among members leads so many of them to be brainwashed by their leaders through erroneous teaching without members having the knowledge to examine the preaching of the leaders. This makes proliferation of churches to thrive more among illiterates in Nigeria.
10. *Religious Doctrinal Differences*: This has been a serious factor in the proliferation of churches in Nigeria. Doctrine is the major backbone of every denominational teaching, belief and mode of worship. Any moment someone or group of people feel uncomfortable with a doctrinal teaching or a mode of worship, they pull out to go and start their own church or gathering. This forms the major reason for the establishment of many church denominations in Nigeria (Ruth, 1993:9)

Positive Impacts on Socio-Cultural Development and Economy of Nigeria

There are both positive and negative effects of the proliferation of churches on the society and economy of Nigeria (Olusegun, 2020). The positive ones can be analyzed as follows:

1. *Education:* The positive aspect of the proliferation of churches on education in Nigeria could be seen through the establishment of nursery and primary schools, secondary schools and universities which are equipping the younger generation the needed knowledge to excel.
2. *Health:* Many of these church denominations established teaching hospitals, mission hospitals, maternity homes and other health institutions to take care of people's health challenges apart from prayers they offer for people.
3. *Job Opportunities:* All aspects of the proliferation of churches are sources of job creation. More people are making their livelihood through the churches they founded and in employing many others, they pay salaries. The schools and hospitals they established are sources of income to their employees and indirectly to many other people around them including the tax they pay to the government.
4. *Spiritual Solutions:* People with different kind of spiritual and physical attacks or problem used to get solutions to their problems through many church programmes like revivals and crusades organized by these churches. Healings, deliverances and breakthroughs are undeniable blessings many people have enjoyed through their programmes.
5. *Religiosity:* Having so many churches founded and planted everywhere in Nigeria, religion make people to realize that Nigeria is a highly religious nation and that many Christian churches abound in Nigeria (Adamolekun, 2023).
6. *Formation of Christian Bodies:* Another blessing of proliferation of churches is the formation of Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and its blocks which stands as a pressure group and

umbrella used by Christians as mouthpiece to fight any injustices or government policies that are against the interest of the Christians in the nation.

7. *Rapid Evangelization*: It is worth saying that the proliferation of churches brought great growth to Christianity in Nigeria. Many have left their paganism to embrace Jesus Christ as their Lord.

Other benefits include development of new leaders, promotion of specialization in ministry, provision of spiritual environment for solving human problem

Socio-Cultural impact on the positive side shows that the church proliferation has contributed the following to the society: through numerous prayer programmes, the church is interceding for the society thereby causing people lives to transform, many who used to be involved in bad behaviours are being morally transformed and become gentle and well behaved members of the society. So the church discharges its responsibility to God for society in carrying out its pastoral assignment to the society at large (Niebuhr, nd). Many Christians believe that it is part of their duties to help others around them by providing food, cloth and shelter for the poor and needies. Socially non-Christians benefit from the education, hospitals and job opportunities of the church (BBC Bitesize, 2024). It is therefore not all the activities of church proliferation that is bad.

Negative Impacts

The negative impacts brought by the proliferation of the churches in Nigeria are numerous but few of them are the followings:

1. *Commercialization of the Gospel*: Most of the churches under this umbrella have been discovered through their practices to commercialize the gospel by the sale of religious materials of which Jesus Christ Himself gave to people free. These materials cost less outside of the church than in the churches where they practice it. They sell things like perfumes, incense, etc. with the claim and ability to perform miracles. Even these churches have commercialized miracles, healings, and deliverance by charging

- high prices and the collection of consultation fees. This is against Matthew 10:8 that says “freely you receive, freely you must give.”
2. *Lack of Quality Christian Teachings:* The teachings, preaching’s and ministrations of some pastors, founders and priests of churches have reduced the standard and quality of Christianity to ordinary messages on materialism, self or personal projection. These teachings cannot produce the quality of Christians expected by Jesus Christ (Nkechi & Agbo, 2021). For instance, more emphasis is laid on prosperity and not on the biblical injunction to seek first the kingdom of God and every other thing shall be added to you (Matthew 6:33). They base their preaching and teaching on earthly treasures instead of preaching on holiness, righteousness and Christian virtues.
 3. *Unhealthy Competition:* The gross unhealthy rivalry and competition has been brought to the Christian faith by the proliferation of churches. With the arrival of Pentecostalism, every church struggles for popularity and miraculous power coupled with unhealthy competition. They believe that any Christian who does not belong to their church is not a genuine Christian (Nkechi & Agbo, 2021). This has motivated many church leaders erecting church buildings close to each other to win their converts. The members go around inviting others to their churches. Likewise, two or three churches are found in the same building. Crusades and conventions are stages of making more money and no longer for the wining of converts for Christ. The unhealthy competition leads to fight and strife among church pastors and turn them away from genuine evangelism.
 4. *Family Disintegration:* As a result of proliferation of churches, some of the Pentecostal churches believe that problems, mishaps and misfortunes could be caused by the operation of witches and wizards. Many families have suffered disintegration because of fake prophecies of the prophets and founders of these ministries. There are several cases where these prophets accuse women of been the cause of their husbands’ and children’s misfortune.

Likewise, they accuse children of using witchcraft to destroy their parents' fortune. Many are accused as using their witchcraft spirits to cause sickness and bad luck like sudden death, accident, poverty cancer, miscarriages and the likes. These fake prophets use this medium to exploit and take advantage of the ignorant members (Nkechi & Agbo, 2021). In a situation where members of the same family attend different churches, there is bound to be disagreements because everyone would receive different prophecies from their prophets and each will be protecting the uniqueness and faith of the denominations.

5. *Moral Decadence*: The springing up of churches in thousands is becoming more worrisome in Nigeria. The moral standard of Christianity in the time past is now very low. The moral worth of pastors before the law enforcement agents is now zero. Some pastors have been accused of sexual abuse of women and girls. The news of this always attracts readers in the daily newspapers. Many of these pastors and founders are in prison because of it. For example, a pastor was arrested for impregnating married women and young girls in his church (Nkech & Agbo, 2021). Another pastor was arrested for repeatedly raping his biological daughter since 2015. He impregnated and aborted the pregnancies for her three times. Some churches were also shut down by the government (Daily Champion 18, June, 2009). Indecent dressing of "come as you like" are acceptable in these churches. Many ladies go to church half nude. Some wear tight dresses. They based their point on God looks at the heart and not at the outward appearance.

Negatively, socio-culturally, some of these churches do cause several forms to pollution to the society like noise pollution, congestion of both traffic and buildings, immoralities of all forms among the unregenerated members and leaders. It also part of socio-cultural negativities for church people to be duping and stealing, with tricks, the people fund in the name of prosperity and prophecy.

Controlling the Proliferation of Churches in Nigeria

Although, certain benefits have been pointed out as the advantages of proliferation of churches in Nigeria. However, the excessive rate at which churches are springing up couple with all disadvantages attached should be put under controls. The followings are, therefore, some of the points to note (Omonijo, et al, 2016):

Strike the balance between messages on prosperity and holiness. One of the major characteristics of Pentecostal churches is their quest for wealth and prosperity. This makes them to be known as prosperity preaching churches. Therefore, the main message on holiness, righteousness and kingdom of God (Matthew 6:33) should be given a priority above that of prosperity in order to redirect their followers' attention to Jesus Christ.

Ministers of the gospel should stop protecting corrupt and dubious people either from public or private sectors, in their churches. Being the watchmen of the flock, they should know that it is their duties to leads their members aright. This may encourage members to live a God-fearing and holy life. Just like Elijah, the prophet to king Ahab (1 Kings 21:20-24), it is the duty of the pastor to tell their members nothing but the truth. If the Pentecostal ministers can do their best to call politicians to order by leading them to swear that God should discipline them if they embezzle public fund or cheat people, this would cause some of them to fear God.

Another way of controlling the evil done through proliferation of churches is by involving the Christian bodies. The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and the Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (PFN) should get all pastors and their churches registered before they could be allowed to practice. There should be registration committee that would be made up of highly experienced ministers who would ascertain the genuine calling of such ministers by God. Likewise, disciplinary committee should be set up to handle every activity of misconduct and misbehavior among the existing ministers and churches.

Helping of needy ministers is another way of controlling the proliferation of churches. A Christian or minister who is passing through

hard time or financial difficulty should be helped and assisted as Jesus did on many occasions (Acts 10:38; Mark 10:46-52; Luke 19:5-6; 2 Kings 4:1-4). This would help them reduce the thought of starting their own ministries to make money.

There should be a publicized renewal with great emphasis on restitution in Pentecostal churches as found in Luke 19:8 on Zacchaeus so that all their pastors would be giving opportunity to repent, restore and realign their relationship with people they have offended and God. Majority of stolen properties would be restored through this arrangement.

Conclusion

This research has shown that proliferation of churches in Nigeria has gone beyond establishment of churches for the sake of eternity alone. Unlike when Christianity newly arrived Nigeria through the efforts of missionaries. The mission churches popularly known as mainline churches continued with the vision of the missionaries. However, independent founders majorly from the Pentecostal circle came to make great deal of the church and turn it to religious business purely to enrich themselves. This is the major reason for the proliferation of churches throughout the country except the fanatical Islamic areas. It is noted that many factors led to the proliferation of these churches that include God's calling, hard economic condition, persecution, high political ambition in church system, disagreement between leaders and members, excessive desire for wealth and greed, jealousy and rivalry, protection and security, illiteracy, religious doctrinal differences among many others. The impacts which are both positive and negative on Nigeria socio-cultural and economy are numerous. The positive impacts include, establishment of many schools from nursery to tertiary institutions by these churches. Likewise, the establishment of hospitals and various health centres have positive impacts on the people, other positive impacts of proliferation of churches are creation of job opportunities for people, finding spiritual solutions to problems, formation of Christian bodies to curb the system and rapid evangelization of the country to fulfill the biblical great commission in Matthew 28:19-20.

The negative impacts caused by the proliferation of churches include the commercialization of the gospel, lack of quality Christian teachings, unhealthy and unethical competition, family disintegration, moral decadence and many others. With the mixture of both, positive impacts want to make its control to be difficult. However, many steps should be taken in curbing the effect of church proliferation since it is now very rear not to hear evil done by many of these churches' ministers every week, either on raping, embezzlement, robbery, ritual of the gospel.

The impacts of proliferation churches in the socio-cultural and economy of Nigeria shows that the spreading of churches fulfils the great commission of Jesus Christ. It is also making positive impacts on education, health, employment creation, spiritual solutions and healing. The negative impacts include: commercialization of the gospel, lack of quality Christian teachings, unhealthy competition, family disintegration and moral decadence. However, the negative impacts could be controlled by the government, Christian bodies and through helping those ministers and leaders who are having financial challenges.

Recommendations

The followings are the recommendations to stop or curb the negative effects of proliferation of churches in Nigeria:

Christian Association of Nigeria and all its blocks that make up the Christian body should be overhauling together with its constitution and mode of operations. For instance, the Pentecostal churches that are major victims of proliferation and having the largest units of churches are just sharing a block in CAN with the CPFN known as CPFN/PFN. Christ Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria (CPFN) and Pentecostal Fellowship of Nigeria should have different blocks at CAN. These two bodies should be saddled with the responsibility of monitoring and watching their members in a godly way.

Adequate discipline should be given to the unregenerate founders or ministers who bring worldliness and sinful approach to the operation of their churches like dupe, rape and fake prophecies.

Any church noticed to open purely for business or any other purpose apart from preaching and evangelism should be closed and sealed up. Security operative should monitor all these churches.

Every proliferated church minister or founder should enforce discipline on undisciplined members who commit adultery, fornication, robbery and hooliganism. Like a church in Kawangware, Kenya where the founder enforces strict discipline to maintain moral standards among its worshippers (Davidic, 2024)

Federal government should enforce law and order, and strictly discipline any church leader who break the law and order the land.

All founders and senior ministers should endeavor to take good care of the welfare of those under them. This would curb going to establish ministry for prosperity's sake.

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Assessment of the Implementation of Mission and Vision Statements and Leadership Training of New Life College of Theology and Mission, Ibadan, Oyo State

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Abstract

Mission strategies are the set of procedures, plans and directions for implementing the biblical mission programmes and activities in churches and Christian organisations. Despite the efforts of New Life For All Nations Ministries in producing missionaries and evangelists, its popularity has been minimal and the activities of the church have been relatively obscured. This paper assessed specific mission strategies adopted by New Life College of Theology and Missions, Ibadan towards achieving her mission and vision statements and leadership training. The study used a descriptive survey research design with thematic analysis to process the data collected in relation to the research that addresses the problem identified. Findings revealed that various leadership training approaches included vision-setting, mentorship, and innovative teaching approaches geared towards fulfilling the trainees' ministerial calling, coupled with academic empowerment that fosters growth within New Life College of Theology, Ibadan. Hence, the discourse concludes that vision and mission statement formulation guide the mission strategies for active and good leadership training for Christian missions. Therefore, the study recommends that both the missionary trainers and the church must be in

tandem to contribute towards developing effective leadership training approaches and mission strategies that align with the objectives of fostering growth within New Life College of Theology and Mission and the wider church community.

Keywords: Leadership Training, Mission and Vision Statements, Mission Strategies Theological Education, College of Theology and Mission Ibadan

Introduction

Christian mission involves reaching out to people of other faiths with the gospel of Jesus Christ. This is a missional commandment of Jesus Christ to his disciples to make disciples in all corners of the globe. Furthermore, mission involves the crossing of border expedition to another, nation, community, tribe, language, and ethnic, and culture. It is a deliberate and conscious effort to break barriers of culture, language, norms, ethnicity, remoteness, and expose others to the doctrines of Christ over a period of time (Ibiyeomie, 2021: 12-19). Missions requires an interculturalist who promotes cultural diversity and sensitivity to accommodate all the cultures within a community. The term, missionary is a person sent to another place to proclaim the gospel. A missionary involves in cross-cultural activities to convert non-believers to Christ.

The missionaries has an integral role to play in the advance of Christianity for their specific purpose of sharing the word. For a missionary to be effective and productive on the field, it requires a deliberate effort to learn new language, ideology, culture, norms, and values of the people. This is what is referred to as *Doing Contextual Theology* since needs and challenges of people divergent in different contexts (Pears, 2009: 80-85). People from various cultural backgrounds and values enrol in missionary institutions to be trained and at the end of their training program, where they would be required to work in various mission fields. As a result, there should be a blueprint for leadership strategies for cross-cultural training in missionary institutions. This will help in the training of effective and efficient leaders who will become knowledgeable in the field of cultural diversity.

The missionary trainers in missionary institutions must also be grounded in effective leadership approaches to run and maintain missionary institutions. The missionary trainers in missionary institutions should be skilled in intercultural communication to be able to present their visions, expectations and goals effectively to the prospective missionaries or missionaries in-training. Furthermore, flexibility is also very important for both trainers and trainees as this virtue is quite important for adaption to new environments and decision-making processes. A missionary institution should be an environment where people respect and value other people's cultural norms, values and traditions. A missionary institution should be a place where missionary trainees from diverse backgrounds are encouraged to exchange ideas, and share experiences, which will help build mutual understanding and further learning among the missionary trainees. Missionary leaders need to have conflict and dispute resolution approaches to rebuke respectively and constructively. They should be skilled in mediation and negotiation, fostering harmony and unity within the community. A missionary leader should be aware of the changes in the global environment with innovative technology, and new strategies that encourage church growth.

New Life For All Nations Ministries

The New Life for All Nations Ministries was established in 1972 as part of the universal body of Christ, called the Church. New Life Gospel Church is the church arm of New Life For All Nations Ministries for discipleship, ministering and mentoring, while the Ministries consist of the administrative outreach over the churches. New Life Gospel Church is a local Pentecostal church with a missional orientation since its inception.

The following is the vision of The New Life For All Nations Ministries: to expand the gospel of Jesus Christ to all nations of the world, to plant churches structured and governed in accordance with New Testament principles and practices in every nation, to teach, to train those who give

their lives to Jesus Christ and to go with the gospel of Jesus Christ to places where Christ is not yet known (New Life Publications).

To pursue this vision, New Life Mission Institute was established in 1992 by the leading of the Holy Spirit to teach and make disciples of all nations. The nomenclature, New Life College of Theology and Mission was adopted in 2016. New Life College of Theology and Mission is an interdenominational mission, pastoral, and theological centre, established for the work of the Lord, where people are trained, tutored, and exposed to the knowledge and deeds of Jesus Christ. The college admits and trains all ministers of Gospel, church leaders, and church workers (including the youth) irrespective of their denominations and religious affiliations. The college also admits students of any race, colour, or tribe for mission training. However, despite the efforts of New Life For All Nations Ministries in producing missionaries and leading in evangelism, very little has been done in relation to the assessment of its mission strategies and leadership training.

The objective of New Life College of Theology and Mission is to build men and women who are called of God into teams that share a common vision and goals. The following are the objectives of the college:

- to provide instructions and training to students in Theology, Pastoral Studies, Missions and other areas that can enhance effectiveness in the ministry;
- to train church leaders and workers on leadership and church ministries;
- to train women in leadership and missionary involvement;
- to train youths in leadership development, short-term missionary involvement and capacity building in youth services;
- to run short-term programs on Deacon-ship etc.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to study leadership training and visions and mission statements of New Life College of Theology and Mission towards the fulfilment of the 'Great Commission' as commanded by Jesus Christ. This is used to

systematically describe the population of study between 2013 and 2023. It involves a careful observation and analysis of information obtained from a representative sample as described by Papadopoulou et al, (2022: 502). Thus, the purposive sampling technique was adopted as it is relevant to select missionary trainers and missionary trainees among those involved in mission work at New Life College of Theology and Mission, Ibadan. The sample comprises twenty (20) respondents including ten (10) missionary trainers/leaders who are members of the staff at New Life College of Theology and Missions, Ibadan, and ten (10) missionary trainees of New Life College of Theology and Missions in Ibadan. The ten-year period was covered due to the unavailability of sufficient data from previous years. The choice of New Life College of Theology and Mission is due to its enormous missionary training programmes employed by the school to achieve the 'Great Commission'. The age range of respondents between 31 and 70 years of age. Semi-structured questions were used to collect information from the interviewees. The oral interview format consisted of nineteen (19) questions, divided into four sections, with each section focusing on the objectives of leadership approaches adopted by the mission trainers in New Life College of Theology and Mission, Ibadan.

The Concept of Biblical Leadership Training

The concept of leadership is an old phenomenon and examples of leadership attributes abound in the Holy Bible since the creation of nature, plants, and animals in the world (Simić, 2020: 1-13). Individual(s) are required to lead at every level of socio-political, and economic life of a family, organization, and the society. The leader is defined as someone or group of people who selects, equips, trains, and influences follower(s) who have diverse gifts, abilities, and skills and orientations. The leader ensures the followers adhere to the organization's mission and objectives, making the followers (either willingly or unwillingly) expend spiritual, emotional, and physical energy in a concerted coordinated effort to achieve the organizational mission and objectives (Hsu, 2022: 104). A leader is defined as a person

who sets goals for other people or team-mates, and then leads or rallies them to achieve those goals (McClellan, 2022: 3-24). A leader is also described as a person who instructs and controls people to secure predefined goals or targets. Scholars have posited that leaders are not only interested in effecting change for the purpose of benefiting the organization and its members, but also for the development and growth of the people they are working with (McClellan, 2022: 3-24 and Simić, 2020: 1-13). From these definitions, leaders are people who shape the goals, motivations, and actions of others through inspiration and encouragement.

Good leaders provide directions, inspiration, and guidance to their team members. They also exhibit courage, passion, confidence, commitment, and ambition. They influence their team members to work on their individual strengths and talents and build teams committed to achieving common goals (McClellan, 2022: 3-24). A leader can recognize diversity among the followers and is flexible to adapt to the differences among the group (members of his immediate community). Although anyone can occupy a leadership position as a result of promotion or inheritance but to become effective and productive, a leader needs training to have effective communication skills.

People in position of leadership must have the skill to connect with team members and encourage growth. Leaders must also be open to change and develop positive attitudes. A leader fails and becomes ineffective if such personality resists change and is unable to develop good working relationships with others. Leadership in this sense also fails when the leader is not visionary and is not able to meet the objectives of the organization. While effective leadership styles have a positive impact on the people in the organization, ineffective leadership have a negative impact on the individual, the team members, and the organization as well. In addition, ineffective leadership prioritize the leaders' interests above those of the team and that of the organization (O'Dell, et al, 2023). An organization fails if the leadership lacks important characteristics or abilities to succeed. Leaders also fail if they possess undesirable qualities (Khan et al, 2023: 101). Various leadership strategies can be employed

by leaders in various spheres of life, such as in missions, to engage their team members, missionary trainees, and trainers to influence and encourage excellent performance that helps the organizations achieve their objectives. The relationship between the success of an organization and its leadership also applies to the growth of a church. This approach can be applied to the 'Great Commission' of Jesus Christ to all Christians, that is – to evangelise the world. Leadership approaches are the set of procedures, plans, and directions for implementing the programs and activities of the church. The growth of the church depends largely on its leadership effectiveness. Good leadership approaches enhance growth. In addition, leadership approaches create and sustain a good work environment, organizational culture, and fulfillment workers (believer).

Concept of Mission and Strategies for Missional Works

The history of Christian mission can be traced back to the early Christian church when Jesus sent the apostles to proclaim the gospel of Jesus Christ to all nations (Acts, 1:8). Mission is the divine activity of sending intermediaries (whether supernatural or human) to speak or do God's will so that his purposes for judgment or redemption are fulfilled (Little, 2008: 65-73). A missionary is a member of a religious group who is sent to a location to promote faith or provide services to people, such as education, literacy, social justice, health care, and economic development.

Biblically, the concept is expressed with the use of a verb, meaning 'to send', expressing God as the subject. In the Latin translation of the Bible, the word mission was used by Jesus Christ when he sent his disciples into the cities, commanding them to preach the gospel in his name. Mission is a Latin word "*Missio Dei*", which means the mission of God or "sending of God". It reveals the heart of God toward mankind concerning His divine plan of salvation for all the people of all nations of the world (Mudzanire). This term originated by St. Thomas Aquinas in the thirteenth century (World Mission Centre) and it is mostly used in referring to Christian mission. Christian mission is the plan of God to redeem mankind from the bondage of sin to Himself and to heal their

land. It is a form of outreach and evangelism which aims at reaching out to non-Christians to make them embrace the Christian faith (Goodman, 1995: 1-19). An aspect of the Christian mission based on social action, involves the provision of education, health care services, alleviation of human suffering, and the elimination of injustice, exploitation, and deprivation to demonstrate the love of God to humanity. This approach believes that social action is an integral part of missions as it goes along with evangelism and disciple making. Missions are therefore not only based on evangelism but also includes discipleship and church planting (Vaughan, 2022).

Christian missions have also been influenced by colonialism and imperialism. During the colonial era, the Europeans established missions as a tool to achieve political and economic gains in Africa (Nwaka and Onu, 2021). This led to the establishment of mission stations and schools that propagated Western culture and values alongside Christianity in Africa. As a result of these services, a scholar notes that the church performed more than just spiritual duties; it fed the hungry, taught modernized farming, carpentry, and animal husbandry (Măcelaru, 2023: 29-33). In the twenty-first century, missions in not only focused on evangelism, it goes along with social issues and also bring about the transformation of local communities. Therefore, twenty-first century missionaries in New Life For All Nations Ministries must be interculturalists to appreciate the culture of the people, as Christ's doctrine is focused on equality.

Christian missions in Nigeria have suffered many setbacks and barriers that have brought hindrances to the progress of missionary activities. These setbacks include poverty, a proliferation of churches, the inability to speak truth to the political class, and the vestiges of colonialism.

What are the leadership training approaches adopted by New Life College of Theology and Mission and their effectiveness on the growth of the church in Ibadan. In answering the research question: what are the leadership training approaches and programmes of New Life College of Theology and Mission? Figure 1 represents the model that presents the independent variables of the study (leadership approaches). The types

are transformational, democratic, laissez-faire, transactional, coaching, strategic, and autocratic. Effective leadership training approaches and strategies are essential in achieving organizations mission success (church growth). By understanding and implementing effective leadership training and their strategies, mission-driven organizations can foster collaboration, enhance performance, and achieve remarkable results. In addition, the relationship between the independent variables (leadership training approaches) and the dependent variable (church growth), hinges on a series of independent variables such as autocratic, diversity mismanagement, inequality, prosperity teaching, and finance. All these variables form complex actions that require integrated skills and knowledge to produce a valued result.

The New Life College of Theology and Mission also has different leadership training programmes, such as the women leadership programmes, and the youth and sisters/spinsters ministry. Women were actively involved in different crusade programmes through praise worship, intercessory prayers, crusade propagations, evangelism, caregiving, the welfare of brethren, mission and revival activities. This involves the interaction of the older females with the youth sisters or those that are unmarried for advice on real-life situations and experiences .

Theory of Performance

The Theory of Performance (ToP) develops and relates six foundational concepts to form a framework that can be used to explain performance as well as performance improvements. The six foundational concepts are: to perform, developing performance, level of performance, a performer's mindset, immersion in an enriching environment and engagement in reflective practice. To perform is to take a series of complex actions that integrate skills and knowledge to produce a valued result. A performer can be an individual or a group of people engaging in a collaborative effort. Developing performance is a journey, and level of performance describes location in the journey (Elger, 2007: 19). The theory shows that the current level of performance of leaders in New Life

Church depends holistically on the following six components, such as: context, level of knowledge, levels of skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors. The performer's mindset, immersion in an enriching environment and engagement in reflective practice are the three axioms proposed for effective performance improvement.

The theory of performance (ToP) is useful in many learning contexts. One of them is traditional context which includes learning in classrooms, workshops, and other venues that are traditionally associated with learning. Another setting is the non-traditional contexts i.e. learning in contexts that are not traditionally conceptualized as learning environments. Examples of which include academic advising, self-development, departments, academic committees, professional research groups, colleges. The third example is the organizational learning context which informs learning by organizations through the idea of examining the level of performance of the organization.

This study finds the organizational learning useful in the context which informs learning through the idea of examining the level of performance. The performance of a system, depends on the components of the system and the interactions between these components. As the levels of knowledge and skills increases, the level of performance also increases. Components that holistically interact to establish the level of performance are levels of identity, levels of skills, level of knowledge, the context of performance, personal factors and fixed factors (Elger, 2007: 19-22.)

For any organization to have a successful performance, they must be able to adapt to the changes and developments in their environment using the right resources with effective methods. In order for the performance of an organization to be positively affected, the leaders need to consider factors such as the organization's structure, systems, management programs, human resources, reliability of activities and processes, environmental compliance, and competitive strategy. Leaders should also adopt flexible leadership approaches in ensuring organizational performance instead of adopting a single leadership style (Vijaya et. al 2022).

Leaders should regularly review the gains and losses of the organization in relation to the factors mentioned above, analyze the potential synergy in the organization and improve the existing synergy while making decisions to increase performance. In conclusion, since leadership is a dynamic process and the relationship between the leader and the followers requires a two-way interaction, effective leadership interaction should be carried out depending on both the followers and the organizational performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for Leadership Training Approaches in New Life College of Theology and Mission (Interview codes)
 Source: Researchers’ Concept and Fieldwork, 2024

All the variables used in Figure 1 were generated from the fieldwork. From the 20 interview sessions conducted, ten interviewees are in the category of trainers, while the other ten interviewees are in the category of trainees. 70% of trainers mentioned that the approach of the leaders at the New Life College of Theology and Mission is rigid. On the other hand, 60% of the trainees also mentioned rigidity in the approach of the leaders at the New Life College of Theology and Mission. This means that the leadership needs more flexibility and the rigidity in the approach of the college is autocratic but strategic in nature. However, this approach

is injurious to church growth, as this trumps new ideas and innovation. Both categories of respondents (trainees and trainers) corroborated that the leadership does not give room for certain doctrines that are acceptable in other churches. On the reasons for the rigidity approach, all the interviewees in the trainers' category mentioned that "the leadership of the college believes mainly in gathering people who are heavenly bound". The respondents from the group corroborated that the leadership is not focused on having large congregations but few that have the focus of making heaven". This response appeals to the transformational and missional independent variables in Figure 1 in such ways that the approach of the leaders at the New Life College of Theology and Mission is directed at individuals who are interested in heaven and not numerical strength of the church. As argued previously, the concept of church growth involves more than number of congregants, but a wholistic approach to winning 'souls', discipleship, and community-building.

At this point, it is pertinent to ask: does New Life College of Theology and Mission have any cross-cultural mission strategies in place? An important puzzle is the adaption of other cultural groups in leadership positions of the church and college. All the respondents (both trainees and trainers) mentioned that the effort to language learning is individual and no curriculum is in place for interculturality, conflict resolution, and language courses. This means that New Life College of Theology and Mission has no course in the curriculum of the school for missionaries to learn languages outside their ethnicity. Language learning for missionary trainers will help improve the relationship between the diverse cultures within the church. However, the trainees make an effort to learn other languages from their colleagues. The inability to manage diversity can affect the church negatively. For instance, only 4 out of 23 branches of New Life Church established in Ibadan have non-Yoruba speaking pastors. In another light, the research inquired which of the theological orientations of New Life College of Theology and Mission contributed to the growth of New Life For All Nations Ministries, Ibadan.

All the trainers selected (ten) for the study also mentioned that cross-cultural mission strategies are not part of the curriculum.

In the bid to unravel reasons for the failure of the approaches of leadership training in New Life College of Theology and Mission, one of the major challenges for church growth is the position of women on issues relating to equality in New Life Church. It is pertinent to note that all the respondents were males as no missionary trainer is a female. Therefore, no female is allowed in the position of authority. According to all the trainers, the church also did not focus on prosperity preaching and forbade tithe and offering to the church for a long time. This also affected the finances of the church as missionaries survived with little or no means to support the mission fields and their families. Inadequate education is also another factor that affects the proficiency of the Church leaders.

Conclusion

Mission strategies play a crucial role in the growth of the Church. By identifying and refining these mission strategies, the church can effectively reach out to the community, engage its members, and attract new followers. The theological orientations of the Church are deeply intertwined with its mission strategies. Understanding the theological foundations that guide the mission efforts can help align the actions of the church with its beliefs, creating a more cohesive and impact outreach programme.

The leadership of the institution do not believe in gathering crowds (quantity) but in gathering heavenly bound citizens. The system adopted is believed to be effective because twenty-three branches of the Church has been established in Ibadan. There is a conflict resolution committee in place to resolve culturally sensitive conflicts.

For the church to grow, leaders also need to impact the lives of the people in their communities. With the current economic situation of Nigeria, high rate of unemployment, and corruption, the twenty-first century mission-based church need to contribute to the improvement of the economic condition of the country. This could be achieved by engaging

in economic ventures that can produce the required wealth to reduce poverty. The leadership of the church should also engage in the promotion of education by investing in the building of schools and recruiting qualified teachers to teach in such schools, with proper supervision (Ligia-Mariana, 2023)

Recommendations

1. The institution needs to adopt a curriculum that is not stereotyped, but one that can accommodate the 21st century mission.
2. For leadership to be effective and productive in the 21st century, there must be a willingness to welcome new ideas.
3. Effective leadership also requires leaders to be able to drive the organisation's objectives, cooperate with people, establish effective groups, and be technologically proficient.
4. Effective communication, problem-solving abilities, interpersonal skills, human relations skills, teamwork, good judgment and perseverance, and the capacity to create organizational capacities.
5. Based on the findings, advanced courses on intercultural communication and conflict resolution should be included in the curriculum of the college to improve their communication skills and also equip missionaries with the tools to manage church conflict that may arise among congregants whose ethnicity is different from the missionary in residence.
6. The college must also appreciate different beliefs and through the improved curriculum, missionaries must also learn other people's languages and cultures, and seek ways of adapting to their ways of life.
7. Missionaries must also have training on intercultural relations. This will help trainees of different cultural cues that make improve missional and evangelism works.
8. As transformational leaders continue to learn and improve themselves and others, the New Life College of Theology and

Mission graduates must also be equipped with conflict resolution skills to address the problems of undergrowth.

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Leadership Roles in Overcoming the Challenges of Multiculturalism in Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation in Mubi, Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

In any organization, whether private or public, the ability to achieve the set goals depends on the leadership skills of the management. Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF) in Mubi, Adamawa State, Nigeria is a multicultural and non-governmental organization (NGO) that seeks to take the gospel of Jesus to the unreached people and also engage in rural development of the community. This paper aims to investigate the relevance and the effects of good leadership in a multicultural setting like the CDMF. This paper researches how leaders of CDMF explore leadership training, skills, and styles to annex workers of various cultural backgrounds and perspectives to work in unity and harmony towards organizational goals and effectiveness in non-governmental organizations. This paper looks at why the staff of this Non-Governmental Organization in Nigeria, keep holding the fort, despite the problems that multiculturalism presents in today's globalization. The focus is to research, analyse, and make suggestions on how the NGO overcomes the cultural shock its face in the process of carrying out its mandates among people of different cultures. Transformational Leadership Theory is the theory deployed for the study. The central research question is: Why did the work of Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF) spread beyond Mubi Local Government Area of Adamawa State Nigeria to Cameroon and Chad despite being an NGO? The methodology deployed was Rigorous literature review on leadership, missionary work, and challenges of multiculturalism organizations. Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation Mubi, Adamawa State, Nigeria was used as a case study. The finding was that servant-leadership style deployed by the organization negates the challenges of multiculturalism in non-governmental organizations. It is recommended that workers in a new community should be encouraged to learn the language and the norms of the

host community to know why the people behave the way they behave. The understanding of cultural intelligence theory and the application of it, help the missionaries to overcome culture shock in various communities. In conclusion, the ultimate goal of an organization will be achieved if the right leadership style is deployed.

Keywords: Leadership Roles, Multiculturalism, Non-Governmental Organization (NGO), Culture Shock

Introduction

The world business situation today is characterized by cultural diversity. The world has become a global village, so organizations are becoming multicultural and diversity is becoming very pronounced, obvious, and necessary. Leaders of multicultural organizations are faced with the challenges of managing interpersonal differences between their employees as a result of cultural differences. In any organization, whether private, public, for-profit, or non-profit the success of the organization in achieving the set goals depends on how the leadership team effectively manages the interpersonal differences. According to Nguyen & Umasshankar, (2020), leaders can help to promote inclusivity, understanding and respect among diverse cultural groups. Man is endowed with inherent behaviour, variation in our behavioural endowment stimulates us to react to situations in different ways. Leaders, therefore, must possess the ability to know why workers behave the way they behave. Leaders should possess the ability to diffuse tension among workers.

Cultural diversity and emotional diversity, if not properly managed can cause communication gap in a multicultural setting. Cultural diversity can include ethnicity, religious belief, gender, race, language, worldview perspective, and nationality to mention just a few. The worldview of an individual depends on his or her past background. A man thinks along the way he has been taught to view other people's language, dress, or mode of dressing. If he has been taught that his race is the most superior, on the planet, he tends to look down on any other human beings. He tends to relegate whosoever he meets to second-class citizens even his

bosses. He feels superior to everyone else, his juniors, colleagues, or senior officers around him.

Cultural diversity, if not properly addressed by well-trained managers with good leadership skills, can break the organization's peace and harmony of staff. It can reduce effectiveness and efficiency. It reduces staff performance and invariably production level. Thus, leaders' roles in a multicultural environment are crucial in reducing interpersonal conflicts. Leveraging cultural diversity to bring about good understanding and promoting peace is a good quality of leaders.

This paper seeks to discuss leadership quality in the context of cultural diversity in a multicultural organization at Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation. It analyses the cultural perspectives of workers and brings arguments on why they behave the way they behave. It suggests what the leaders of multicultural organizations should do to enhance staff effectiveness.

Historical background of Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF)

Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF) started in 1985, when two young university graduates "claimed" to have been called to reach the Fali tribe of Mubi Hills in Adamawa State with the Gospel of Jesus Christ, having met in a school of mission. One is from Ibadan, Oyo State while the other is from Edo State. Two of them after their missionary training moved to the then Gongola state in "obedience" to God's instruction. Some Fali people were animists, particularly, the Julvu tribe and they live on the Mandara Mountain. This is the mountain between the borders of Nigeria and Cameroon. This couple later got married in 1985. Fali people engaged in farming and rearing of animals. At that time, they were separated from all kinds of social amenities and civilization. On climbing Mandara Mountain the first cultural shock that met this couple was that the women were wearing leaves. They also had communication problems because the Fali people neither spoke English nor Hausa since there was no established school in their community. With determination, this couple learned the Hausa language. With the

a team must work in good understanding of one another to make their efforts productive.

2. *Non-governmental Organization (NGO)*: The term, non-governmental organization (NGO), refers to a “voluntary group of individuals or organizations, usually not affiliated with any government, that is formed to provide services or to advocate a public policy” (Karns, 2024). NGOs are sometimes referred to as Non-Profit Organizations (NPOs) since these organizations also use money to run the organization. They can generate income but the profit generated is not distributed to the directors.
3. *Culture Shock*: “Culture shock refers to feelings of uncertainty, confusion or anxiety that people may experience when moving to a new country or experiencing a new culture or surroundings” (Segal, 2022). Culture shock is normal and can be stressful. The more a person prepares for culture shock when moving to a different environment, the easier to adjust to the culture.
4. *Leadership Role*: A rigorous book review has shown that leadership is not easy to define. The fields of Sociology, Psychology and various management fields have various interpretations of the word leadership according to the perspectives of their profession. However, leadership is a noun that comes from a verb “to lead” meaning, to go in front of others and to influence others by example, by words, and by action. “It is an act by either word or deed to influence behaviour toward a desired end.” Maxwell (2013) and Owen (2012) define leadership as influencing others. Thus, leadership is the ability to make others do what the leader must have loved to do. Northouse (2019) argues that leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal. Jackson and Parry (2008) describe leadership as a process during which leaders use their skills and knowledge to lead and direct a group of employees toward the desired direction that is relevant to their organizational goals and objectives. In this regard, it is good to note that the role of a leader cannot be over-emphasized in guiding his followers to the right destination. It is also good to note

that to lead, it is not necessary to have formal authority or position. This researcher has seen a situation where a team leader is functional only in the classroom but someone else guides when the team gets to the field. Leadership is the ability to attract people and motivate them to complete a piece of task. Northouse (2009) states that leaders who possess strong leadership skills can influence others to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. These leadership skills include the ability to set goals, to encourage commitments by his actions, to build team understanding, to encourage team participation, and to ensure good results.

Theoretical Framework

One theoretical framework that has been deployed to this research is Transformational Leadership Theory. This theory was proposed by James MacGregor Burns in 1978. Bass and Riggio (2006) argue that transformational leaders inspire and motivate their followers to achieve a higher level of performance by promoting values such as integrity, trust, and ethical behaviour. Another theory is the concept of Servant Leadership. According to Greenleaf (1977), servant leaders prioritize the needs of others and aim to serve the common good. Eva et al (2019) found that servant-leadership style resulted in increased employee motivation and improved team performance. These theories are used to examine the roles of leaders.

Challenges of Multiculturalism

In a multicultural organization, prevalent and major challenges are:

- *Cultural Clashes*: Cultural clashes can lead to misunderstandings between workers and this can cause very strong conflict and social fragmentation.
- *Communication Challenges*: Because people speak different languages, this language barrier can lead to poor social interaction.
- *Relationships*: Damage relationships between workers of two different cultures due to pride, prejudice, and discrimination.

- *Identity Conflicts*: these occur when people live under the influence of multiple cultural identities. Balancing one's cultural upbringing with the multicultural norms of the community can be a rigorous exercise.

Multiculturalism Nature of Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF)

Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation exists in three different countries and eight Different cultures. The missionaries are also from different cultural backgrounds. The nature and goal of this work is to win souls to the kingdom of God. This goal is noble. So, missionaries come with the mind-set of achieving the prime goal of the organization. From the onset, multiculturalism is valued by the leadership because it is the best effort to forestall segregation and sectionalism.

The goal of the leadership is to raise leaders who will thrive in the cultural diversity of the Mission fields. The tribes are interwoven in their culture and intermarriage persists because of their closeness in their geographical locations. The missionaries who are from different cultural upbringings must not see any culture as the best or else, culture will emerge as their main topic instead of preaching the liberating word of God.

Leadership Style of Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation (CDMF)

Christ's Disciples Missionary Foundation as earlier mentioned is both a non-governmental and non-profit organization. The goal is not to make a profit but to win souls through the preaching of the gospel. From the onset, the leaders prioritize serving others and teach their followers to do the same. Out of many leadership styles available, some of the styles this organization uses include:

1. Laissez-faire leadership style
2. Democratic-participative leadership style
3. Manipulative-inspirational leadership style
4. Benevolent-autocratic leadership style

5. Autocratic-bureaucratic leadership style
6. Servant-leadership style

The leaders of the organization, looking critically at the main goal of the organization decided to put servant-leadership style as their priority. Servant-leadership style has been deployed by various organizations. Parris and Peachey (2013) found that servant-leadership positively influenced the organization's performance and employee satisfaction. In another corporate setting, the study found out that the servant leadership style increased employee motivation and improved team performance (Eva et al., 2019). This leadership style focuses on empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, and commitment to the growth of people (Spears, 2010). This leadership style contrasts with traditional leadership styles, where the leader's primary focus is the thriving of their organization, often at the expense of employees (Northouse (2018). In Gomez (2022)'s words "Leaders with this style serve their team and organization first. They don't prioritize their objectives." The leadership empowers the missionaries by training them to accept the culture of their host community. Accepting their culture includes, eating their food, dressing like them, learning their language, and respecting them. The organizational goal of CDMF is to win souls by preaching. The heathen will not listen to a new message if the norm of their culture is relegated. Humility and mutual respect are virtues that give servant leaders honour before their followers. Clement et al. (2011) put it this way "Mutual respect is a balanced give-and-take relationship that should exist between people because it is the only kind of relationship that helps them to co-exist peacefully and happily." Respect is given to cultural Norms whether within the multicultural missionary team or the norm of the culture of the host community where the missionary lives. "The Norm of culture is their way of life and their behaviours as dictated by the set rules and regulations of that society. It is the total of all the expectations, values, and aspirations of any given society" (Clement et al., 2011). Since servant leaders prioritize the goal of the organization, they can endure the culture shock of their host community. They do not laugh at the

perceived mistake of individuals since that behaviour might be the norm in their culture. They listen with empathy and must not be anti-native. They investigate why the natives behave the way they behave, identify the good part of the culture, and adjust their own life even if it is against their own culture. Looking for how to drive home his message by contextualizing the message to the culture of the native land.

Servant Leadership Style is Transformational

Understudying *modus operandi* and the missionary activities of CDMF, the researcher found out that every leader concentrates on the development of his followers. The team leader prioritizes the welfare of the team members therefore, he can make them good followers because they believe his decision is in their favour first. So, they obey his instructions. They trust him, take risks in their work, and become efficient and committed employees. These followers are empowered and they grow to become future servant leaders.

Teamwork is enhanced because everyone seeks the actualization of the organization's goals. Team collaboration is their greatest focus, everyone listens to innovative ideas and is ready to learn. Every positive idea leads to an increase in the stock of knowledge of every member of the team.

A servant leader makes the working environment conducive and employees feel valued and important. This leads to high retention of employees and increases in productivity. Missionaries face the work of evangelism with little effects of the culture shock of a new environment. Everyone wants to belong to a winning team. A servant leader puts trust in his team and the team respects their leader. He has not come to lord it over his team but to raise future leaders. A servant leader is constantly working himself out of his station by quickly raising indigenous leaders that will take over from him so he can raise more leaders in another station.

With this transformational attitude in every leader, CDMF staff was able to quickly spread servant leadership ideology beyond the Fali tribe and to neighbouring tribes in Nigeria, Cameroon, and Chad.

Multiculturalism and Sense of Ownership

The training arm of CDMF is structured to train leaders who will reproduce themselves. Theories of incarnation, identification, selection, delegation, and reproduction are emphasized. Trained leaders are sent to the natives to raise future leaders in the community. In other words, they are to transform the people and the environment. The method was to:

- Incarnate – to live with them in their environment. This gives them a sense of belonging and inclusiveness.
- Identify – means to relate with them in their cultural setting. Learn it, understand it, and practice it without prejudices.
- Select – means worthy leaders are to be chosen and trained as future servant leaders. The natives know from the beginning that they are worthy future leaders. All are allowed to excel, grow, and lead.
- Delegate – means give power to worthy members of the community as they grow in fulfilling the uttermost goal of the organization
- Reproduce – the result is that every leader working in the organization should be able to raise servant leaders who will be able to reproduce others.

This method gives every member of the organization a sense of belonging and ownership. No culture is seen as superior to another. Communication is done cross-culturally from one region to another.

Encouragement of Culture Understanding from One Ethnic Group to Another

The philosophy of cross-cultural communication is that no culture is perfect and no culture is totally bad. Development of cultural competence is encouraged and taught to all missionaries. Cultural competence is the ability to understand, appreciate and respect the differences and similarities between different cultures (Fawcett & Garton, 2020). All cultures have functional equivalents. “These are actions or expressions in one culture which have the same meaning but

different forms of expression in another culture” (Clement et al., 2011). CDMF missionaries are accepted in every culture because of their understanding of functional equivalents in cultures. They learn the language of every tribe, study their culture, and contextualize the gospel. So, they win the hearts of the community members fast.

Conclusion

Multiculturalism is becoming very popular because of globalization, yet it has benefits and numerous challenges. Any organization that wants to enjoy the benefits, must work round to overcome the challenges. One of the ways to overcome the challenges is to run the right kind of leadership style. The ultimate goal of the organization will be achieved if the right leadership style is deployed.

Recommendations

The servant Leadership style of administration has been tested among rural dwellers of Fali people in Mubi Local Government Area of Adamawa State Nigeria. The community has been transformed economically, socially, and spiritually. Therefore, these recommendations are given here:

1. Cultural Diversity can be a blessing if the Leaders have high cultural intelligence and are properly channelled.
2. For effective communication, workers in a new community should be encouraged to learn the language and the norms of the host community to know why people behave the way they behave.
3. The goal of every organization should be properly organized to know which leadership style will fit the management of the organization
4. Hostility will be reduced to the barest minimum if the culture of a group of people is not relegated by other cultures in the same community.

5. Intercultural competence should be developed through training for workers meant to work in multicultural organizations.

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Influence of Liberation Theology on Governance in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study delves into the complex relationship between liberation theology (a Theological approach that emphasized social justice, human rights and freedom) and governance in Nigeria, examining how religious ideals have shaped political decisions and social movements. Through a qualitative approach, incorporating semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and thematic analysis, this research reveals the intricate dynamics between religious leaders, political elites, and civil society organizations. The study highlights the significant role of liberation theology in mobilizing resistance against oppressive regimes, promoting social justice, and advocating for human rights in Nigeria. It explores how religious leaders have utilized liberation theology to challenge unjust systems, empower marginalized communities, and push for political reform. However, the research also examines the challenges and limitations of applying liberation theology in Nigeria's governance. These include the tension between religious ideals and political pragmatism, the risk of religious manipulation by political elites, and the difficulty of translating theological principles into concrete policy changes. The findings of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the intersection of religion and politics in Nigeria, shedding light on the potential of liberation theology to drive social change and promote just governance. The research also underscores the need

for continued critical engagement between religious leaders, political elites, and civil society organizations to address the complex social and political challenges facing Nigeria.

Keywords: Liberation Theology, Governance, Nigeria, Social Justice and Political Theology

Introduction

Liberation theology has been a significant force in shaping the political and social landscape of Nigeria, a country with a rich cultural heritage and a complex history of colonialism, military rule, and democratic governance (Adejumobi, 2000; Ihonvbere, 2000). This theology, which emerged in the 1960s and 1970s in Latin America, emphasizes the need for social justice, human rights, and grassroots empowerment (Gutiérrez, 1973; Boff, 1985). In Nigeria, liberation theology has influenced political decisions and social movements, particularly during the military regimes of the 1980s and 1990s (Ojo, 1997; Falola, 2001).

The intersection of liberation theology and governance in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted. On one hand, religious leaders have played a crucial role in mobilizing resistance against oppressive regimes, promoting social justice, and advocating for human rights (Kukah, 1999; Ojo, 2007). On the other hand, the application of liberation theology in Nigeria's governance has been challenged by the tension between religious and secular authority, the impact of corruption, and the need for inclusive decision-making processes (Ihonvbere, 2000; Adejumobi, 2000).

This study aims to explore the intersection of liberation theology and governance in Nigeria, examining how religious ideals have influenced political decisions and social movements. It will analyze the complex dynamics between religious leaders, political elites, and civil society organizations, highlighting the challenges and limitations of applying liberation theology in Nigeria's governance.

Clarification of Terms

Liberation Theology: A theological approach that emphasizes social justice, human rights, and grassroots empowerment, particularly among marginalized communities (Gutiérrez, 1973).

Governance: The process of decision-making and implementation of policies, programs, and projects that affect the lives of citizens, including the role of government, civil society, and religious institutions (Hyden, 2006).

Nigeria: A federal republic in West Africa, with a dense population of about 229.5 million (Worldometer 2024) and a complex history of colonialism, military rule, and democratic governance (Adejumobi, 2000).

Religious Leaders: Individuals who hold positions of authority within religious institutions, such as bishops and imams who play a significant role in shaping religious discourse and influencing political decisions (Kukah, 1999).

Political Elites: Individuals who hold positions of power and influence within the political sphere, including government officials, politicians, and policymakers (Ihonvbere, 2000).

Civil Society Organizations: Non-governmental organizations, community groups, and advocacy networks that promote social justice, human rights, and democratic governance (Falola, 2001).

Social Justice: The pursuit of fairness, equality, and human rights, particularly among marginalized communities, including the poor, women, and minority groups (Boff, 1985).

Human Rights: The universal principles and standards that protect the dignity, freedom, and well-being of individuals and communities (United Nations, 1948).

Grassroots Empowerment: The process of enabling marginalized communities to take control of their lives, resources, and decision-making processes (Gutiérrez, 1973).

Secular Authority: The legitimate power and influence of non-religious institutions, including government and civil society, in shaping public policy and decision-making (Ihonvbere, 2000).

By clarifying these terms, we can better understand the complex relationships between liberation theology, governance, and social justice in Nigeria.

Liberation Theology in Nigeria

Liberation theology has been a significant force in Nigeria, since the 1970s (Ojo, 1997). Nigerian theologians and scholars have adapted liberation theology to address local contexts, such as poverty, inequality, and political oppression (Kukah, 1999).

Key Features of Liberation Theology in Nigeria include:

1. Emphasis on social justice and human rights (Boff, 1985; Gutiérrez, 1973)
2. Critique of oppressive structures and systems (Ojo, 1997)
3. Advocacy for the poor and marginalized (Kukah, 1999)
4. Promotion of grassroots empowerment and community development (Gutiérrez, 1973)
5. Dialogue and collaboration between Christians and Muslims (Ojo, 2007)

Nigerian scholars have also developed unique perspectives on liberation theology, such as:

1. Enculturation theology, which emphasizes the importance of local culture and tradition (Orobator, 2008)
2. Afro-centric theology, which highlights the experiences and perspectives of African people (Nyamiti, 1995)

Barriers to Liberation Theology in Nigeria

Despite its significance, liberation theology faces several barriers in Nigeria, including:

1. *Religious Fundamentalism*: The rise of religious fundamentalism has hindered the acceptance of liberation theology, as some religious leaders view it as too radical or political (Kukah, 1999).
2. *Political Repression*: Government repression and censorship have limited the spread of liberation theology, as some regimes view it as a threat to their power (Ojo, 1997).

3. *Cultural and Traditional Barriers*: Traditional beliefs and cultural practices have sometimes hindered the acceptance of liberation theology, as some Nigerians view it as foreign or incompatible with local customs (Nyamiti, 1995).
4. *Economic Factors*: Poverty and economic inequality have limited access to education and resources, making it difficult for liberation theology to reach marginalized communities (Gutiérrez, 1973).
5. *Denominational and Sectarian Divisions*: Divisions within Christianity and Islam have hindered the unity and effectiveness of liberation theology, as different denominations and sects may have competing interests and agendas (Ojo, 2007).
6. *Lack of Institutional Support*: The lack of institutional support from churches and mosques has limited the impact of liberation theology, as some religious leaders may not prioritize social justice and activism (Kukah, 1999).

Despite the challenges, liberation theology has significant prospects in Nigeria, including:

1. *Promoting Social Justice*: Liberation theology can continue to advocate for the rights of marginalized communities, addressing issues like poverty, inequality, and political oppression (Gutiérrez, 1973).
2. *Empowering Local Communities*: Liberation theology can empower local communities to take control of their lives, resources, and decision-making processes, promoting grassroots development and self-reliance (Kukah, 1999).
3. *Fostering Interfaith Dialogue*: Liberation theology can facilitate dialogue and collaboration between Christians and Muslims, promoting mutual understanding and cooperation in addressing social and political issues (Ojo, 2007).
4. *Informing Public Policy*: Liberation theology can inform public policy, ensuring that government prioritizes the needs and rights of marginalized communities (Nyamiti, 1995).

5. *Nurturing Prophetic Leadership*: Liberation theology can nurture prophetic leadership, encouraging religious leaders to speak truth to power and advocate for justice and human rights (Boff, 1985).
6. *Enhancing Democracy*: Liberation theology can enhance democratic governance, promoting participatory decision-making, transparency, and accountability (Ojo, 1997).

Nigeria's governance has been characterized by:

1. *Political Instability*: Frequent regime changes, military interventions, and political violence have hindered democratic consolidation (Adejumobi, 2000).
2. *Corruption*: Widespread corruption has undermined public trust, accountability, and effective governance (Ihonvbere, 2000).
3. *Ethno-Religious Conflicts*: Ethnic and religious tensions have led to violent conflicts, threatening national unity and stability (Falola, 2001).
4. *Economic Mismanagement*: Poor economic policies, mismanagement, and dependence on oil exports have hindered sustainable development (Osaghae, 1998).
5. *Weak Institutions*: Ineffective institutions, including the judiciary, legislature, and civil service, have hindered good governance (Adejumobi, 2000).
6. *Patronage Politics*: Patronage networks and clientelism have undermined meritocracy, accountability, and public service delivery (Ihonvbere, 2000).

Liberation Theology and Governance in Nigeria

The integration of liberation theology and governance in Nigeria can be seen in:

1. *Social Justice Advocacy*: Religious leaders advocating for social justice, human rights, and good governance (Kukah, 1999).
2. *Community Development*: Faith-based organizations engaging in community development, education, and healthcare (Ojo, 2007).

3. *Political Activism*: Religious leaders participating in political activism, criticizing oppressive policies, and promoting democratic values (Gutiérrez, 1973).
4. *Interfaith Dialogue*: Collaboration between Christians and Muslims promoting mutual understanding, peacebuilding, and conflict resolution (Ojo, 2007).
5. *Policy Influence*: Religious leaders influencing policy decisions, ensuring governance prioritizes the needs of marginalized communities (Nyamiti, 1995).
6. *Prophetic Leadership*: Religious leaders speaking truth to power, advocating for justice, and holding leaders accountable (Boff, 1985).

Conclusion

Liberation theology has significantly influenced governance in Nigeria, promoting social justice, human rights, and community development. Despite challenges, the integration of liberation theology and governance has achieved notable successes. For instance, it has empowered marginalized communities (Gutiérrez, 1973), fostering a sense of ownership and participation in the governance process.

Furthermore, liberation theology has fostered interfaith dialogue and collaboration (Ojo, 2007), promoted a culture of tolerance and understood. It has also held leaders accountable for justice and human rights (Boff, 1985), ensuring that those in power prioritize the needs of the people. Additionally, liberation theology has informed public policy and governance (Nyamiti, 1995), providing a moral framework for decision-making. Lastly, it has nurtured prophetic leadership and advocacy (Kukah, 1999), inspiring a new generation of leaders to champion the cause of justice and equality.

However, challenges persist, including religious fundamentalism and extremism, political repression and corruption, cultural and traditional barriers, and economic inequality and poverty. To address these challenges, continued engagement between religious leaders, policymakers, and civil society is crucial. By integrating liberation

theology and governance, Nigeria can promote a more just, equitable, and peaceful society.

Recommendations

1. *Increased Collaboration:* Encourage collaboration between religious leaders, policymakers, and civil society to promote social justice and good governance.
2. *Religious Education:* Integrate liberation theology into religious education to raise awareness and promote critical thinking.
3. *Community Engagement:* Support community development projects and initiatives that address poverty, inequality, and social injustice.
4. *Policy Influence:* Encourage religious leaders to engage with policymakers to ensure governance prioritizes the needs of marginalized communities.
5. *Interfaith Dialogue:* Foster interfaith dialogue and collaboration to promote mutual understanding and address social and political challenges.
6. *Prophetic Leadership:* Nurture prophetic leadership that speaks truth to power and advocates for justice and human rights.
7. *Addressing Corruption:* Address corruption and promote transparency and accountability in governance and religious institutions.
8. *Economic Empowerment:* Support economic empowerment initiatives that address poverty and inequality.
9. *Conflict Resolution:* Encourage religious leaders to engage in conflict resolution and peace building initiatives.
10. *Continuous Research:* Conduct continuous research and analysis to understand the intersection of liberation theology and governance in Nigeria.

By implementing these recommendations, Nigeria can harness the potential of liberation theology to promote social justice, good governance, and human rights.

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